

Supplementary information Chapter 1

Supplementary tables Chapter 1

Table SI1: AIC table. To analyze the gut microbiomes of natural populations, different combinations of the fixed factors year (2014 vs 2017), region (Leuven, Kortrijk or Ghent) and population (the eight different populations) were tested. In addition, population was included as a random factor in the tested models, as multiple populations came from the same region. To analyze short-term dynamics the fixed factors time (different sampling days) and microbiome (timepoint 0 vs all other timepoints) were evaluated with a repeated measures model (i.e., time as a random factor, as multiple timepoints were sampled from the same aquarium). To analyze long-term dynamics, the fixed factors microbiome (natural vs lab) and population (the four different populations or clones) were included in the models tested.

Model	df	AIC
<u>Natural populations</u>		
<u>Species richness</u>		
<u>LMER</u>		
fit1 <- lmer(N0~ Year+Region+Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	11	73.69655
fit2 <- lmer(N0~ Year+Region + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	6	97.22006
fit3 <- lmer(N0~ Year+Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	11	73.69655
fit4 <- lmer(N0~ Region+Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	10	77.50134
fit5 <- lmer(N0~ Year + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	4	105.32982
fit6 <- lmer(N0~ Region + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	5	100.70270
fit7 <- lmer(N0~ Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	10	77.50134
<u>GLM</u>		
fit1 <- glm(N0~ Year*Region*Location , data=div_samp_A1)	16	-870.3771
fit2 <- glm(N0~ Year+Region+Location , data=div_samp_A1)	10	120.2350
fit3 <- glm(N0~ Year*Region , data=div_samp_A1)	7	111.5992
fit4 <- glm(N0~ Year+Region , data=div_samp_A1)	5	114.6025
fit5 <- glm(N0~ Year*Location, data=div_samp_A1)	16	-903.2134

fit6 <- glm(N0~ Year+Location, data=div_samp_A1)	10	120.2350
fit7 <- glm(N0~ Region*Location , data=div_samp_A1)	9	119.3879
fit8 <- glm(N0~ Region+Location , data=div_samp_A1)	9	119.3879
fit9 <- glm(N0~ Year , data=div_samp_A1)	3	111.5125
fit10 <- glm(N0~ Region , data=div_samp_A1)	4	113.3010
fit11 <- glm(N0~ Location , data=div_samp_A1)	9	119.3879
Shannon diversity		
<u>LMER</u>		
fit1 <- lmer(N1~ Year+Region+Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	11	55.24370
fit2 <- lmer(N1~ Year+Region + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	6	62.82639
fit3 <- lmer(N1~ Year+Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	11	55.24370
fit4 <- lmer(N1~ Region+Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	10	55.96134
fit5 <- lmer(N1~ Year + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	4	64.73705
fit6 <- lmer(N1~ Region + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	5	63.26610
fit7 <- lmer(N1~ Location + (1 Location), data=div_samp_A1)	10	55.96134
<u>GLM</u>		
fit1 <- glm(N1~ Year*Region*Location , data=div_samp_A1)	16	-943.39012
fit2 <- glm(N1~ Year+Region+Location , data=div_samp_A1)	10	74.10290
fit3 <- glm(N1~ Year*Region , data=div_samp_A1)	7	68.63333
fit4 <- glm(N1~ Year+Region , data=div_samp_A1)	5	67.70202
fit5 <- glm(N1~ Year*Location, data=div_samp_A1)	16	-943.25886
fit6 <- glm(N1~ Year+Location, data=div_samp_A1)	10	74.10290
fit7 <- glm(N1~ Region*Location , data=div_samp_A1)	9	73.23070
fit8 <- glm(N1~ Region+Location , data=div_samp_A1)	9	73.23070
fit9 <- glm(N1~ Year , data=div_samp_A1)	3	64.67468
fit10 <- glm(N1~ Region , data=div_samp_A1)	4	66.50524

fit11 <- glm(N1~ Location , data=div_samp_A1)	9	73.23070
Short-term experiment		
Species richness		
<u>LMER</u>		
fit1 <- lmer(N0~ Day*Microbiome +(1 Day), data=div_samp_B1GUT)	18	304.3391
fit2 <- lmer(N0~ Day +(1 Day), data=div_samp_B1GUT)	18	304.3391
fit3 <- lmer(N0~ Microbiome +(1 Day), data=div_samp_B1GUT)	4	377.1920
<u>LM</u>		
fit1 <- lm(N0~ Day*Microbiome , data=div_samp_B1GUT)	17	400.0817
fit2 <- lm(N0~ Day , data=div_samp_B1GUT)	17	400.0817
fit3 <- lm(N0~ Microbiome , data=div_samp_B1GUT)	3	385.2478
Shannon diversity		
<u>LMER</u>		
fit1 <- lmer(N1~ Day*Microbiome +(1 Day), data=div_samp_B1GUT)	18	206.1390
fit2 <- lmer(N1~ Day +(1 Day), data=div_samp_B1GUT)	18	206.1390
fit3 <- lmer(N1~ Microbiome +(1 Day), data=div_samp_B1GUT)	4	249.0086
<u>LM</u>		
fit1 <- lm(N1~ Day*Microbiome , data=div_samp_B1GUT)	17	249.5082
fit2 <- lm(N1~ Day , data=div_samp_B1GUT)	17	249.5082
fit3 <- lm(N1~ Microbiome , data=div_samp_B1GUT)	3	254.9881
Long-term experiment		
Species richness		
fit1 <- glm(N0~ Microbiome*Location , data=div_samp_C1)	9	92.50588
fit2 <- glm(N0~ Microbiome+Location , data=div_samp_C1)	6	86.92628
fit3 <- glm(N0~ Microbiome , data=div_samp_C1)	3	83.03999
fit4 <- glm(N0~ Location , data=div_samp_C1)	5	84.93380

Shannon diversity		
fit1 <- glm(N1~ Microbiome*Location , data=div_samp_C1)	9	60.31417
fit2 <- glm(N1~ Microbiome+Location , data=div_samp_C1)	6	55.08734
fit3 <- glm(N1~ Microbiome , data=div_samp_C1)	3	50.65489
fit4 <- glm(N1~ Location , data=div_samp_C1)	5	55.43372

Table SI2: Results of the post-hoc analysis on the species richness of the natural microbiomes.

contrast	estimate	SE	df	z.ratio	p.value
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Aalbeke	0.0833816089390542	0.288926047400332	Inf	0.288591526064529	0.99999999994688
2014 Aalbeke - 2014 Blauwe Hoeve	0.385662480811988	0.314362099181551	Inf	122.680.972.615.996	0.997866341471054
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Blauwe Hoeve	-0.788457360364267	0.241209075659535	Inf	-326.877.153.443.915	0.0809873879320034
2014 Aalbeke - 2014 Kennedy park	-0.518793793415165	0.252605470661588	Inf	-205.377.101.317.883	0.794472216130709
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Kennedy park	-0.336472236621211	0.261861468280322	Inf	-128.492.457.798.724	0.9964504408954
2014 Aalbeke - 2014 Morrinestraat	0.127833371509889	0.292326094372163	Inf	0.437297162213452	0.99999997661227
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Morrinestraat	-0.732367893713223	0.243373723375122	Inf	-300.923.157.831.791	0.16474340803152
2014 Aalbeke - 2014 Muink	-0.565313809050057	0.250454132978338	Inf	-225.715.504.203.299	0.655823235549938
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Muink	0.127833371509889	0.292326094372163	Inf	0.437297162213452	0.99999997661227
2014 Aalbeke - 2014 Oude Meren	-0.246860077931522	0.266926956297719	Inf	-0.924822585757075	0.999928215515758
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Oude Meren	-0.277631736598276	0.265147186108861	Inf	-104.708.535.916.458	0.99966377857447
2014 Aalbeke - 2014 Wevelgem	0.0833816089390549	0.288926047400332	Inf	0.288591526064531	0.99999999994688
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Wevelgem	0.0833816089390548	0.288926047400333	Inf	0.288591526064531	0.99999999994688
2014 Aalbeke - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014 Aalbeke - 2017 Zwevegem	0.0408219945202588	0.285773803319772	Inf	0.142847224084358	1
2017 Aalbeke - 2014 Blauwe Hoeve	0.302280871872934	0.319846510487051	Inf	0.945081037190718	0.999905523999418
2017 Aalbeke - 2017 Blauwe Hoeve	-0.871838969303321	0.24831447611736	Inf	-351.102.756.043.618	0.0379379238419907
2017 Aalbeke - 2014 Kennedy park	-0.602175402354219	0.259398891048274	Inf	-232.142.627.873.515	0.607574826112213
2017 Aalbeke - 2017 Kennedy park	-0.419853845560265	0.268420732133041	Inf	-156.416.325.305.367	0.974517246045147

2017 Aalbeke - 2014 Morrinesstraat	0.0444517625708343	0.298216039675593	Inf	0.149058925935674	1
2017 Aalbeke - 2017 Morrinesstraat	-0.815749502652277	0.250417711231418	Inf	-325.755.514.113.145	0.083699291571054
2017 Aalbeke - 2014 Muink	-0.648695417989111	0.257304359844218	Inf	-25.211.209.727.727	0.455709079270944
2017 Aalbeke - 2017 Muink	0.0444517625708344	0.298216039675593	Inf	0.149058925935675	1
2017 Aalbeke - 2014 Oude Meren	-0.330241686870576	0.273364703038406	Inf	-120.806.264.744.494	0.998204734089946
2017 Aalbeke - 2017 Oude Meren	-0.36101334553733	0.271627117884719	Inf	-132.907.696.532.181	0.994904390052661
2017 Aalbeke - 2014 Wevelgem	6,66E-02	0.294883912303284	Inf	2,26E-01	1
2017 Aalbeke - 2017 Wevelgem	6,38E-02	0.294883912303284	Inf	2,16E-01	1
2017 Aalbeke - 2014 Zwevegum	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017 Aalbeke - 2017 Zwevegum	-0.0425596144187954	0.291796037554933	Inf	-0.145853983403675	1
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Blauwe Hoeve	-117.411.984.117.626	0.277498374022067	Inf	-423.108.728.227.318	0.00246088566049119
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Kennedy park	-0.904456274227153	0.28745965493009	Inf	-314.637.640.001.034	0.114764721443932
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Kennedy park	-0.722134717433199	0.295626382405715	Inf	-24.427.275.791.717	0.514842332111554
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Morrinesstraat	-0.2578291093021	0.322921158884405	Inf	-0.798427424801836	0.999989395857835
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Morrinesstraat	-111.803.037.452.521	0.279381994111708	Inf	-400.179.824.787.914	0.00632537694730118
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Muink	-0.950976289862045	0.285571010661613	Inf	-333.008.692.884.763	0.0674086168846193
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Muink	-0.257829109302099	0.322921158884405	Inf	-0.798427424801835	0.999989395857835
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Oude Meren	-0.63252255874351	0.300122523984336	Inf	-210.754.777.864.164	0.760626172588028
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Oude Meren	-0.663294217410264	0.29854071699822	Inf	-222.178.811.680.894	0.681732391211965
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Wevelgem	-0.302280871872933	0.319846510487051	Inf	-0.945081037190716	0.999905523999418
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Wevelgem	-0.302280871872933	0.319846510487051	Inf	-0.945081037190715	0.999905523999418
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Zwevegum	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Zwevegum	-0.344840486291729	0.317001886537307	Inf	-10.878.184.040.433	0.999468010925626
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Kennedy park	0.269663566949103	0.204917890851976	Inf	131.595.911.820.065	0.995413421772147
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Kennedy park	0.451985123743056	0.216224991046331	Inf	209.034.636.355.336	0.771712171506044
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Morrinesstraat	0.916290731874156	0.252262489549958	Inf	363.229.084.716.019	0.0251273456473263
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Morrinesstraat	0.0560894666510441	0.193423337300673	Inf	0.289982932948024	0.99999999994297
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Muink	0.22314355131421	0.202259958738725	Inf	110.325.124.510.908	0.99937112495021

2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Muink	0.916290731874156	0.252262489549958	Inf	363.229.084.716.019	0.0251273456473263
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Oude Meren	0.541597282432745	0.222332674569943	Inf	24.359.770.037.416	0.519993712330403
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Oude Meren	0.510825623765991	0.220192753024497	Inf	231.990.207.102.393	0.608731884646735
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Wevelgem	0.871838969303322	0.24831447611736	Inf	351.102.756.043.618	0.0379379238419911
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Wevelgem	0.871838969303322	0.24831447611736	Inf	351.102.756.043.618	0.0379379238419905
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017 Blauwe Hoeve - 2017 Zwevegem	0.829279354884526	0.244639499768348	Inf	338.980.154.745.975	0.0560637385730357
2014 Kennedy park - 2017 Kennedy park	0.182321556793954	0.228868854107808	Inf	0.796620219490729	0.999989710275399
2014 Kennedy park - 2014 Morrinestraat	0.646627164925053	0.263180677979174	Inf	245.697.051.124.787	0.503995998248408
2014 Kennedy park - 2017 Morrinestraat	-0.213574100298058	0.207461545931205	Inf	-102.946.355.354.395	0.999726533771301
2014 Kennedy park - 2014 Muink	-0.0465200156348921	0.215723889582555	Inf	-0.215646100786114	1
2014 Kennedy park - 2017 Muink	0.646627164925053	0.263180677979175	Inf	245.697.051.124.787	0.503995998248408
2014 Kennedy park - 2014 Oude Meren	0.271933715483643	0.234647658861237	Inf	115.890.231.679.002	0.998882156373005
2014 Kennedy park - 2017 Oude Meren	0.241162056816889	0.232621052598732	Inf	103.671.638.539.479	0.999702082600888
2014 Kennedy park - 2014 Wevelgem	0.60217540235422	0.259398891048274	Inf	232.142.627.873.515	0.607574826112211
2014 Kennedy park - 2017 Wevelgem	0.60217540235422	0.259398891048274	Inf	232.142.627.873.515	0.607574826112212
2014 Kennedy park - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014 Kennedy park - 2017 Zwevegem	0.559615787935423	0.25588315785636	Inf	218.699.734.919.468	0.706620126972585
2017 Kennedy park - 2014 Morrinestraat	0.464305608131099	0.272077147190538	Inf	170.652.189.250.552	0.945631302798769
2017 Kennedy park - 2017 Morrinestraat	-0.395895657092012	0.218637137289	Inf	-181.074.295.977.772	0.913076058021456
2017 Kennedy park - 2014 Muink	-0.228841572428846	0.226492166086136	Inf	-101.037.301.370.422	0.99978262821997
2017 Kennedy park - 2017 Muink	0.464305608131099	0.272077147190538	Inf	170.652.189.250.552	0.945631302798769
2017 Kennedy park - 2014 Oude Meren	0.0896121586896886	0.244584195259675	Inf	0.366385729031049	0.99999999821818
2017 Kennedy park - 2017 Oude Meren	0.0588405000229348	0.242640596096172	Inf	0.242500640740319	1
2017 Kennedy park - 2014 Wevelgem	0.419853845560266	0.268420732133041	Inf	156.416.325.305.367	0.974517246045147
2017 Kennedy park - 2017 Wevelgem	0.419853845560266	0.268420732133041	Inf	156.416.325.305.367	0.974517246045147
2017 Kennedy park - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017 Kennedy park - 2017 Zwevegem	0.37729423114147	0.26502470684128	Inf	142.361.908.683.263	0.989662530319744

2014 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Morrinesstraat	-0.860201265223112	0.254333078231845	Inf	-338.218.398.960.661	0.0574146119282564
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Muink	-0.693147180559945	0.261116483928814	Inf	-265.455.160.137.999	0.360425401014354
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Muink	6,94E-03	0.301511344569816	Inf	2,30E-02	1
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Oude Meren	-0.374693449441411	0.276955854698506	Inf	-135.289.954.368.108	0.993859225756735
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Oude Meren	-0.405465108108164	0.275240941276661	Inf	-147.312.789.379.181	0.98552020533197
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Wevelgem	-0.0444517625708337	0.298216039675593	Inf	-0.149058925935672	1
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Wevelgem	-0.0444517625708337	0.298216039675593	Inf	-0.149058925935672	1
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Zwevegem	-0.0870113769896297	0.295163026338434	Inf	-0.294790909515416	0.99999999992731
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Muink	0.167054084663166	0.204836622599412	Inf	0.815547935438601	0.999985955641561
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Muink	0.860201265223112	0.254333078231845	Inf	338.218.398.960.661	0.0574146119282567
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Oude Meren	0.485507815781701	0.224679258567335	Inf	216.089.290.519.088	0.724834524471912
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Oude Meren	0.454736157114947	0.222561900453447	Inf	204.318.958.540.734	0.800840682332901
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Wevelgem	0.815749502652278	0.250417711231418	Inf	325.755.514.113.145	0.0836992915710532
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Wevelgem	0.815749502652278	0.250417711231418	Inf	325.755.514.113.145	0.0836992915710542
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017 Morrinesstraat - 2017 Zwevegem	0.773189888233482	0.246774058393201	Inf	313.318.949.839.334	0.118985278313479
2014 Muink - 2017 Muink	0.693147180559945	0.261116483928814	Inf	265.455.160.137.999	0.360425401014356
2014 Muink - 2014 Oude Meren	0.318453731118535	0.232330094320189	Inf	13.706.951.398.197	0.992967255675137
2014 Muink - 2017 Oude Meren	0.287682072451781	0.230283093235068	Inf	124.925.398.738.726	0.997390817130484
2014 Muink - 2014 Wevelgem	0.648695417989112	0.257304359844218	Inf	25.211.209.727.727	0.455709079270943
2014 Muink - 2017 Wevelgem	0.648695417989112	0.257304359844218	Inf	25.211.209.727.727	0.455709079270945
2014 Muink - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014 Muink - 2017 Zwevegem	0.606135803570315	0.253759609458069	Inf	238.862.206.978.007	0.556242789366957
2017 Muink - 2014 Oude Meren	-0.374693449441411	0.276955854698506	Inf	-135.289.954.368.108	0.993859225756735
2017 Muink - 2017 Oude Meren	-0.405465108108165	0.275240941276661	Inf	-147.312.789.379.181	0.98552020533197
2017 Muink - 2014 Wevelgem	-0.0444517625708337	0.298216039675593	Inf	-0.149058925935672	1
2017 Muink - 2017 Wevelgem	-0.0444517625708337	0.298216039675593	Inf	-0.149058925935672	1

2017 Muink - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017 Muink - 2017 Zwevegem	-0.0870113769896297	0.295163026338435	Inf	-0.294790909515416	0.999999999992731
2014 Oude Meren - 2017 Oude Meren	-0.0307716586667539	0.248098831723053	Inf	-0.124029841063917	1
2014 Oude Meren - 2014 Wevelgem	0.330241686870577	0.273364703038406	Inf	120.806.264.744.494	0.998204734089946
2014 Oude Meren - 2017 Wevelgem	0.330241686870577	0.273364703038406	Inf	120.806.264.744.494	0.998204734089946
2014 Oude Meren - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014 Oude Meren - 2017 Zwevegem	0.287682072451781	0.270030862430102	Inf	106.536.738.009.437	0.99958558137402
2017 Oude Meren - 2014 Wevelgem	0.361013345537331	0.271627117884719	Inf	132.907.696.532.181	0.994904390052661
2017 Oude Meren - 2017 Wevelgem	0.361013345537331	0.271627117884719	Inf	132.907.696.532.181	0.994904390052661
2017 Oude Meren - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017 Oude Meren - 2017 Zwevegem	0.318453731118535	0.268271684990846	Inf	118.705.681.193.825	0.998528176041048
2014 Wevelgem - 2017 Wevelgem	-2,78E-03	0.294883912303284	Inf	-9,41E-03	1
2014 Wevelgem - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2014 Wevelgem - 2017 Zwevegem	-0.042559614418796	0.291796037554933	Inf	-0.145853983403678	1
2017 Wevelgem - 2014 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017 Wevelgem - 2017 Zwevegem	-0.042559614418796	0.291796037554933	Inf	-0.145853983403677	1
2014 Zwevegem - 2017 Zwevegem	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table SI3: Relative abundance of the gut microbiomes of the natural *D. magna* populations at the ASV level.

ASV	2014 Aalbeke	2017 Aalbeke	2014 Blauwe Hoeve	2017 Blauwe Hoeve	2014 Kennedy park	2017 Kennedy park	2014 Morraine straat	2017 Morraine straat	2014 Muink	2017 Muink	2014 Oude Meren	2017 Oude Meren	2014 Wevelgem	2017 Wevelgem	2017 Zwevegem
ASV_2_Candidatus Bacilloplasma_sp.	65,41	0,00	89,68	31,02	2,95	0,07	1,59	0,02	64,55	0,04	64,30	0,15	6,57	0,00	1,19
ASV_1_Comamonadaceae	0,00	1,51	0,08	10,97	0,00	34,31	0,00	35,98	0,03	8,71	0,00	3,22	0,00	65,64	45,12
ASV_11_Pseudomonadales	0,00	80,87	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	84,05	0,34	0,91	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_4_Candidatus Hepatinticola	0,00	2,46	0,04	0,22	82,92	0,22	0,28	0,67	23,85	0,06	0,14	23,10	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_5_Rickettsiales	27,81	0,02	0,27	1,13	5,49	1,00	33,55	40,55	4,46	0,00	0,00	1,01	0,03	0,00	0,00
ASV_7_Bacilli	0,00	0,00	1,93	0,90	2,29	0,28	49,97	0,00	1,69	0,47	0,00	0,12	24,98	0,00	0,00

ASV_14_Streptococcus_sp.	0,06	3,60	0,00	0,16	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	65,83	0,00	0,03	0,04
ASV_12_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,03	0,30	2,29	0,00	40,24	0,02	0,00	0,00	4,65	0,03	0,49	0,00	0,00	17,23
ASV_8_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,00	0,03	0,00	2,72	0,04	5,42	0,00	0,04	0,61	0,44	0,17	1,11	0,01	6,52	32,56
ASV_13_Babeliales	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	1,84	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,09	47,04	0,00	0,00
ASV_22_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	26,93	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,18	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,27
ASV_23_Pasteuria_sp.	0,00	4,25	0,00	0,00	0,39	2,68	10,33	0,55	0,88	0,58	0,00	0,07	6,74	0,00	0,00
ASV_16_Enterobacterales	1,22	0,06	3,67	0,14	0,37	3,30	2,06	0,41	0,56	0,04	6,49	0,16	4,92	0,05	0,00
ASV_20_Alcaligenaceae	0,02	0,00	0,00	1,65	1,02	0,85	0,38	0,45	0,44	0,35	8,56	0,03	0,00	5,82	0,00
ASV_35_Bacteroidia	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	18,92	0,00
ASV_18_Microbacteriaceae	0,02	0,03	3,13	0,36	0,05	0,03	0,31	10,11	0,32	0,00	1,78	0,43	0,02	0,04	0,50
ASV_9_Emticicia_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	7,86	0,00	0,00	0,14	1,54	0,02	0,00	2,32	0,10	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_17_Lacihabitans_sp.	0,00	0,23	0,00	0,53	0,00	7,72	0,00	0,27	0,02	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_3_Burkholderiales	0,01	6,27	0,01	0,14	0,17	0,00	0,00	0,15	0,13	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_25_Chitinophagales	0,00	0,00	0,00	4,43	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,82	0,00	0,08	0,00	0,05	0,00	1,18	0,00
ASV_40_Methyloparacoccus_sp.	0,57	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,02	0,00	3,62	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,13	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_28_Verrucomicrobiaceae	3,78	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_41_Steroidobacteraceae	0,10	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,24	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,05	0,00	3,06	0,06	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_6_Polynucleobacter_sp.	0,00	0,38	0,00	0,18	0,49	0,14	0,00	1,28	0,00	0,00	0,69	0,06	0,00	0,00	0,28
ASV_39_Bacilli	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,38	0,00	0,20	0,00	2,33	0,00	0,25	0,00	0,01
ASV_36_Acidibacter_sp.	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,06	0,00	0,00	0,00	2,94	0,00	0,00
ASV_70_Saprospiraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	2,47	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,14	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,25	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_52_Methylophilaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,76	0,00	0,00	0,16	0,15	0,01	0,00	1,33	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,21
ASV_65_Paenibacillus_sp.	0,00	0,09	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	2,13	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_37_Legionella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	2,23	0,00	0,00
ASV_27_Pedobacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,40	0,00	0,49	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_43_Sva0485	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,63	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_15_Acinetobacter_sp.	0,06	0,00	0,20	0,03	0,22	0,07	0,09	0,00	0,20	0,00	0,26	0,00	0,21	0,00	0,27
ASV_46_Isosphaeraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,54	0,00	0,00
ASV_57_Chitinophagales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,23	0,00	1,28	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_76_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,38	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_31_Rhodobacteraceae	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,24	0,00	0,76	0,02	0,00	0,06	0,05	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,16

ASV_26_Pseudarcicella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,43	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,74	0,00
ASV_59_SC-I-84	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,13	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_49_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,10	0,00	1,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_30_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,09	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,92
ASV_10_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,05	0,26	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,53	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,07	0,00
ASV_53_Massilia_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,95	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_56_Mitochondria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,90	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_48_Actibacter_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,09	0,27	0,00	0,27	0,00	0,20	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_58_Methylobacterium- Methylorubrum_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,18	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,59	0,00	0,00
ASV_51_Absconditabacteriales (SR1)	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,08	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,69	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_29_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,10	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,62
ASV_114_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,67	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_62_Solirubrobacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,65	0,00	0,00
ASV_88_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,18	0,00	0,08	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,06	0,00	0,09	0,00	0,14	0,00
ASV_66_Pirellula_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,49	0,00	0,00
ASV_107_Holospora_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,40	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_67_Gracilibacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,23	0,00	0,07	0,00	0,00
ASV_126_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,16	0,16
ASV_68_Gracilibacteria	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_74_Absconditabacteriales (SR1)	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,34	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_33_Algoriphagus_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,33	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_34_Spirosomaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_64_Arenicellaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,33	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_38_Clostridium sensu stricto 1_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,28	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01
ASV_77_Intrasporangiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,31	0,00	0,00
ASV_125_Chitinophagaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,08	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,18	0,00
ASV_71_Pirellula_sp.	0,28	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_82_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,09	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,18	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_81_Thiothrix_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,14	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,07	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,06

ASV_156_Rickettsiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_166_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_167_Verrucomicrobiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_168_Micrococcales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_169_Aminicenantales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_171_Microbacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_184_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_185_Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_186_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00
ASV_120_Rhizobiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_127_Pedosphaeraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_109_Sulfurovum_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_128_Illumatobacteraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_130_Fluviicola_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_153_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_165_Enterobacterales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_183_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_138_Corynebacteriales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_158_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02
ASV_73_Shinella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00
ASV_106_Rubinisphaeraceae	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_173_Bacillales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00
ASV_175_Parablastomonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_177_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_178_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_180_Clostridiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_181_Candidatus Megaira_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_24_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

Table S14: Results of the post-hoc analysis on the Shannon diversity of the short-term experiment.

Contrast	Estimate	SE	df	t-ratio	p-value
0 - 1	3.71485687142318	3.37070700250161	40.9613894625779	1.10210020291475	0.998887481132193
0 - 10	5.65066840283214	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719749	1.81048781150507	0.899205095536561
0 - 11	6.67016281518101	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719748	2.1371362849016	0.732312859479441
0 - 12	6.57554009808087	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719749	2.10681893768027	0.750955095172462
0 - 13	7.95888084834346	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719749	2.55004465700462	0.456722969098343
0 - 14	4.98231510564883	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719747	1.59634579996478	0.9605264768056
0 - 15	7.60925993419012	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719747	2.43802527122636	0.531563243752418
0 - 2	2.76188401465759	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719747	0.884914312583278	0.999918352326269
0 - 3	3.40850543532857	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719747	1.09209337837241	0.999022932924403
0 - 4	4.00777441755812	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719747	1.2841006084544	0.994540191298184
0 - 5	8.87593676648729	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719749	2.84387158930804	0.283725053254806
0 - 6	5.37010500528564	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719746	1.72059462092999	0.929648977851984
0 - 7	7.28679048444865	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719747	2.33470528025909	0.602050467802725
0 - 8	7.96561666764721	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719747	2.55220282978713	0.455313417242086
0 - 9	13.7852449517634	3.12107508646231	43.3580784719746	4.41682579555905	0.00570250884294976
1 - 10	1.93581153140896	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	0.620238692688159	0.999999210372379
1 - 11	2.95530594375783	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	0.946887166084694	0.999813687897305
1 - 12	2.86068322665769	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	0.916569818863358	0.999874331514588
1 - 13	4.24402397692029	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	1.35979553818772	0.990434356608054
1 - 14	1.26745823422566	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	0.406096681147874	0.99999997949588
1 - 15	3.89440306276695	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719756	1.24777615240946	0.995917996775167
1 - 2	-0.952972856765586	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	-0.305334806233633	0.99999999967588
1 - 3	-0.306351436094601	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	-0.0981557404445037	1
1 - 4	0.292917546134944	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	0.0938514896374897	1
1 - 5	5.16107989506412	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	1.65362247049113	0.94783156984128

1 - 6	1.65524813386247	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	0.530345502113078	0.999999909152827
1 - 7	3.57193361302548	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719756	1.14445616144218	0.998362129978565
1 - 8	4.25075979622404	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	1.36195371097022	0.990288428031039
1 - 9	10.0703880803403	3.1210750864623	43.3580784719755	3.22657667674215	0.1314446870875
10 - 11	1.01949441234887	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.357760203321096	0.999999999693904
10 - 12	0.924871695248733	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.324555271446535	0.99999999926065
10 - 13	2.30821244551133	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.809996154772286	0.999974476985456
10 - 14	-0.668353297183304	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.234538030414237	1
10 - 15	1.95859153135799	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.687307449647727	0.999997024242515
10 - 2	-2.88878438817455	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.01373001906211	0.999599916726824
10 - 3	-2.24216296750356	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.786818122215081	0.999982418315248
10 - 4	-1.64289398527402	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.576523107029552	0.99999727690753
10 - 5	3.22526836365516	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.13180871966517	0.998602137970537
10 - 6	-0.280563397546492	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.0984550939513558	1
10 - 7	1.63612208161652	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.574146715751648	0.99999742809381
10 - 8	2.31494826481508	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.812359883356233	0.99997350901269
10 - 9	8.13457654893129	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.85457941193777	0.275479544127644
11 - 12	-0.0946227171001377	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.033204931874561	1
11 - 13	1.28871803316246	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.45223595145119	0.99999991038891
11 - 14	-1.68784770953217	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.592298233735333	0.9999960483613
11 - 15	0.939097119009117	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.329547246326631	0.9999999907551
11 - 2	-3.90827880052342	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.3714902223832	0.989891179326878
11 - 3	-3.26165737985243	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.14457832553618	0.998419158199637
11 - 4	-2.66238839762289	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.934283310350647	0.999848687798397
11 - 5	2.20577395130629	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.774048516344072	0.999985770050646
11 - 6	-1.30005780989536	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.456215297272452	0.99999989846687

11 - 7	0.616627669267647	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.216386512430552	1
11 - 8	1.29545385246621	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.454599680035137	0.999999990347338
11 - 9	7.11508213658242	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.49681920861667	0.490672821173642
12 - 13	1.38334075026259	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.485440883325751	0.999999975473186
12 - 14	-1.59322499243204	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.559093301860772	0.999999822050442
12 - 15	1.03371983610925	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.362752178201192	0.99999999625615
12 - 2	-3.81365608342328	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.33828529050864	0.992019106736026
12 - 3	-3.16703466275229	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.11137339366162	0.998857326799888
12 - 4	-2.56776568052275	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.901078378476087	0.99990276709614
12 - 5	2.30039666840643	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.807253448218633	0.999975560302498
12 - 6	-1.20543509279522	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.423010365397891	0.99999996555028
12 - 7	0.711250386367785	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.249591444305113	0.99999999998595
12 - 8	1.39007656956634	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.487804611909698	0.999999973727953
12 - 9	7.20970485368256	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.53002414049123	0.468435427788955
13 - 14	-2.97656574269463	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.04453418518652	0.999433799017682
13 - 15	-0.34962091415334	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.122688705124559	1
13 - 2	-5.19699683368587	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.82372617383439	0.895137522158182
13 - 3	-4.55037541301489	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.59681427698737	0.961106658520815
13 - 4	-3.95110643078534	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.38651926180184	0.988789190315183
13 - 5	0.917055918143832	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.321812564892882	0.99999999934691
13 - 6	-2.58877584305782	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.908451248723642	0.999892525095639
13 - 7	-0.672090363894809	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.235849439020638	1
13 - 8	0.00673581930374922	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.00236372858394721	1
13 - 9	5.82636410341997	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.04458325716548	0.78838939672592
14 - 15	2.62694482854129	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.921845480061964	0.999871449852146
14 - 2	-2.22043109099124	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.779191988647872	0.999984496250335

14 - 3	-1.57380967032026	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.552280091800844	0.99999984994263
14 - 4	-0.974540688090712	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.341985076615315	0.999999999841233
14 - 5	3.89362166083846	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.36634675007941	0.990247714232303
14 - 6	0.387789899636813	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.136082936462881	1
14 - 7	2.30447537879982	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.808684746165885	0.999975000226871
14 - 8	2.98330156199838	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.04689791377047	0.999418880258785
14 - 9	8.8029298461146	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	3.08911744235201	0.173266701236964
15 - 2	-4.84737591953253	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.70103746870984	0.936212438533571
15 - 3	-4.20075449886155	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.47412557186281	0.980328411062965
15 - 4	-3.601485516632	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.26383055667728	0.995491868874693
15 - 5	1.26667683229717	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.444501270017442	0.999999992995034
15 - 6	-2.23915492890448	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.785762543599083	0.999982720119773
15 - 7	-0.32246944974147	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.113160733896079	1
15 - 8	0.356356733457089	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.125052433708506	1
15 - 9	6.17598501757331	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.16727196229004	0.713787885916588
2 - 3	0.646621420670985	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.226911896847027	1
2 - 4	1.24589040290053	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.437206912032557	0.999999994470934
2 - 5	6.11405275182971	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.14553873872728	0.727611739017131
2 - 6	2.60822099062805	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.915274925110752	0.999882205753693
2 - 7	4.52490646979106	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.58787673481376	0.962849698911959
2 - 8	5.20373265298962	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.82608990241834	0.894215260512136
2 - 9	11.0233609371058	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	3.86830943099988	0.0255119290772466
3 - 4	0.599268982229545	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.21029501518553	1
3 - 5	5.46743133115872	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.91862684188025	0.854237201318069
3 - 6	1.96159956995707	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.688363028263725	0.999996962605409
3 - 7	3.87828504912008	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.36096483796673	0.990609893656334

3 - 8	4.55711123231864	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.59917800557131	0.960635874503474
3 - 9	10.3767395164349	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	3.64139753415285	0.0468635930025193
4 - 5	4.86816234892918	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.70833182669472	0.934137558177167
4 - 6	1.36233058772752	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.478068013078196	0.999999980254238
4 - 7	3.27901606689053	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.1506698227812	0.998324925434361
4 - 8	3.95784225008909	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.38888299038579	0.988607471898154
4 - 9	9.77747053420531	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	3.43110251896732	0.0795791346647987
5 - 6	-3.50583176120165	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-1.23026381361652	0.996584217321614
5 - 7	-1.58914628203864	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.557662003913521	0.999999828276638
5 - 8	-0.910320098840083	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	-0.319448836308935	0.99999999941366
5 - 9	4.90930818527614	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	1.7227706922726	0.929896281536887
6 - 7	1.91668547916301	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.672601809703004	0.999997772666769
6 - 8	2.59551166236157	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.910814977307589	0.99988904497727
6 - 9	8.41513994647779	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.95303450588912	0.22848297197344
7 - 8	0.678826183198558	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	0.238213167604585	1
7 - 9	6.49845446731478	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.28043269618612	0.638819250165108
8 - 9	5.81962828411622	2.84965852234229	47.0808689341221	2.04221952858154	0.789735068447181

Table S15: Relative abundance of the gut microbiome composition at the ASV level of the short term exposure experiment. Timepoint 0 is the natural *D. magna* population. Timepoint 1 is after being 1 hour in a laboratory environment. Timepoint 2 is after being 1 day in a laboratory environment, and so on.

ASV	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
ASV_1_Burkholderiales	22,61	27,36	25,59	26,21	23,68	27,38	25,48	27,46	29,78	16,74	20,11	27,93	21,16	19,84	25,87	27,29
ASV_3_Pseudomonadaceae	11,71	12,00	11,30	12,64	13,55	11,27	14,06	13,05	10,22	20,55	11,16	9,89	12,06	22,29	13,20	13,61
ASV_5_Burkholderiales	7,71	7,30	7,67	7,25	8,50	8,98	7,96	8,24	9,68	24,06	11,62	11,07	10,60	6,58	8,51	8,38
ASV_6_Alphaproteobacteria	7,44	6,76	7,48	6,59	6,60	7,70	6,88	7,62	8,38	3,67	4,86	6,26	6,03	5,70	7,10	7,32
ASV_8_Flavobacterium_sp.	5,58	5,63	6,26	6,03	5,66	5,99	7,06	8,13	5,75	5,66	5,55	6,80	6,27	7,37	6,70	5,91

ASV_11_Bacteria	3,97	3,92	3,58	3,98	4,60	3,14	4,39	4,67	2,89	2,54	3,48	3,80	2,95	4,07	4,57	3,15
ASV_10_Cyclobacteriaceae	4,11	3,61	3,76	4,02	5,06	3,39	4,85	3,99	2,74	2,14	3,66	3,31	2,76	3,66	4,36	3,09
ASV_13_Emticicia_sp.	3,70	3,18	2,77	2,80	3,25	2,66	3,29	3,94	3,28	2,28	2,63	2,47	2,48	2,85	3,30	3,19
ASV_19_Acinetobacter_sp.	0,24	0,31	0,21	0,25	0,35	0,30	0,41	0,21	5,43	0,36	4,08	2,85	11,25	0,80	1,47	5,01
ASV_15_Silanimonas_sp.	1,85	2,09	2,11	1,98	2,52	2,25	2,96	2,58	1,36	1,28	2,07	1,81	1,44	1,84	2,46	1,70
ASV_14_Gammaproteobacteria	1,60	1,51	1,05	1,29	1,13	0,89	1,31	1,15	1,42	3,41	1,46	1,12	2,19	5,37	1,62	2,65
ASV_38_Alphaproteobacteria	1,08	1,08	1,05	1,12	1,23	6,89	1,24	1,19	0,72	6,74	0,96	0,99	0,82	1,01	1,32	0,92
ASV_9_Rickettsiales	0,74	3,42	1,66	1,47	1,20	0,66	1,58	1,96	2,45	1,23	2,56	3,11	3,34	0,86	0,82	0,76
ASV_17_Microbacteriaceae	1,56	1,29	1,25	1,58	1,95	1,04	2,00	1,41	0,97	0,70	1,26	1,54	1,52	1,45	2,11	1,58
ASV_23_Polynucleobacter_sp.	0,95	1,64	0,96	2,40	0,45	2,73	0,04	0,49	0,30	0,05	9,53	0,31	0,37	0,36	0,26	0,31
ASV_2_Candidatus Bacilloplasma_sp.	0,00	0,14	0,79	0,37	0,00	0,02	0,23	0,04	0,01	0,00	1,76	2,95	2,45	2,62	1,21	1,91
ASV_12_Bacilli	0,05	0,00	1,51	1,18	3,43	3,76	0,59	0,38	2,27	0,08	0,42	0,14	0,18	0,10	0,00	0,04
ASV_22_Lacihabitans_sp.	0,75	0,77	0,73	0,97	0,87	0,52	0,91	0,70	0,67	0,41	0,70	0,67	0,69	0,78	0,77	0,76
ASV_24_Flavobacteriaceae	0,81	0,78	0,74	0,83	0,70	0,50	0,57	0,93	0,68	0,40	0,62	0,84	0,59	0,75	0,78	0,84
ASV_25_Fluviicola_sp.	0,79	0,94	0,59	0,74	0,88	0,42	0,93	0,66	0,51	0,39	0,69	0,69	0,63	0,79	0,68	0,57
ASV_31_Rhizobiales	0,52	0,64	0,70	0,65	0,78	0,57	0,73	0,76	0,35	0,41	0,52	0,50	0,50	0,70	0,70	0,54
ASV_29_Rhizobiales	0,63	0,50	0,59	0,83	0,72	0,45	0,52	0,66	0,45	0,40	0,52	0,44	0,38	0,49	0,59	0,60
ASV_41_Rhizobiales	0,33	1,54	2,80	0,75	0,30	0,13	0,32	0,37	0,17	0,12	0,25	0,29	0,15	0,35	0,25	0,22
ASV_28_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,54	0,49	0,55	0,60	0,55	0,56	0,66	0,71	0,37	0,28	0,46	0,55	0,39	0,50	0,52	0,50
ASV_34_Acetobacteraceae	0,57	0,39	0,47	0,61	0,76	0,50	0,64	0,47	0,37	0,26	0,52	0,51	0,46	0,55	0,63	0,48
ASV_32_Chitinophagaceae	0,54	0,43	0,45	0,50	0,63	0,36	0,69	0,53	0,31	0,35	0,67	0,49	0,47	0,48	0,63	0,43
ASV_30_Bacteroidia	0,49	0,45	0,37	0,47	0,48	0,42	0,60	0,45	0,41	0,31	0,52	0,54	0,40	0,59	0,53	0,51
ASV_20_Streptococcus_sp.	0,54	0,45	0,48	0,56	0,54	0,53	0,58	0,42	0,42	0,28	0,52	0,39	0,39	0,37	0,47	0,44
ASV_4_Enterobacteriales	0,51	0,47	0,38	0,54	0,45	0,39	0,45	0,48	0,42	0,30	0,39	0,48	0,38	0,43	0,57	0,52
ASV_37_Proteobacteria	0,56	0,51	0,44	0,46	0,44	0,23	0,51	0,32	0,25	0,22	0,36	0,37	0,26	0,41	0,47	0,42
ASV_39_Fimbriimonadaceae	0,40	0,23	0,37	0,44	0,47	0,30	0,40	0,28	0,31	0,25	0,37	0,37	0,32	0,43	0,50	0,40
ASV_40_Legionella_sp.	0,34	0,48	0,59	0,31	0,34	0,32	0,28	0,31	0,34	0,17	0,27	0,35	0,31	0,34	0,50	0,35
ASV_45_Pseudomonas_sp.	0,17	0,05	0,16	0,23	0,14	0,15	0,48	0,18	0,65	0,31	0,28	0,53	0,86	0,37	0,25	0,72

ASV_71_Comamonadaceae	0,01	0,16	0,07	0,09	0,16	0,07	0,05	0,13	0,03	0,05	0,03	0,04	0,01	0,07	0,00	0,10
ASV_70_Prevotellaceae	0,08	0,06	0,08	0,08	0,06	0,04	0,10	0,11	0,05	0,03	0,07	0,05	0,03	0,08	0,06	0,02
ASV_74_Bacilli	0,06	0,13	0,07	0,10	0,11	0,05	0,03	0,04	0,06	0,03	0,04	0,02	0,08	0,03	0,08	0,10
ASV_91_Steroidobacteraceae	0,84	0,09	0,02	0,01	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_33_Burkholderiales	0,28	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,02	0,09	0,00	0,08	0,00	0,03	0,10	0,24	0,02	0,01	0,05
ASV_66_FukuN18 freshwater group_sp.	0,04	0,10	0,07	0,10	0,06	0,05	0,02	0,06	0,10	0,05	0,04	0,05	0,06	0,01	0,07	0,06
ASV_76_Bacteroidia	0,03	0,08	0,05	0,05	0,07	0,08	0,04	0,05	0,07	0,02	0,03	0,11	0,03	0,03	0,07	0,05
ASV_79_FukuN57_sp.	0,06	0,04	0,05	0,02	0,09	0,08	0,06	0,08	0,03	0,03	0,01	0,03	0,05	0,05	0,06	0,03
ASV_81_Sphingomonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,05	0,02	0,05	0,05	0,03	0,21	0,26	0,01	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,02
ASV_92_Babeliales	0,00	0,03	0,57	0,07	0,03	0,01	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_94_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,04	0,05	0,09	0,08	0,06	0,04	0,02	0,02	0,04	0,02	0,03	0,02	0,08	0,03	0,03	0,05
ASV_82_Legionellaceae	0,02	0,00	0,05	0,06	0,08	0,02	0,05	0,02	0,06	0,03	0,03	0,10	0,04	0,01	0,04	0,06
ASV_36_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,08	0,09	0,02	0,03	0,03	0,04	0,04	0,03	0,06	0,01	0,03	0,04	0,04	0,01	0,05	0,04
ASV_80_Proteobacteria	0,06	0,04	0,02	0,04	0,08	0,03	0,05	0,00	0,04	0,01	0,05	0,03	0,04	0,04	0,08	0,02
ASV_87_Brevundimonas_sp.	0,08	0,04	0,01	0,07	0,05	0,02	0,03	0,03	0,00	0,05	0,07	0,02	0,02	0,05	0,04	0,03
ASV_77_Acetobacterales	0,06	0,06	0,08	0,03	0,00	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,02	0,03	0,02	0,01	0,04	0,02	0,07	0,05
ASV_124_Pirellulaceae	0,54	0,03	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_61_Runella_sp.	0,02	0,03	0,01	0,04	0,05	0,01	0,04	0,04	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,04	0,07	0,03	0,05	0,01
ASV_89_PeM15	0,06	0,07	0,07	0,01	0,03	0,01	0,05	0,05	0,03	0,03	0,04	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,02	0,03
ASV_120_Legionella_sp.	0,01	0,18	0,14	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,03	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,12	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,01
ASV_108_Legionella_sp.	0,00	0,32	0,20	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_83_Enhydrobacter_sp.	0,03	0,01	0,01	0,02	0,07	0,01	0,08	0,02	0,04	0,01	0,05	0,01	0,01	0,04	0,06	0,00
ASV_88_SC-I-84	0,38	0,08	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_122_Mitochondria	0,43	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_105_Alphaproteobacteria	0,04	0,00	0,05	0,01	0,05	0,01	0,01	0,03	0,04	0,01	0,02	0,03	0,05	0,03	0,04	0,02
ASV_85_Rhizobiales	0,02	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,00	0,02	0,03	0,03	0,04	0,00	0,03	0,02	0,03	0,02	0,05	0,00
ASV_86_Burkholderiales	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,02	0,05	0,00	0,01	0,05	0,04	0,05	0,00	0,02	0,04	0,02	0,02	0,02
ASV_95_Polyangiales	0,06	0,00	0,02	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,01	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,01	0,02	0,03	0,04	0,00

ASV_155_Clostridiaceae	0,04	0,02	0,04	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_136_Truepera_sp.	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,04	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01
ASV_118_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,03	0,01
ASV_126_Aquicella_sp.	0,00	0,05	0,07	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_137_Nibri bacter_sp.	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00
ASV_104_Pseudomonadales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,07	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,03	0,00	0,00
ASV_142_Mitochondria	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,11	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_193_Proteobacteria	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,06	0,01
ASV_154_Propionibacteriales	0,00	0,03	0,01	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,02	0,00	0,00
ASV_189_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,06
ASV_140_Beijerinckiaceae	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,03
ASV_127_Rhizobiales	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_173_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,05	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,02
ASV_329_Proteobacteria	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00
ASV_157_Rhodobacteraceae	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,05	0,00
ASV_172_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,02
ASV_135_Absconditabacteriales (SR1)	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,04	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_130_Rhodococcus_sp.	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01
ASV_242_Propionibacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,01
ASV_163_Micrococcaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03
ASV_177_Streptococcus_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,05	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01
ASV_207_Proteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,00
ASV_335_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,01
ASV_113_FukuN57_sp.	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01
ASV_149_Caulobacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01
ASV_51_Pirellula_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,02
ASV_182_Rhizobiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_148_Holosporaceae	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00

ASV_243_Bacteroidia	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_222_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,02
ASV_139_Pseudomonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00
ASV_218_Pseudomonadaceae	0,06	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_194_Comamonadaceae	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00
ASV_257_Cytophagales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,02	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00
ASV_150_Xanthobacter_sp.	0,00	0,03	0,05	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_216_Gammaproteobacteria	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_184_Fimbriimonadaceae	0,01	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_352_Proteobacteria	0,01	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_168_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00
ASV_197_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,00
ASV_102_env.OPS 17	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01
ASV_121_Alloprevotella_sp.	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01
ASV_187_Bacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,03
ASV_180_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00
ASV_158_Mitochondria	0,07	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_181_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,01	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01
ASV_200_Holosporaceae	0,00	0,01	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_339_Rhizobiales	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_226_Enterobacterales	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_176_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01
ASV_161_Pseudoxanthomonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,01
ASV_114_Lactobacillaceae	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_143_Mitochondria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,07	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_264_Microbacteriaceae	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_221_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00
ASV_295_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

ASV_244_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_270_Bacteroidia	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_73_Actibacter_sp.	0,03	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_246_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_374_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00
ASV_293_Proteobacteria	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_398_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_254_Cyclobacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_312_Microbacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_325_Bacteroidia	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00
ASV_166_Pseudomonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_365_Propionibacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00
ASV_233_Rhodobacteraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_400_Vicinamibacteraceae	0,01	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_144_Prevotella_7_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_358_Proteobacteria	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_276_Lactobacillales	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_224_Alphaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_213_Rhodobacteraceae	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_212_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_238_Thermicanus_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_152_Diplorickettsiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_304_Rhizobiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_320_Bacteroidia	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_280_Proteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_245_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00
ASV_342_Corynebacteriales	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_377_Proteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00

ASV_336_Bacillales	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02
ASV_316_Planctomycetales	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_237_Pseudomonadaceae	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_214_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_408_Rhizobiales	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_382_Acetobacteraceae	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01
ASV_170_Alphaproteobacteria	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_340_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01
ASV_271_Kinneretia_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00
ASV_350_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_305_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_349_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_323_Bacteroidia	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_363_Elstera_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01
ASV_369_Bacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01
ASV_317_Microbacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_250_Rhizobiaceae	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_301_Pseudomonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_388_Alphaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_267_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_330_Alphaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_302_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_397_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_252_Emticicia_sp.	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_315_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_409_Cyclobacteriaceae	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_387_JI49D030	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_285_Rhizobiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

ASV_376_Silanimonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_402_Micrococcales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_375_Proteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_338_SWB02_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_404_Rhizobiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_378_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_379_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_313_Rhizobiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_384_Acetobacterales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_314_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_259_Actinomyces_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_169_Candidatus Berkiella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_215_Rheinheimera_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00
ASV_268_Verrucomicrobiaceae	0,00	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_145_Candidatus Falkowbacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

Table S16: Results of the post-hoc analysis on the species richness in the long-term experiment.

contrast	estimate	SE	df	z.ratio	p.value
Lab Blauwe Hoeve - Natural Blauwe Hoeve	-0.711496319228142	0.234986925631977	Inf	-302.781.236.579.284	0.0504509877925533
Lab Blauwe Hoeve - Lab Kennedy park	-0.367724780125318	0.250355872064273	Inf	-146.880.828.914.975	0.824202688621861
Lab Blauwe Hoeve - Natural Kennedy park	-0.259511195485085	0.256141495286037	Inf	-101.315.562.008.133	0.972639891772993
Lab Blauwe Hoeve - Lab Morrinestraat	-0.105360515657827	0.265274141915487	Inf	-0.397175973870055	0.999928434181566
Lab Blauwe Hoeve - Natural Morrinestraat	-0.76460614454209	0.23297728719019	Inf	-328.189.135.414.692	0.0229989877495259
Lab Blauwe Hoeve - Lab Zwevegem	0.117783035656383	0.280541803839087	Inf	0.419841300100647	0.999895859125758
Lab Blauwe Hoeve - Natural Zwevegem	0.0377403279828461	0.274770041119245	Inf	0.137352412326741	0.999999953182961
Natural Blauwe Hoeve - Lab Kennedy park	0.343771539102824	0.20933906425386	Inf	164.217.577.033.755	0.724525236477481

Natural Blauwe Hoeve - Natural Kennedy park	0.451985123743057	0.216224991046331	Inf	209.034.636.355.337	0.421107607941506
Natural Blauwe Hoeve - Lab Morrinesstraat	0.606135803570315	0.226969494678507	Inf	267.056.066.027.235	0.131610994956426
Natural Blauwe Hoeve - Natural Morrinesstraat	-0.0531098253139485	0.188210513766153	Inf	-0.282183095148107	0.999993080293926
Natural Blauwe Hoeve - Lab Zwevegem	0.829279354884525	0.244639499768348	Inf	338.980.154.745.974	0.0160713582706128
Natural Blauwe Hoeve - Natural Zwevegem	0.749236647210988	0.237998648404336	Inf	314.807.101.735.347	0.0351479768914342
Lab Kennedy park - Natural Kennedy park	0.108213584640233	0.232835680710841	Inf	0.464763752316055	0.999793828346736
Lab Kennedy park - Lab Morrinesstraat	0.262364264467491	0.242846369076648	Inf	108.037.137.003.553	0.961003667373198
Lab Kennedy park - Natural Morrinesstraat	-0.396881364416773	0.207080672567997	Inf	-191.655.435.292.472	0.539354856697692
Lab Kennedy park - Lab Zwevegem	0.485507815781701	0.259437260828128	Inf	18.713.881.507.689	0.570744570007902
Lab Kennedy park - Natural Zwevegem	0.405465108108164	0.253184841768588	Inf	160.145.886.015.862	0.749670698021475
Natural Kennedy park - Lab Morrinesstraat	0.154150679827258	0.248806675762561	Inf	0.619560063470185	0.998632016553104
Natural Kennedy park - Natural Morrinesstraat	-0.505094949057006	0.21403926714862	Inf	-235.982.376.404.928	0.261389779773782
Natural Kennedy park - Lab Zwevegem	0.377294231141468	0.26502470684128	Inf	142.361.908.683.262	0.846605823888095
Natural Kennedy park - Natural Zwevegem	0.297251523467931	0.258907255656711	Inf	11.481.003.987.855	0.946055700380485
Lab Morrinesstraat - Natural Morrinesstraat	-0.659245628884264	0.224888222553226	Inf	-293.143.687.739.466	0.0664774165860589
Lab Morrinesstraat - Lab Zwevegem	0.22314355131421	0.273861278748818	Inf	0.814805044121898	0.992357529512725
Lab Morrinesstraat - Natural Zwevegem	0.143100843640673	0.267945650819939	Inf	0.534066678084794	0.999480946816864
Natural Morrinesstraat - Lab Zwevegem	0.882389180198473	0.242709797856288	Inf	363.557.296.817.885	0.00673772043071019
Natural Morrinesstraat - Natural Zwevegem	0.802346472524937	0.236014655839045	Inf	339.956.207.241.686	0.0155476489445896
Lab Zwevegem - Natural Zwevegem	-0.0800427076735368	0.283069258531567	Inf	-0.282767221311002	0.999992981081607

Table SI7: Relative abundance of the gut microbiome composition at the ASV level of the long term exposure experiment. Lab represents the clonal lineage of the natural *D. magna* populations that have been in the lab for two years. Natural stands for the respective natural *D. magna* population (a mix of the 2014 and 2017 samples). In the last two columns the mean relative abundance for the lab and natural gut microbiomes are shown.

ASV	Natural Blauwe Hoeve	Lab Blauwe Hoeve	Natural Kennedy park	Lab Kennedy park	Natural Morrinestraat	Lab Morrinestraat	Natural Zwevegem	Lab Zwevegem
ASV_1_Comamonadaceae	10,97	0,00	34,32	0,02	35,74	4,16	44,38	0,04
ASV_6_Burkholderiales	0,18	10,04	0,15	18,46	1,21	22,82	0,17	39,73
ASV_11_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,05	0,19	0,03	42,71	0,00	0,00	0,00	37,37
ASV_13_Acinetobacter_sp.	0,03	41,28	0,07	11,58	0,00	8,15	0,26	10,62
ASV_12_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	2,29	0,00	40,39	0,00	0,00	0,10	17,54	0,00
ASV_33_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,00	0,09	0,00	5,75	0,00	47,17	0,00	0,98
ASV_5_Rickettsiales	1,13	0,00	1,06	0,00	40,54	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_9_Flavobacterium_sp.	2,72	0,00	5,38	0,00	0,03	0,00	33,18	0,00
ASV_2_Candidatus Bacilloplasma_sp.	31,02	0,00	0,07	0,00	0,03	0,00	1,03	0,00
ASV_20_Ralstonia_sp.	0,00	19,35	0,00	5,45	0,00	4,82	0,00	2,28
ASV_15_Microbacteriaceae	0,36	9,32	0,05	3,47	10,09	6,85	0,52	0,63
ASV_21_Burkholderiales	26,93	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,31	0,00
ASV_10_Emticicia_sp.	7,86	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,54	0,08	0,00	0,00
ASV_18_Lacihabitans_sp.	0,53	0,00	7,65	0,00	0,36	0,07	0,00	0,00
ASV_32_Pseudomonas_sp.	0,00	4,65	0,05	1,20	0,00	0,71	0,00	0,69
ASV_40_Sphingomonas_sp.	0,00	4,44	0,00	1,33	0,00	0,60	0,00	0,65
ASV_46_Enterobacterales	0,14	0,62	3,02	0,61	0,47	0,90	0,00	0,11
ASV_24_Chitinophagales	4,43	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,89	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_37_Pirellula_sp.	0,00	0,17	0,00	0,18	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,90
ASV_35_Lactobacillaceae	0,00	1,02	0,00	3,19	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_31_Bacilli	0,00	1,94	0,00	0,90	0,00	0,44	0,02	0,86
ASV_41_Methyloparacoccus_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,49	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_22_Pasteuria_sp.	0,00	0,00	2,58	0,00	0,51	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_16_GKS98 freshwater group_sp.	1,65	0,00	0,79	0,00	0,38	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_43_Micrococcales	0,00	1,46	0,00	0,59	0,00	0,27	0,00	0,50
ASV_60_Saprospiraceae	2,47	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,16	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_30_Rhodobacteraceae	0,24	0,88	0,87	0,07	0,00	0,23	0,14	0,00
ASV_27_Pedobacter_sp.	1,40	0,00	0,56	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_3_Burkholderiales	0,14	1,64	0,00	0,00	0,10	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_50_Chitinophagales	0,23	0,00	1,32	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_23_Bosea_sp.	0,00	0,08	0,00	0,66	0,00	0,26	0,00	0,47
ASV_58_Shinella_sp.	0,00	0,11	0,00	0,09	0,00	1,11	0,00	0,11
ASV_61_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,42	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_53_Xanthobacteraceae	0,02	1,14	0,00	0,11	0,02	0,06	0,00	0,04

ASV_8_Bacilli	0,90	0,00	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_4_Candidatus Hepaticola	0,22	0,00	0,23	0,00	0,74	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_29_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,10	0,00	0,97	0,00
ASV_44_Methylophilaceae	0,76	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,10	0,00	0,21	0,00
ASV_52_OLB17_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_55_Phreatobacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,84	0,00	0,17	0,00	0,00
ASV_7_Legionella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,47	0,00	0,33
ASV_28_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,10	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,57	0,00
ASV_85_Burkholderiales	0,67	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_26_Pseudarcicella_sp.	0,43	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_82_Alphaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,46	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_17_Streptococcus_sp.	0,16	0,25	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00
ASV_94_Actinomyces_sp.	0,27	0,11	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03
ASV_36_Algoriphagus_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,42	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_72_Enterobacterales	0,00	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,10	0,00	0,00
ASV_65_Pirellula_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,39	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_38_Arcicella_sp.	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_64_Vermiphilaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,09	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,22
ASV_66_Legionella_sp.	0,00	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_68_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,27	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_74_Burkholderiales	0,18	0,00	0,09	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_19_Fluviicola_sp.	0,22	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,04	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_49_hgcl clade_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,17	0,00	0,00	0,06
ASV_59_Brevifollis_sp.	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,24	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_67_Granulicatella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,21	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_95_Comamonadaceae	0,06	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,13	0,00
ASV_70_Thiothrix_sp.	0,14	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,05	0,00
ASV_79_Saprospiraceae	0,00	0,00	0,08	0,00	0,00	0,09	0,00	0,00
ASV_73_Verrucomicrobiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,18
ASV_76_Hyphomicrobium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,17	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_90_Paracaedibacteraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,17	0,00	0,00
ASV_97_Alphaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,17	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_96_Saprospiraceae	0,00	0,00	0,16	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_47_Arcobacteraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,15	0,00
ASV_77_Defluviimonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,15	0,00
ASV_92_Cupriavidus_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,15	0,00	0,00	0,00

ASV_104_Nannocystis_sp.	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_116_Devesia_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00
ASV_122_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_124_Methylococcaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_125_Rickettsiales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_127_Corynebacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_130_Microbacteriaceae	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_131_Candidatus Limnoluna_sp.	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_132_Burkholderiales	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_133_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_134_Aquicola_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_138_Verrucomicrobiaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_140_Yokenella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_141_RB41_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_142_Micrococcales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_146_Rhodobacteraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_39_Acidibacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_34_Sulfurimonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,03	0,00
ASV_100_Bifidobacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_102_Clostridium sensu stricto 1_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00
ASV_115_Pirellula_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_117_Puniceicoccaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00
ASV_118_Flavobacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00
ASV_123_Syntrophorhabdus_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_135_Silanimonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_137_Comamonadaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_139_Microbacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_143_Aminicenantales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_144_Desulfuromonadales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_149_Burkholderiales	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_150_Gammaproteobacteria	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_151_Lentimicrobiaceae	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_152_env.OPS 17	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_153_Candidatus Megaira_sp.	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_154_UKL13-1_sp.	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_80_Caulobacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

ASV_84_Rickettsiella_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00
ASV_93_Stenotrophomonas_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_99_Fluviicola_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_112_Cutibacterium_sp.	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_113_Luteolibacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_126_Pseudomonadales	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_128_Weeksellaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00
ASV_136_Enterobacterales	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_147_Microbacteriaceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_155_Burkholderiales	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_156_Gammaproteobacteria	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_157_Cloacibacterium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_158_Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_159_Nissabacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00
ASV_160_Lachnospiraceae	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00
ASV_42_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_86_Sphingopyxis_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_87_Lacibacter_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00
ASV_98_Lacihabitans_sp.	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00

Table S18 : List of the recent *Daphnia* gut microbiome papers used for completion of the genbank used here.

Paper	Project ID	Environment	Sequence region	Forward primer	Reverse primer
Akbar et al., 2020	PRJNA561047	Lab	V3-V4	338F	806R
Akbar et al., 2021	PRJNA660107	Lab	V3-V4	338F	806R
Bulteel et al.,2021	Author was contacted to receive sequences	Inoculated	V4	515F	806R
Callens et al., 2020	Author was contacted to receive sequences	Inoculated	V4	515F	806R
Hegg et al., 2021	PRJNA748877	Natural	V4	515F	806R
Macke et al., 2017	PRJNA398629 and	Inoculated	V4	515F	806R

	PRJNA398630				
Macke et al., 2020	PRJNA498431 and PRJNA498417	Inoculated	V4	515F	806R
Motiei et al., 2020	PRJNA560134	Lab	V3-V4	341F	805R

Supplementary figures Chapter 1

Figure SI1: Bray Curtis, weighted Unifrac and unweighted Unifrac distances between natural and laboratory *D. magna* gut microbiomes. “Between populations” stands for the comparison between laboratory and natural gut microbiomes. “Within populations” stands for the comparison within laboratory (“Lab”) or within natural (“Natural”) gut microbiome communities.

Supplementary information Chapter 2

Network analysis

Network analysis was performed following Massol et al. (2021) to investigate whether specific bacterial communities could be linked to a treatment in our experiment (i.e., culture, species, genotype). We looked for modules of interacting nodes in the microbes-*Daphnia* population network using the `cluster_leading_eigen` function in the R package `igraph` (i.e. using Newman's leading eigenvalue method). To assess the effect of categorical drivers on network organization, we investigated the congruence of node classifications obtained by network modules and by external categorical variables. The Normalized Mutual Information index (NMI) was used to gauge the congruence of two classifications ('compare' function in the R package `igraph`). In addition, the beta diversity of links in the different sub-networks was investigated using the `disPairwise` function of the `econetwork` package (Table S19).

Applying the leading-eigenvector community search algorithm to the whole network (combining bacterioplankton and gut microbiomes) led to nine communities. In the bacterioplankton network five communities were found (Figure S12), while in the gut microbiomes network seven were found (Figure S13). Within both the bacterioplankton and gut microbiomes network, there was no congruence with any of the factors, i.e. culture, species or genotype.

EdgeR analysis

EdgeR analysis showed that 86 ASVs significantly differed between the donor inocula and the recipients (bacterioplankton and gut microbiomes), and 619 ASVs significantly differed between bacterioplankton and gut microbiomes (Figure S14). Within the bacterioplankton, EdgeR analysis showed 76 significantly different ASVs between mono- and co-cultures, 45 significantly different ASVs between the species *D. magna* and *D. pulex*, and 12 significantly different ASVs between the genotypes. Within the gut microbiomes, EdgeR analysis revealed 148 significantly different ASVs between mono- and co-cultures, 62 significantly different ASVs between the species *D. magna* and *D. pulex*, and 6 significantly different ASVs between the genotypes.

Supplementary tables Chapter 2

Table SI1:AIC Table

Model	df	AIC
Full data set (Bacterioplankton and gut microbiomes)		
Species richness		
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	1279.748
fit8 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit9 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit10 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit11<- lmer(N0~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit12<- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit13<- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit14<- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit15<- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit16<- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit17 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	1279.748

fit18 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit19 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit20 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1309.256
fit21 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit22 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit23 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit24 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit25 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit26 <- lmer(N0~Sort + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1287.795
fit27 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1309.256
fit28 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit29 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	6	1279.748
fit8 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit9 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725

fit10 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit11<- lmer(N0~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit12<- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit13<- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit14<- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit15<- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit16<- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit17 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	6	1279.748
fit18 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit19 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit20 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1309.256
fit21 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit22 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit23 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit24 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit25 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit26 <- lmer(N0~Sort + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1287.795
fit27 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1309.256
fit28 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit29 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349

fit2 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	6	1279.748
fit8 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit9 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit10 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit11<- lmer(N0~Sort*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit12<- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit13<- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit14<- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit15<- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
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fit22 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit23 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199

fit24 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit25 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit27 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1287.795
fit28 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1309.256
fit29 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	1279.748
fit8 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit9 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit10 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
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fit13<- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit14<- lmer(N0~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit15<- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit16<- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170

fit17 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	1279.748
fit18 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	1264.725
fit19 <- lmer(N0~Sort*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	1047.349
fit20 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1309.256
fit21 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit22 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit23 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit24 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit25 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
fit26 <- lmer(N0~Sort + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1287.795
fit27 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	1309.256
fit28 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	1282.199
fit29 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	1103.170
Shannon diversity		
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659

fit8 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit9 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit10 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit11<- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit12<- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit13<- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit14<- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit15<- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit16<- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit17 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659
fit18 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit19 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit20 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit21 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.6547
fit22 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit23 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit24 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit25 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit26 <- lmer(N1~Sort + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	871.9916
fit27 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit28 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit29 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633

fit1 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659
fit8 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit9 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit10 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit11<- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit12<- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit13<- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit14<- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit15<- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit16<- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit17 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659
fit18 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit19 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit20 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit21 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.6547

fit22 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit23 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit24 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit25 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit26 <- lmer(N1~Sort + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	871.9916
fit27 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit28 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit29 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659
fit8 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit9 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit10 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit11<- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit12<- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit13<- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633

fit14<- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit15<- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit16<- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit17 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659
fit18 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit19 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit20 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit21 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.6547
fit22 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit23 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit24 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit25 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit27 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	871.9916
fit28 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit29 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633

fit7 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659
fit8 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit9 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit10 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit11<- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit12<- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit13<- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit14<- lmer(N1~Sort*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit15<- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit16<- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit17 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	6	868.8659
fit18 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	9	863.1160
fit19 <- lmer(N1~Sort*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	41	746.2367
fit20 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit21 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.6547
fit22 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit23 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547
fit24 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit25 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
fit26 <- lmer(N1~Sort + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	871.9916
fit27 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	4	886.7555
fit28 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	7	869.3547

fit29 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_R)	35	776.0633
<u>Data set gut microbiomes</u>		
Species richness		
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	832.9796
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	832.9796
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524

fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	832.9796
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	832.9796
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	822.9524
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	684.1701
Shannon diversity		
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	580.4585
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106

fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	580.4585
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	580.4585
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	4	580.4585

fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	6	576.3610
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_GUT)	26	499.0106
<u>Data set bacterioplankton</u>		
Species richness		
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	450.1707
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	450.1707
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404

fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	450.1707
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit1 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit2 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit3 <- lmer(N0~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit4 <- lmer(N0~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
fit5 <- lmer(N0~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	450.1707
fit6 <- lmer(N0~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	445.0727
fit7 <- lmer(N0~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	366.1404
Shannon diversity		
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	287.7213
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290

fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	287.7213
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	287.7213
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit1 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species*Clone + (1 Culture:Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit2 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290
fit3 <- lmer(N1~Culture*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668
fit4 <- lmer(N1~Species*Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668

fit5 <- lmer(N1~Culture + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	4	287.7213
fit6 <- lmer(N1~Species + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	5	286.2290
fit7 <- lmer(N1~Clone + (1 Species:Clone) , data=div_samp_BPK)	17	249.6668

Table SI2: linear mixed-effect model on the ASV richness and the exponential value of the Shannon entropy on the bacterioplankton and gut microbiomes. Following AIC the best model only included culture type (mono- vs co-culture), species (*D. magna* and *D. pulex*), genotype and all possible interactions, with genotype nested in species and species nested within culture type as random factor.

	F	df	df res	p-value
ASV richness of bacterioplankton				
Culture	0.0075	1	66.703	0.9315
Species	0.2174	1	71.337	0.6425
Genotype	0.3132	12	77.662	0.9851
Shannon entropy of bacterioplankton				
Culture	0.0709	1	76.566	0.7908
Species	0.2730	1	52.699	0.6027
Genotype	0.3434	12	90.938	0.9875
ASV richness of gut microbiome				
Culture	0.6366	1	415.84	0.4254
Species	0.0511	2	418.29	0.9501
Genotype	0.5334	20	431.68	0.9523
Shannon entropy of gut microbiome				
Culture	1.4575	1	377.79	0.2281
Species	0.02	2	380.17	0.9802
Genotype	0.4847	20	391.99	0.9717

Table SI3: Relative abundance (in %) of the bacterioplankton and gut samples at class level.

Class	BPK	Gut
Actinobacteria	53,38	21,50
Gammaproteobacteria	35,36	38,00
Bacteroidia	1,61	28,95
Verrucomicrobiae	4,07	5,73
Alphaproteobacteria	3,31	3,41
Bacilli	1,58	0,17

Planctomycetacia	0,30	0,55
Ignavibacteria	0,03	0,66
Deltaproteobacteria	0,03	0,39
Acidimicrobiia	0,03	0,27
Gracilibacteria	0,00	0,09
Babeliae	0,07	0,01
Blastocatellia_(Subgroup_4)	0,02	0,06
Clostridia	0,05	0,02
Gemmatimonadetes	0,01	0,03
Parcubacteria	0,00	0,04
Armatimonadia	0,00	0,03
Acidobacteriia	0,01	0,03
Mollicutes	0,03	0,00
Negativicutes	0,03	0,00
OM190	0,00	0,02
Subgroup_6	0,01	0,01
Deinococci	0,01	0,00
Anaerolineae	0,00	0,01
Fusobacteriia	0,01	0,00
Saccharimonadia	0,01	0,00
Thermoleophilia	0,01	0,00
Hydrogenedentia	0,00	0,01
Holophagae	0,01	0,00
Phycisphaerae	0,00	0,01

Table SI4: List of bacteria (ASVs) that differ between the gut microbiomes and bacterioplankton. Results from the DESeq analysis to investigate the differences in ASVs between donor and recipients. The different ASVs, their class, the log2 fold changes, and adjusted p-values are represented in the table.

ASV	Class	Log2FoldChange	Padj
ASV2-Ralstonia sp.	Gammaproteobacteria	3.91899	<0.0001
ASV3 env OPS 17	Bacteroidia	5.760402	<0.0001

ASV6 Bradyrhizobium sp	Alphaproteobacteria	2.789670	<0.0001
ASV8 Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobiae	2.893256	<0.0001
ASV67 OPB56	Ignavibacteria	6.406771	<0.0001
ASV73 Roseimartima sp.	Planctomycetacia	2.942296	<0.0001
ASV74 Oligoflexus sp.	Deltaproteobacteria	5.201426	<0.0001
ASV109 cL500-29 marine group sp.	Acidimicrobiia	4.982064	<0.0001
ASV244 Absconditabacteriales SR1	Gracilibacteria	5.425947	<0.0001
ASV275 Vermiphilaceae	Babeliae	-1.890474	0.03182938
OUT 385 Gaiellales	Thermoleophilia	2.523055	0.0009200537

Table S15: Results of the DESeq analysis. Significant differences of the relative abundance are shown between the bacterioplankton (BPK) and the gut microbiome (GUT) per genotype, the ASVs that differ are shown (list of ASVs see Table S14). (-) means that the relative abundance of this ASV is higher in bacterioplankton than in gut microbiomes, (+) the reverse. Relative abundances that differ between samples are in red. Relative abundances that are equal between samples are in black. Short explanation of representation of the genotypes: KNO(DB) are gut microbiomes from the *D. magna* genotype KNO that was in co-culture with *D. pulex* genotype DB. DB(KNO) are gut microbiomes from the *D. pulex* genotype DB that was in co-culture with *D. magna* genotype KNO.

<i>D. magna</i>	GUT mono vs BPK mono	GUT co vs BPK co	<i>D. pulex</i>	GUT mono vs BPK mono	GUT co vs BPK co
KNO	GUT KNO ≠ BPK KNO ASV1(-), 3(+), 6(+) and 10(+)	GUT KNO(DB) ≠ BPK KNO-DB ASV130(-)	DB	GUT DB = BPK DB	GUT DB(KNO) ≠ BPK KNO-DB ASV126(+)
		GUT KNO(DK) ≠ BPK KNO-DK ASV1(-), 3(+) and 8(+)			GUT DB(OM2) ≠ BPK OM2-DB ASV3(+) and 212(-)
		GUT KNO(GB) ≠ BPK KNO-GB ASV1(-) and 12(+)			GUT DB(T2) ≠ BPK T2-DB ASV3(+) and 24(-)

OM2	GUT OM2 ≠ BPK OM2 OUT1(-), 2(+), 3(+) and 6(+)	GUT OM2(DB) ≠ BPK OM2-DB ASV1(-), 3(+) and 212(-)	DK	GUT DK ≠ BPK DK ASV7	GUT DK(KNO) ≠ BPK KNO-DK ASV3(+) and 8(+)
		GUT OM2(DK) ≠ BPK OM2-DK ASV87(+)			GUT DK(OM2) ≠ BPK OM2-DK ASV3(+)
		GUT OM2(GB) ≠ BPK OM2-GB ASV3(+), 6(+), 7(+) and 8(+)			GUT DK(T2) = BPK T2-DK
T2	GUT T2 ≠ BPK T2 ASV3(+) and 8(+)	GUT T2(DB) = BPK T2-DB	GB	GUT GB ≠ BPK GB ASV3(+), 6(+) and 8(+)	GUT GB(KNO) ≠ BPK KNO-GB ASV14(+)
		GUT T2(DK) ≠ BPK T2-DK ASV1(-), 2(+), 8(-), 12(+) and 24(-)			GUT GB(OM2) ≠ BPK OM2-GB ASV2(+), 3(+), 6(+) and 8(+)
		GUT T2(GB) ≠ BPK T2-GB ASV3(+)			GUT GB(T2) ≠ BPK T2-GB ASV3(+)

Table SI6 Significant differences of the relative abundance between bacterioplankton per genotype, ASVs that differ are shown. >, =, and < show in which treatment the relative abundance of that ASV is higher, equal or lower. Relative abundances that differ between samples are in red. Relative abundances that are equal between samples are in black.

	<i>D. magna</i> Mono vs co	Mono vs mono		<i>D. pulex</i> Mono vs co
KNO	KNO > KNO-DB ASV1	KNO = DB	DB	DB = KNO-DB
	KNO > KNO-DK ASV13	KNO > DK ASV1		DB = OM2-DB

	KNO > KNO-GB ASV1 and 13	KNO > GB ASV1 and 13		DB = T2-DB
OM2	OM2 = OM2-DB	OM2 ≠ DB ASV4 (<) and 8 (>)	DK	DK = KNO-DK
	OM2 = OM2-DK	OM2 ≠ DK ASV2 (<) and 8 (>)		DK = OM2-DK
	OM2 > OM2-GB ASV2, 3 and 8	OM2 > GB ASV3 and 8		DK = T2-DK
T2	T2 = T2-DB	T2 = DB	GB	GB = KNO-GB
	T2 < T2-DK ASV24	T2 = DK		GB = OM2-GB
	T2 = T2-GB	T2 = GB		GB = T2-GB

Table S17: List of ASVs that differ in the Deseq2 analyses.

ASV	ASV name	Class
ASV1	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria
ASV2	Ralstonia	Gammaproteobacteria
ASV3	Env OPS 17	Bacteroida
ASV4	Betaproteobacteriales	Gammaproteobacteria
ASV6	Bradyrhizobium	Alphaproteobacteria
ASV7	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobiaceae
ASV8	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobiaceae
ASV10	Bacteroida	Bacteroida
ASV12	Burkholderiaceae	Gammaproteobacteria
ASV13	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae
ASV14	Bacilli	Bacilli
ASV24	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobiaceae
ASV73	Rosermartima	Planctomycetacea
ASV87	Microscillaceae	Bacteroida
ASV126	Burkholderiaceae	Gammaproteobacteria

ASV130	Env OPS 17	Bacterioidea
ASV211	Gracilibacteria	Gracilibacteria
ASV212	Paracaedibacteraceae	Alphaproteobacteria

Table S18: Significant differences of the relative abundance between gut microbiomes per genotype, ASVs that differ are shown. >, =, and < show in which treatment the relative abundance of that ASV is higher, equal or lower. Relative abundances that differ between samples are in red. Relative abundances that are equal between samples are in black. Short explanation of representation of the genotypes: KNO(DB) are gut microbiomes from the *D. magna* genotype KNO that was in co-culture with *D. pulex* genotype DB. DB(KNO) are gut microbiomes from the *D. pulex* genotype DB that was in co-culture with *D. magna* genotype KNO.

	Mono vs co same	Mono vs co other	Mono vs mono	Co vs co
KNO	KNO = KNO(DB)	KNO = DB(KNO)	KNO < DB ASV6 and 7	KNO(DB) = DB(KNO)
	KNO = KNO(DK)	KNO = DK(KNO)	KNO = DK	KNO(DK) = DK(KNO)
	KNO = KNO(GB)	KNO = GB(KNO)	KNO = GB	KNO(GB) = GB(KNO)
OM2	OM2 = OM2(DB)	OM2 = DB(OM2)	OM2 = DB	OM2(DB) = DB(OM2)
	OM2 = OM2(DK)	OM2 > DK(OM2) ASV6	OM2 = DK	OM2(DK) = DK(OM2)
	OM2 > OM2(GB) ASV6	OM2 = GB(OM2)	OM2 = GB	OM2(GB) = GB(OM2)
T2	T2 = T2(DB)	T2 = DB(T2)	T2 < DB ASV6 and 7	T2(DB) = DB(T2)
	T2 > T2(DK) ASV8	T2 = DK(T2)	T2 = DK	T2(DK) < DK(T2) ASV2 and 8
	T2 = T2(GB)	T2 > GB(T2) ASV2	T2 = GB	T2(GB) > GB(T2) ASV5
DB	DB = DB(KNO)	DB > KNO(DB) ASV6 and 7		
	DB > DB(OM2) ASV7	DB = OM2(DB)		

	DB > DB(T2) ASV7 and 211	DB > T2(DB) ASV7		
DK	DK = DK(KNO)	DK = KNO(DK)		
	DK = DK(OM2)	DK = OM2(DK)		
	DK = DK(T2)	DK > T2(DK) ASV8		
GB	GB < GB(KNO) ASV24	GB = KNO(GB)		
	GB = GB(OM2)	GB = OM2(GB)		
	GB = GB(T2)	GB < T2(GB) ASV8		

Table SI9: Results of the pairwise comparison

Comparison	Observation	p-value
Gut magna mono with gut magna co	0.47	0.95
Gut pulex mono with gut pulex co	0.49	0.32
Gut and BPK magna mono with gut and BPK magna co	0.46	0.8
Gut and BPK pulex mono with gut and BPK pulex co	0.43	0.74
BPK magna mono with BPK magna co	0.58	0.17
BPK pulex mono with BPK pulex co	0.55	0.56
Gut magna mono with BPK magna mono	0.78	0.01
Gut magna co with BPK magna	0.64	0

Gut magna with BPK magna	0.64	0
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Supplementary figures Chapter 2

Figure S11: Rarefaction curve of the raw sequencing data, zoomed in on the first 5000 reads.

Figure S12: Bacterioplankton communities per genotype.

Figure S13: Gut communities per genotype.

Figure S14: ggplot representing the ASVs at family level that were significantly different between the bacterioplankton and gut microbiomes.

Supplementary information Chapter 3

Supplementary tables Chapter 3

Table SI1: Overview of the ponds and collected *Daphnia magna* genotypes per region. In Kortrijk, we obtained *D. magna* genotypes from the Blauwe Hoeve (K_BH), Kennedypark (K_KP) and Morinnestraat (K_MS), by sampling one individual from the active population in each pond. In addition, two genotypes were obtained from a recent (top layer) resting eggs in Zwevegem (K_ZWE1 and K_ZWE2) as at the time of sampling no active population of *D. magna* was present. In Leuven, all genotypes were obtained from recent (T = top layer sediments) resting eggs of two ponds: Heverlee (L_OM2) and Oud-Heverlee (L_T2, L_T3, L_T7 and L_T8; coding is based on Cousyn et al.⁷⁴).

Genotype	Pond	Coordinates
Kortrijk		
K_BH	Blauwe Hoeve (K1)	50°48'58.63"N, 3°16'17.28"E
K_KP	Kennedypark (K2)	50°48'60.50"N, 3°16'38.45"E
K_MS	Morinnestraat (K3)	50°48'20.83"N, 3°18'44.91"E
K_ZWE1	Zwevegem (K5)	50°49'4.37"N, 3°20'17.37"E
K_ZWE2	Zwevegem (K5)	50°49'4.37"N, 3°20'17.37"E
Leuven		
L_OM2	Heverlee, Abdij van 't Park (L1)	50°51'45.0"N, 04°42'58.8"E
L_T2	Oud Heverlee (L2)	50°50'24.0"N, 04°39'40.4"E
L_T3	Oud Heverlee (L2)	50°50'24.0"N, 04°39'40.4"E
L_T7	Oud Heverlee (L2)	50°50'24.0"N, 04°39'40.4"E
L_T8	Oud Heverlee (L2)	50°50'24.0"N, 04°39'40.4"E

Table S12: Overview of the number of *D. magna* individuals per treatment for the amplicon sequencing, replicates are pooled per genotype.

Genotype	Received a sympatric donor microbiome pre-exposed to <i>M. aeruginosa</i>	Received a sympatric donor microbiome not pre-exposed to <i>M. aeruginosa</i>	Received an allopatric donor microbiome pre-exposed to <i>M. aeruginosa</i>	Received an allopatric donor microbiome not pre-exposed to <i>M. aeruginosa</i>
K_BH	3	4	4	2
K_KP	1	2	2	1
K_MS	3	3	4	5
K_ZWE2	2	2	1	2
L_OM2	2	3	2	3
L_T3	6	3	3	5
L_T7	3	3	3	2
L_T8	3	2	5	5

Table SI3: AIC tables. Showing the df (degrees of freedom) and AIC values (Akaike information criterion) of the different tested models (GLMER, LMER and GLM), with different random factors (1|Region:Pond:Genotype and 1|Region:Pond) on the percentage survived *Daphnia* (PercentSurvived), total number of juveniles (Juveniles), the body size (BodySize) and Shannon entropy (ShannonEntropy).

Model: GLMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond) on percentage survived <i>Daphnia</i>	df	AIC
fit1 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit2 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	26	778.4938
fit3 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit4 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit5 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit6 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit7 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	10	900.2830
fit8 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	26	775.7212
fit9 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	26	775.7212
fit10 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	866.2487
fit11<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit12<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit13<- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit14<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.9995
fit15<- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328

fit16<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit17 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	6	925.7001
fit18 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	6	926.0586
fit19 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	870.6112
fit20 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.995
fit21 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	6	924.4231
fit22 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	864.8624
fit23 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit24 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	864.8624
fit25 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit26 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
fit27 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	4	937.5637
fit28 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	4	936.4223
fit29 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	4	936.7077
fit30 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	8	908.9325
fit31 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
Model: GLMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond) on percentage survived <i>Daphnia</i>	df	AIC
fit1 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit2 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	26	778.0628
fit3 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit4 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit5 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484

fit6 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit7 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	10	905.8093
fit8 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	26	784.2902
fit9 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	26	784.2902
fit10 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	876.9831
fit11<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit12<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit13<- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit14<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.9995
fit15<- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit16<- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit17 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	6	930.3198
fit18 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	6	930.8629
fit19 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	875.2823
fit20 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.9995
fit21 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	6	930.9567
fit22 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	875.5968
fit23 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit24 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	875.5968
fit25 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit26 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
fit27 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Diet + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	4	941.9731

fit28 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	4	941.5949
fit29 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	4	941.9838
fit30 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	8	914.5121
fit31 <- glmer(PercentSurvived~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) on percentage survived <i>Daphnia</i>	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit2 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	26	778.4938
fit3 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit4 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit5 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit6 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit7 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	10	900.2830
fit8 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	26	775.7212
fit9 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	26	775.7212
fit10 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	866.2487
fit11<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit12<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit13<- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit14<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.9995
fit15<- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328

fit16<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit17 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	6	925.7001
fit18 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	6	926.0586
fit19 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	870.6112
fit20 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.9995
fit21 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	6	924.4231
fit22 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	864.8624
fit23 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit24 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	14	864.8624
fit25 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit26 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
fit27 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	4	937.5637
fit28 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	4	936.4223
fit29 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	4	936.7077
fit30 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	8	908.9325
fit31 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond) on percentage survived <i>Daphnia</i>	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit2 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	26	787.0628
fit3 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	679.5210
fit4 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit5 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484

fit6 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit7 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	10	905.8093
fit8 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	26	784.2902
fit9 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	26	784.2902
fit10 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	876.9831
fit11<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit12<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	38	676.7484
fit13<- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	814.7191
fit14<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.9995
fit15<- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit16<- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit17 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	6	930.3198
fit18 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	6	930.8629
fit19 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	875.2823
fit20 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.9995
fit21 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	6	930.9567
fit22 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	875.5968
fit23 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit24 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	14	875.5968
fit25 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	20	813.3328
fit26 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
fit27 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Diet + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	4	941.9731

fit28 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	4	941.5949
fit29 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	4	941.9838
fit30 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	8	914.5121
fit31 <- lmer(PercentSurvived~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataS1)	11	872.3569
Model: GLM on percentage survived <i>Daphnia</i>	df	AIC
fit1 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	37	963.3175
fit2 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=dataS1)	25	978.3827
fit3 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype data=dataS1)	37	963.3175
fit4 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	37	963.3175
fit5 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	37	963.3175
fit6 <- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.0911
fit7 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataS1)	9	958.5865
fit8 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataS1)	25	978.3827
fit9 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Pond, data=dataS1)	25	978.3827
fit10 <- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=dataS1)	13	963.5784
fit11<- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataS1)	37	963.3175
fit12<- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region*Genotype, data=dataS1)	37	963.3175
fit13<- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.0911
fit14<- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.8397
fit15<- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.0911
fit16<- glm(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.0911
fit17 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*MicrobiomeType, data=dataS1)	5	952.8640

fit18 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*Region, data=dataS1)	5	953.4297
fit19 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*Pond, data=dataS1)	13	963.2143
fit20 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.0911
fit21 <- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataS1)	5	953.6085
fit22 <- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataS1)	13	963.5784
fit23 <- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.0911
fit24 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Region*Pond, data=dataS1)	13	963.5784
fit25 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Region*Genotype, data=dataS1)	19	944.0911
fit26 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Pond*Genotype, data=dataS1)	10	930.3863
fit27 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Diet, data=dataS1)	3	950.8786
fit28 <- glm(PercentSurvived~MicrobiomeType, data=dataS1)	3	950.4919
fit29 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Region, data=dataS1)	3	950.8899
fit30 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Pond, data=dataS1)	7	953.2309
fit31 <- glm(PercentSurvived~Genotype, data=dataS1)	10	930.3863
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) on total number of juveniles	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	34	567.8499
fit2 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	26	607.2696
fit3 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	34	567.8499
fit4 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit5 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit6 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	660.8931
fit7 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	10	702.3937

fit8 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	26	604.4970
fit9 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	26	604.4970
fit10 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	14	679.1022
fit11<- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit12<- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit13<- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	660.8931
fit14<- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	660.7503
fit15<- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit16<- lmer(Juveniles~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit17 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	6	722.0320
fit18 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	6	723.6910
fit19 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	14	677.9053
fit20 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	660.7503
fit21 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	6	720.0995
fit22 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	14	677.7159
fit23 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit24 <- lmer(Juveniles~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	14	677.7159
fit25 <- lmer(Juveniles~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit26 <- lmer(Juveniles~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	10	693.0774
fit27 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	4	729.7242
fit28 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	4	729.1697
fit29 <- lmer(Juveniles~Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	4	729.1515

fit30 <- lmer(Juveniles~Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	8	701.7124
fit31 <- lmer(Juveniles~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataN1)	10	693.0774
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond) on total number of juveniles	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	34	567.8499
fit2 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	26	607.9774
fit3 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	34	567.8499
fit4 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit5 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit6 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	660.8931
fit7 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	10	702.4561
fit8 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	26	605.2049
fit9 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	26	605.2049
fit10 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	14	679.4517
fit11<- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit12<- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	34	565.0774
fit13<- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	660.8931
fit14<- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	660.7503
fit15<- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit16<- lmer(Juveniles~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit17 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	6	721.8446
fit18 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	6	724.2793
fit19 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	14	677.9056

fit20 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	660.7503
fit21 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	6	720.2809
fit22 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	14	678.0654
fit23 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit24 <- lmer(Juveniles~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	14	678.0654
fit25 <- lmer(Juveniles~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	18	659.5068
fit26 <- lmer(Juveniles~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	10	693.0774
fit27 <- lmer(Juveniles~Diet + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	4	730.4548
fit28 <- lmer(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	4	729.5013
fit29 <- lmer(Juveniles~Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	4	729.4674
fit30 <- lmer(Juveniles~Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	8	701.7124
fit31 <- lmer(Juveniles~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataN1)	10	693.0774
Model: GLM on total number of juveniles	df	AIC
fit1 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	33	728.7506
fit2 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=dataN1)	25	727.3817
fit3 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype data=dataN1)	33	728.7506
fit4 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	33	728.7506
fit5 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	33	728.7506
fit6 <- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	733.2143
fit7 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataN1)	9	739.1909
fit8 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataN1)	25	727.3817
fit9 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Pond, data=dataN1)	25	727.3817

fit10 <- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=dataN1)	13	732.2617
fit11<- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataN1)	33	728.7506
fit12<- glm(Juveniles~Diet*Region*Genotype, data=dataN1)	33	728.7506
fit13<- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	733.2143
fit14<- glm(Juveniles~Diet*Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	734.7150
fit15<- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	733.2143
fit16<- glm(Juveniles~Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	733.2143
fit17 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*MicrobiomeType, data=dataN1)	5	740.5595
fit18 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*Region, data=dataN1)	5	741.6364
fit19 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*Pond, data=dataN1)	13	732.0911
fit20 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	734.7150
fit21 <- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataN1)	5	736.2109
fit22 <- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataN1)	13	732.2617
fit23 <- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	733.2143
fit24 <- glm(Juveniles~Region*Pond, data=dataN1)	13	732.2617
fit25 <- glm(Juveniles~Region*Genotype, data=dataN1)	17	733.2143
fit26 <- glm(Juveniles~Pond*Genotype, data=dataN1)	9	723.4948
fit27 <- glm(Juveniles~Diet, data=dataN1)	3	738.0408
fit28 <- glm(Juveniles~MicrobiomeType, data=dataN1)	3	738.0400
fit29 <- glm(Juveniles~Region, data=dataN1)	3	738.2020
fit30 <- glm(Juveniles~Pond, data=dataN1)	7	723.6271
fit31 <- glm(Juveniles~Genotype, data=dataN1)	9	723.4948

Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) on body size with Time as a factor	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	130	3972.796
fit2 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	98	4346.979
fit3 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	130	3972.796
fit4 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706
fit5 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706
fit6 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4744.633
fit7 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	34	5120.824
fit8 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	98	4335.889
fit9 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	98	4335.889
fit10 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	50	4921.374
fit11<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706
fit12<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706
fit13<- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4744.633
fit14<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4752.047
fit15<- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit16<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit17 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	5320.426
fit18 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	5323.846
fit19 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	50	4932.989

fit20 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4752.047
fit21 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	5302.237
fit22 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	50	4915.829
fit23 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit24 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	50	4915.829
fit25 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit26 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	34	5116.842
fit27 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	10	5409.607
fit28 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	10	5408.399
fit29 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	10	5405.053
fit30 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	26	5202.653
fit31 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	34	5116.842
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) on body size and without Time as a factor	df	AIC
fit6 <- lmer(BodySize~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	34	5924.408
fit7 <- lmer(BodySize~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	10	6213.966
fit8 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	26	6017.975
fit9 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	26	6017.975
fit10 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	14	6165.752
fit11<- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	34	5921.636
fit12<- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	34	5921.636
fit13<- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	6120.107
fit14<- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	6119.857

fit15<- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit16<- lmer(BodySize~ Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit17 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	6	6260.937
fit18 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	6	6261.900
fit19 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	14	6165.301
fit20 <- lmer(BodySize~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	6119.857
fit21 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	6	6257.900
fit22 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	14	6164.366
fit23 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit24 <- lmer(BodySize~ Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	14	6164.366
fit25 <- lmer(BodySize~ Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit26 <- lmer(BodySize~ Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	10	6211.750
fit27 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	4	6281.985
fit28 <- lmer(BodySize~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	4	6282.222
fit29 <- lmer(BodySize~ Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	4	6282.270
fit30 <- lmer(BodySize~ Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	8	6233.603
fit31 <- lmer(BodySize~ Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=dataNb1)	10	6211.750
Model: LMER with random factor 1 Region:Pond) on body size with time as a factor	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	130	3972.796
fit2 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	98	4354.474
fit3 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	130	3972.796
fit4 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706

fit5 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706
fit6 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4744.633
fit7 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	34	5127.532
fit8 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	98	4343.383
fit9 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	98	4343.383
fit10 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	50	4929.329
fit11<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706
fit12<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	130	3961.706
fit13<- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4744.633
fit14<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4753.938
fit15<- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit16<- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit17 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	5325.497
fit18 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	5325.805
fit19 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	50	4940.432
fit20 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4753.938
fit21 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	5309.176
fit22 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	50	4923.783
fit23 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit24 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	50	4923.783
fit25 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	66	4739.088
fit26 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	34	5118.490

fit27 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Diet + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	10	5412.761
fit28 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	10	5412.071
fit29 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	10	5408.810
fit30 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	26	5211.151
fit31 <- lmer(BodySize~Time*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	34	5118.490
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond) on body size without Time as a factor	df	AIC
fit6 <- lmer(BodySize~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	34	5924.408
fit7 <- lmer(BodySize~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	10	6213.966
fit8 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	26	6017.975
fit9 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	26	6017.975
fit10 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	14	6165.752
fit11<- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	34	5921.636
fit12<- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	34	5921.636
fit13<- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	6120.107
fit14<- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	6119.857
fit15<- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit16<- lmer(BodySize~ Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit17 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	6	6260.781
fit18 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	6	6261.460
fit19 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	14	6165.301
fit20 <- lmer(BodySize~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	6119.857
fit21 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	6	6257.900

fit22 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	14	6164.366
fit23 <- lmer(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit24 <- lmer(BodySize~ Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	14	6164.366
fit25 <- lmer(BodySize~ Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	18	6118.721
fit26 <- lmer(BodySize~ Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	10	6211.750
fit27 <- lmer(BodySize~ Diet + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	4	6281.826
fit28 <- lmer(BodySize~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	4	6281.852
fit29 <- lmer(BodySize~ Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	4	6281.857
fit30 <- lmer(BodySize~ Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	8	6233.603
fit31 <- lmer(BodySize~ Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=dataNb1)	10	6211.750
Model: GLM on body size with Time as a factor	df	AIC
fit1 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	129	5524.048
fit2 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=dataNb1)	97	5511.991
fit3 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype data=dataNb1)	129	5524.048
fit4 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	129	5524.048
fit5 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	129	5524.048
fit6 <- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5480.127
fit7 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataNb1)	33	5493.075
fit8 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataNb1)	97	5511.991
fit9 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Pond, data=dataNb1)	97	5511.991
fit10 <- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=dataNb1)	49	5476.578
fit11<- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	129	5524.048

fit12<- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	129	5524.048
fit13<- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5480.127
fit14<- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5500.340
fit15<- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5480.127
fit16<- glm(BodySize~Time*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5480.127
fit17 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*MicrobiomeType, data=dataNb1)	17	5530.888
fit18 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*Region, data=dataNb1)	17	5539.132
fit19 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*Pond, data=dataNb1)	49	8597.551
fit20 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5500.340
fit21 <- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataNb1)	17	5488.729
fit22 <- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataNb1)	49	5476.578
fit23 <- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5480.127
fit24 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Region*Pond, data=dataNb1)	49	5476.578
fit25 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Region*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	65	5480.127
fit26 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	33	5471.863
fit27 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Diet, data=dataNb1)	9	5532.384
fit28 <- glm(BodySize~Time*MicrobiomeType, data=dataNb1)	9	5533.526
fit29 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Region, data=dataNb1)	9	5531.236
fit30 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Pond, data=dataNb1)	25	5474.772
fit31 <- glm(BodySize~Time*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	33	5471.863
Model: GLM on body size without Time as a factor.	df	AIC
fit6 <- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	33	6348.031

fit7 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataNb1)	9	6307.237
fit8 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataNb1)	25	6334.464
fit9 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet*Region*Pond, data=dataNb1)	25	6334.464
fit10 <- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=dataNb1)	13	6312.808
fit11<- glm(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	33	6348.031
fit12<- glm(BodySize~ Diet*Region*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	33	6348.031
fit13<- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	17	6318.980
fit14<- glm(BodySize~ Diet*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	17	6320.171
fit15<- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	17	6318.980
fit16<- glm(BodySize~ Region*Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	17	6318.980
fit17 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet*MicrobiomeType, data=dataNb1)	5	6303.755
fit18 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet*Region, data=dataNb1)	5	6304.763
fit19 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet*Pond, data=dataNb1)	13	6312.808
fit20 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	17	6320.171
fit21 <- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Region, data=dataNb1)	5	6300.707
fit22 <- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=dataNb1)	13	6312.808
fit23 <- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	17	6318.980
fit24 <- glm(BodySize~ Region*Pond, data=dataNb1)	13	6312.808
fit25 <- glm(BodySize~ Region*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	17	6318.980
fit26 <- glm(BodySize~ Pond*Genotype, data=dataNb1)	9	6305.247
fit27 <- glm(BodySize~ Diet, data=dataNb1)	3	6301.001
fit28 <- glm(BodySize~ MicrobiomeType, data=dataNb1)	3	6301.240

fit29 <- glm(BodySize~ Region, data=dataNb1)	3	6301.290
fit30 <- glm(BodySize~ Pond, data=dataNb1)	7	6302.609
fit31 <- glm(BodySize~ Genotype, data=dataNb1)	9	6305.247
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) on Shannon entropy	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273
fit2 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	26	148.20455
fit3 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273
fit4 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273
fit5 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398
fit6 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	19	193.40674
fit7 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	14	228.37080
fit8 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	26	148.20455
fit9 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	17	211.44541
fit10 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	15	215.89417
fit11<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273
fit12<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398
fit13<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	19	192.40674
fit14<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398

fit15<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	19	192.40674
fit16<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951
fit17 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	8	260.19644
fit18 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	6	281.78455
fit19 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	17	211.44541
fit20 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398
fit21 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	8	258.44870
fit22 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	15	215.89417
fit23 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	19	192.40674
fit24 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	10	247.65894
fit25 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951
fit26 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951
fit27 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	4	290.42593
fit28 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	5	271.52212
fit29 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	4	289.10296
fit30 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Pond + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	10	247.65894
fit31 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond:Genotype) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951
Model: LMER with random factor (1 Region: Pond) on Shannon entropy	df	AIC
fit1 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273
fit2 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	26	148.20455
fit3 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273
fit4 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273

fit5 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398
fit6 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	19	192.40674
fit7 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	14	228.37080
fit8 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	26	148.20455
fit9 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	17	211.44541
fit10 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	15	215.89417
fit11<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	34	83.59273
fit12<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398
fit13<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	19	192.40674
fit14<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398
fit15<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	19	192.40674
fit16<- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region*Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951
fit17 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	8	260.19644
fit18 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	6	279.72577
fit19 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	17	211.44541
fit20 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	21	188.63398
fit21 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	8	258.44870
fit22 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	15	215.89417
fit23 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	19	192.40674
fit24 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region*Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	10	247.65894
fit25 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951
fit26 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Pond*Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951

fit27 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Diet + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	4	289.02175
fit28 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	5	271.50475
fit29 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Region + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	4	287.09977
fit30 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Pond + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	10	247.65894
fit31 <- lmer(ShannonEntropy~Genotype + (1 Region:Pond) , data=div_samp)	12	238.98951
Model: GLM Shannon entropy	df	AIC
fit1 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	33	104.8703
fit2 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=div_samp)	25	278.4255
fit3 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype data=div_samp)	33	104.8703
fit4 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	33	104.8703
fit5 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	20	299.1639
fit6 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	18	283.3489
fit7 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Region, data=div_samp)	13	293.3227
fit8 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=div_samp)	25	278.4255
fit9 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Pond, data=div_samp)	16	298.0675
fit10 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Pond, data=div_samp)	14	285.3937
fit11<- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=div_samp)	33	104.8703
fit12<- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region*Genotype, data=div_samp)	20	299.1639
fit13<- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region*Genotype, data=div_samp)	18	283.3489
fit14<- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	20	299.1639
fit15<- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	18	283.3489
fit16<- glm(ShannonEntropy~Region*Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	11	291.1749

fit17 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*MicrobiomeType, data=div_samp)	7	287.8047
fit18 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Region, data=div_samp)	5	305.5938
fit19 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Pond, data=div_samp)	16	298.0675
fit20 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet*Genotype, data=div_samp)	20	299.1639
fit21 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Region, data=div_samp)	7	285.3937
fit22 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Pond, data=div_samp)	14	285.3937
fit23 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType*Genotype, data=div_samp)	18	283.3489
fit24 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Region*Pond, data=div_samp)	9	288.2207
fit25 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Region*Genotype, data=div_samp)	11	291.1749
fit26 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Pond*Genotype, data=div_samp)	11	291.1749
fit27 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Diet, data=div_samp)	3	301.6665
fit28 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~MicrobiomeType, data=div_samp)	4	282.1380
fit29 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Region, data=div_samp)	3	301.7083
fit30 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Pond, data=div_samp)	9	288.2207
fit31 <- glm(ShannonEntropy~Genotype, data=div_samp)	11	291.1749

Table SI4: Mantel-Haenszel test on *D. magna* survival testing for the effects of diet (donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not), microbiome type (sympatric or allopatric microbiome), genotypes and their interactions on a random selection of one individual per pond.

	χ^2	df	<i>p</i> -value
Diet	3.9	1	0.05
Microbiome type	0.3	1	0.6
Genotype	10.1	7	0.2
Diet x Microbiome type	4.8	3	0.2
Diet x Genotype	22	13	0.06 (*)
Microbiome type x Genotype	36.2	12	<0.0001***
Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	57.9	23	<0.0001***

Table SI5: General linear mixed-effects model on the percentage surviving *D. magna* until the end of the experiment, testing for the effects of diet (donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not), microbiome type (sympatric or allopatric microbiome), genotype and their interactions, with genotype nested within pond and pond nested within the region. (df: model degrees of freedom, df.res: Error or residuals degrees of freedom)

	<i>F</i>	df	df.res	<i>p</i> -value
Diet	0.0260	1	56.00	0.8724
Microbiome type	0.2500	1	707.15	0.6173
Genotype	1.1931	8	665.20	0.3004
Diet x Microbiome type	0.8942	1	56.00	0.3484
Diet x Genotype	0.3105	8	56.00	0.9590
Microbiome type x Genotype	0.0788	8	650.09	0.9997
Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	0.9691	8	56.00	0.4694

Table SI6: Linear mixed model analysis of total *D. magna* fecundity testing for the effects of diet (donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not), microbiome type (sympatric or allopatric microbiome),

genotype and their interactions, with genotype nested within pond and pond nested within the region. (df: model degrees of freedom, df.res: Error or residuals degrees of freedom)

	<i>F</i>	df	df.res	<i>p</i> -value
Diet	0.5943	1	63	0.44366
Microbiome type	0.0156	1	12393	0.90071
Genotype	0.3281	7	12912	0.94159
Diet x Microbiome type	3.7680	1	63	0.05672
Diet x Genotype	0.9521	7	63	0.47368
Microbiome type x Genotype	0.0979	7	11748	0.99845
Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	2.5663	7	63	0.02161 *

Table SI7: Linear mixed model with repeated measures on *D. magna* body size testing for the effects of time (day 3, 6, 10 and 20), diet (donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not), microbiome type (sympatric or allopatric microbiome), genotype and their interactions, with genotype nested within pond and pond nested within the region. (df: model degrees of freedom, df.res: Error or residuals degrees of freedom)

	<i>F</i>	df	df.res	<i>p</i> -value
Time	1114.5867	3	248	<0.0001 ***
Diet	1.4975	1	248	0.222223
Microbiome type	0.0449	1	656.67	0.832314
Genotype	5.9080	7	648.40	<0.0001 ***
Time x Diet	1.0481	3	248	0.371911
Time x Microbiome type	1.4794	3	248	0.220658
Diet x Microbiome type	6.5135	1	248	0.011306 *
Time x Genotype	2.0407	21	248	0.005587 **
Diet x Genotype	1.1571	7	248	0.328219
Microbiome type x Genotype	1.9660	7	617.22	0.057460
Time x Diet x Microbiome type	1.1095	3	248	0.345847
Time x Diet x Genotype	0.7811	21	248	0.741880
Time x Microbiome type x Genotype	0.9332	21	248	0.548387

Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	1.9344	7	248	0.064778
Time x Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	0.5047	21	248	0.967052

Table S18: Pearson correlation test with bonferroni correction testing for pairwise relationships between delta values of different traits (e.g. survival, fecundity, body size at day10 and Shannon entropy). (r = Pearson's correlation coefficient, t = test statistic, df = degrees of freedom, p = p-value)

	Survival	Fecundity	Body size day 10	Shannon entropy
Survival				
Fecundity	$r=-0.05636138$ $t=-0.21122$ $df=14$ $p=0.8358$			
Body size day 10	$r=-0.4872618$ $t=-2.0878$ $df=14$ $p=0.05557$	$r=-0.05982255$ $t=-0.22424$ $df=14$ $p=0.8258$		
Shannon entropy	$r=0.1103409$ $t=0.41539$ $df=14$ $p=0.6841$	$r=0.1909124$ $t=0.72771$ $df=14$ $p=0.4788$	$r=-0.06545091$ $t=-0.24542$ $df=14$ $p=0.8097$	

Table S19: List of bacteria (OTUs) that differ between the donor and recipient microbiomes. Results from the DESeq analysis to investigate the differences in OTUs between donor and recipients. The different OTUs, their class, the log2 fold changes, and adjusted p -values are represented in the table.

OTU	Class	Log2FoldChange	Padj
OTU1-Burkholderiaceae	Gammaproteobacteria	-2.858439	<0.00001 ***
OTU5-Candidatus Hepatincola sp.	Alphaproteobacteria	2.627916	<0.00001 ***
OTU6-Flavobacterium sp.	Bacteroidia	-2.989165	<0.00001 ***
OTU12-Staphylococcus sp.	Bacilli	6.366721	<0.00001 ***
OTU13-Candidatus Limnoluna sp.	Actinobacteria	8.078177	<0.00001 ***
OTU22-Luteolibacter sp.	Verrucomicrobiae	4.702418	<0.00001 ***
OTU47-Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetacia	8.663749	<0.00001 ***

Table S110: Linear mixed model on the exponential value of the Shannon (*D. magna* gut) entropy testing for the effects of diet (donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not), microbiome type (sympatric or allopatric microbiome), genotype and their interactions, with genotype nested within pond and pond nested within the region. (df: model degrees of freedom, df.res: Error or residuals degrees of freedom)

	<i>F</i>	df	df.res	<i>p</i> -value
Diet	35.2519	1	4	0.0040347 **
Microbiome type	89.9831	2	9.37	<0.0001***
Genotype	6.8175	8	423.24	<0.0001***
Microbiome type x Diet	26.6568	2	4	0.0048709 **
Diet x Genotype	85.7493	7	4	0.0003413 ***
Microbiome type x genotype	171.9533	6	4	<0.0001***
Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	131.9702	5	4	0.0001579 ***

Table S111: MANOVA with Bray-Curtis dissimilarity indices on the β -diversity of the *D. magna* gut microbiomes testing for the effects of diet (donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not), microbiome type (sympatric or allopatric microbiome), genotype and their interactions, with genotype nested within pond and pond nested within the region for the full data set, i.e. donors and recipients together. (R^2 = the variation of the dependent variable explained by the model)

	<i>F</i>	R^2	df	<i>p</i> -value
Donor-Recipient	11.0436	0.26177	1	0.001 ***
Microbiome type	1.1603	0.02750	1	0.326
Diet	0.3502	0.00830	1	0.986
Genotype	1.0323	0.19575	8	0.448
Donor-Recipient x Diet	0.3894	0.00923	1	0.969
Diet x Microbiome type	0.9923	0.02352	1	0.434
Diet x Genotype	0.7231	0.11998	7	0.920
Microbiome type x Genotype	1.0430	0.14833	6	0.451
Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	0.9350	0.11081	5	0.577

Table SI12: General linear model on the Bray Curtis distance between donors and recipients, testing for the effects of diet (donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not), microbiome type (sympatric or allopatric microbiome), genotype and their interactions.

	<i>F</i>	df	<i>p</i> -value
Diet	0.3083	1	0.580203
Microbiome type	2.8744	1	0.093705
Genotype	4.3683	2	0.015674 *
Microbiome type x Diet	7.1474	1	0.009019 **
Diet x Genotype	1.5098	2	0.226884
Microbiome type x genotype	3.9019	2	0.023965 *
Diet x Microbiome type x Genotype	7.3070	2	0.001187 **

Supplementary figures Chapter 3

Figure SI1: Total number of juveniles from *D. magna* genotypes pooled together in function of genotype, the microbiome type (i.e. sympatric or allopatric microbiome) and the diet (i.e. donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not). Errorbars represent the standard deviation.

Figure S12: Total *D. magna* fecundity in function of the donor microbiome type (red: allopatric, blue: sympatric microbiome) and donor diet (left panel: donor microbiome not pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa*, right panel: donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa*). A: Allopatric microbiome, S: Sympatric microbiome, C: not pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa*, M: pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa*. Errorbars represent the standard deviation.

Figure S13: Body size at day 3, 6, 10 and 20 of the *D. magna* genotypes pooled together in function of the microbiome type (i.e. sympatric or allopatric microbiome) and the diet (i.e. donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa* or not). Errorbars represent the standard deviation.

Figure S14: Body size at day 3, 6, 10 and 20 of the *D. magna* genotypes pooled together in function of the microbiome type (i.e sympatric or allopatric microbiome). Errorbars represent the standard deviation.

Figure S15: Exponential value of the Shannon entropy of the donor vs the recipient microbiomes. Errorbars represent the standard deviation.

Figure S16: PCA of microbial communities from donor and recipient gut microbiomes based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity indices and grouped by region (dots: genotypes from Kortrijk; crosses: genotypes from Leuven) and microbiome type (red: allopatric microbiome, green: donor microbiomes, blue sympatric microbiomes). Left panel full data set (donor + recipients), right panel data set with only the recipients (in the recipients only, there were no significant factors/interactions).

Figure S17: Exponential value of the Shannon entropy of the donor populations grouped per region and donor diet, representing the region x donor diet interaction in the donor microbiomes. Errorbars represent the standard deviation.

Figure S18: Exponential value of the Shannon entropy of the genotypes grouped per donor diet and donor microbiome type, representing the microbiome type x donor diet x recipient genotype interaction. Left panel: donor microbiome not pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa*, right panel: donor microbiome pre-exposed to *M. aeruginosa*. Numbers above the bars represent the number of guts sequenced per treatment. There was no correlation between the number of guts per sample and the Shannon entropy ($r=0.246$, $t=1.3884$, $df=30$, $p=0.1753$). Results for K_BH and K_KP are partially lacking due to failure of sequencing or low number of reads/sample (these samples were after rarefaction excluded from further analysis).

Supplementary information Chapter 4

Characterization of the fungus

To characterize the fungal strain, samples of infected *Daphnia* with visible signs of the fungal infection and *Daphnia* with no visible infections were compared. Fifteen infected animals were transferred per five individuals in a sterile Eppendorf tube. Guts from 60 infected animals were dissected and transferred per 20 guts to 10 µL of sterile MilliQ water. Samples were stored at -20°C until further processing. DNA of all samples was extracted using a PowerSoil DNA isolation kit (MO BIO laboratories). The total DNA yield was determined using a Qubit dsDNA HS assay (Invitrogen) on 1 µL of sample. A PCR reaction was run using a combination of primers for the large subunit (LSU) and small subunit (SSU) region (see Table SI10; White et al., 1990; Vilgalys and Sun, 1994) on all of the template (98°C – 30s, 30 cycles of 98°C – 10s, 55°C – 45s, 72°C – 30s, and 72°C – 5s, 12°C hold) using the Platinum SuperFi DNA polymerase (ThermoFisher). PCR products were subsequently purified using the QIAquick PCR purification kit (Qiagen) and were sent for Sanger sequencing to LGC Genomics (Berlin, Germany).

The Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST), BLASTn was performed on the obtained fasta files, using FungiDB (Basenko et al., 2018). All query sequences were blasted with all the fungal species present in the database, including oomycetes. The Expectation value (E-value, expected number of hits) was set as 50% of the length of the query sequence. Maximum descriptions (number of descriptions/alignment to show) were set to 50 to avoid compromising the e-value and possible sequence matches. Additionally, the low complexity filter mode was set off to avoid omission of results which contain repetitive and low complexity sequences. Similar settings were performed for all blasted sequences. Obtained results of FungiDB were verified with NCBI. To improve the sequence matches with fungi, BLAST search was limited to RefSeq sequences only (using BioProject Number specific to Fungi, 177353, Schoch et al., 2014). Blasting results (score, E-value) can be found in Table SI11. In addition, a reference based multiple sequence alignment was performed to create a multiple sequence alignment table, using PRANK (probabilistic multiple alignment program for DNA) hosted by wasabi using the HKY model (Veidenberg et al., 2015). *Daphnia* with visible or non-visible infection showed the highest match with *Aspergillus aculeatus* and *Aspergillus niger*. Multiple sequence alignment further revealed a highly specific match with nucleotides 1 to 1900 for *Aspergillus aculeatus* KV879170 (strain: ATCC 16872, Figure SI8). No specific match with *Aspergillus niger* was found in the multiple sequence alignment. Based on these results, we concluded that the fungal infection is related to *Aspergillus aculeatus* ATCC 16872.

Uptake bacterial strains from environment by gut

The uptake of bacteria by the recipient *Daphnia* from the environment (donor bacterioplankton), was analysed with Unionplots. Two Unionplots were made, one for each microbiome type. In each Unionplot, the donor bacterioplankton was compared with the gut microbiomes from the *Daphnia* that received a control treatment or a stressor treatment (Figure S13). When *Daphnia* received a laboratory donor inoculum, they take up 35.8% of the donor inoculum. In the control treatment, 41.0% of the gut microbiomes consists of ASVs present in the donor laboratory bacterioplankton, while in the stressor treatments, only 34.5% of the gut microbiomes consists of ASVs present in the donor laboratory bacterioplankton. When *Daphnia* received a natural donor inoculum, they take up 31.4% of the donor inoculum. The difference in uptake between *Daphnia* that received a control or stressor treatment is smaller when they received a natural donor inoculum than when they received a laboratory donor inoculum. In the control treatment, 32.5% of the gut microbiomes consists of ASVs present in the donor natural bacterioplankton, and in the stressor treatments, 31.6% of the gut microbiomes consists of ASVs present in the donor natural bacterioplankton.

Supplementary tables Chapter 4

Table SI1: Overview of the number of pooled recipient guts per microbial sample. Green: samples in the dataset. Orange: samples lost due to rarefaction. Red: samples lost during molecular work

Stressor	Microbiome	Clone	Replicate	Guts
Control	Lab	KNO	1	9
Control	Lab	KNO	2	8
Control	Lab	KNO	3	9
Infection	Lab	KNO	1	8
Infection	Lab	KNO	2	7
Infection	Lab	KNO	3	8
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	KNO	1	9
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	KNO	2	5
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	KNO	3	8
Combi	Lab	KNO	1	6
Combi	Lab	KNO	2	7
Combi	Lab	KNO	3	10
Control	Natural	KNO	1	8
Control	Natural	KNO	2	7
Control	Natural	KNO	3	9
Infection	Natural	KNO	1	8
Infection	Natural	KNO	2	5
Infection	Natural	KNO	3	8
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	KNO	1	10
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	KNO	2	9
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	KNO	3	9
Combi	Natural	KNO	1	8
Combi	Natural	KNO	2	8
Combi	Natural	KNO	3	9
Control	Lab	OM2	1	10
Control	Lab	OM2	2	9
Control	Lab	OM2	3	10
Infection	Lab	OM2	1	8

Infection	Lab	OM2	2	8
Infection	Lab	OM2	3	8
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	OM2	1	6
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	OM2	2	7
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	OM2	3	4
Combi	Lab	OM2	1	9
Combi	Lab	OM2	2	8
Combi	Lab	OM2	3	8
Control	Natural	OM2	1	9
Control	Natural	OM2	2	9
Control	Natural	OM2	3	4
Infection	Natural	OM2	1	7
Infection	Natural	OM2	2	9
Infection	Natural	OM2	3	8
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	OM2	1	8
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	OM2	2	9
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	OM2	3	8
Combi	Natural	OM2	1	7
Combi	Natural	OM2	2	6
Combi	Natural	OM2	3	10
Control	Lab	T8	1	9
Control	Lab	T8	2	7
Control	Lab	T8	3	3
Infection	Lab	T8	1	8
Infection	Lab	T8	2	8
Infection	Lab	T8	3	3
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	T8	1	8
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	T8	2	9
<i>Microcystis</i>	Lab	T8	3	5
Combi	Lab	T8	1	9
Combi	Lab	T8	2	6
Combi	Lab	T8	3	4
Control	Natural	T8	1	4

Control	Natural	T8	2	8
Control	Natural	T8	3	3
Infection	Natural	T8	1	2
Infection	Natural	T8	2	4
Infection	Natural	T8	3	5
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	T8	1	6
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	T8	2	6
<i>Microcystis</i>	Natural	T8	3	5
Combi	Natural	T8	1	5
Combi	Natural	T8	2	8
Combi	Natural	T8	3	5

Table S12: Overview results for Pearson correlation between the number of guts per sample and ASV richness. Raw and adjusted (adjusted for multiple comparisons through the control of the false discovery rate (FDR)) p-values are given. Significant results ($p < 0.05$) are indicated with *. Highly significant results ($p < 0.001$) are indicated with ***.

	df	ASV richness			
		cor	t	p-value	Adjusted p-value
Stressor	2	-0.9305785	-3.5948	0.06942	0.38185
Microbiome	-	-	-	-	-
Genotype	1	-0.560576	-0.67694	0.6212	0.62120
Stressor x Microbiome	6	-0.6089163	-1.8803	0.1091	0.38185
Stressor x Genotype	10	-0.3261138	-1.0909	0.3009	0.46095
Microbiome x Genotype	4	-0.4297461	-0.95187	0.3951	0.46095
Stressor x Microbiome x Genotype	21	-0.2100054	-0.98432	0.3362	0.46095
Stressor x Microbiome x Genotype x Replicate	40	-0.1449094	-0.92626	0.3599	0.46095

Table S13: Survival analysis, significant four-way interaction (fungus x cyanobacterium x microbiome x genotype) split up per fixed factor. Per fixed factor all interactions were further investigated.

Factor	χ^2	Df	p-value
Within genotype a microbiome x fungus x cyano interactions?			
KNO	8.6	7	0.3
OM2	5.4	7	0.6
T8	10	7	0.2
Within genotype a microbiome x fungus interaction?			
KNO	5.9	3	0.1
OM2	0.4	3	0.9
T8	1.9	3	0.6
Within genotype a microbiome x cyano interactions?			
KNO	3	3	0.4
OM2	1.4	3	0.7
T8	4.5	3	0.2
Within genotype a fungus x cyano interactions?			
KNO	2.6	3	0.5
OM2	4.4	3	0.2
T8	2.3	3	0.5
Within genotype a microbiome effect?			
KNO	2.6	1	0.1
OM2	0.2	1	0.7
T8	1.6	1	0.2
Within genotype a fungus effect?			
KNO	2.3	1	0.1
OM2	0	1	1
T8	0.1	1	0.7
Within genotype a cyano effect?			
KNO	0.3	1	0.6
OM2	1.1	1	0.3
T8	1.6	1	0.2
Within microbiome a genotype x fungus x cyano interactions?			
Lab	14	11	0.2
Nat	22	11	0.02**
Within microbiome a genotype x fungus interaction?			
Lab	3.2	5	0.7
Nat	13.3	5	0.02**

Within microbiome a genotype x cyano interactions?			
Lab	1.5	5	0.9
Nat	18.2	5	0.003***
Within microbiome a fungus x cyano interactions?			
Lab	9.5	3	0.02**
Nat	0.8	3	0.9
Within microbiome a genotype effect?			
Lab	1	2	0.6
Nat	12.7	2	0.002***
Within microbiome a fungus effect?			
Lab	0.8	1	0.4
Nat	0.2	1	0.7
Within microbiome a cyano effect?			
Lab	0.2	1	0.6
Nat	0.1	1	0.7
Within fungus a microbiome x genotype x cyano interactions?			
Fungus	14.1	11	0.2
Not Fungus	20.2	11	0.04*
Within fungus a genotype x microbiome interaction?			
Fungus	7.7	5	0.2
Not Fungus	8	5	0.2
Within fungus a genotype x cyano interactions?			
Fungus	11	5	0.05*
Not Fungus	7.2	5	0.2
Within fungus a microbiome x cyano interactions?			
Fungus	3.5	3	0.3
Not Fungus	5.6	3	0.1
Within fungus a genotype effect?			
Fungus	6.8	2	0.03*
Not Fungus	3.8	2	0.2
Within fungus a microbiome effect?			
Fungus	0.2	1	0.7
Not Fungus	0	1	0.9
Within fungus a cyano effect?			
Fungus	1.2	1	0.3
Not Fungus	1.1	1	0.3

Within cyano a microbiome x genotype x fungus interactions?			
Cyano	10.3	11	0.5
Not Cyano	26	11	0.006***
Within cyano a genotype x microbiome interaction?			
Cyano	2.6	5	0.8
Not Cyano	17.4	5	0.004***
Within cyano a genotype x fungus interactions?			
Cyano	4.4	5	0.5
Not Cyano	14.5	5	0.01**
Within cyano a microbiome x fungus interactions?			
Cyano	7.4	3	0.06
Not Cyano	2.7	3	0.4
Within cyano a genotype effect?			
Cyano	1.3	2	0.5
Not Cyano	12	2	0.002***
Within cyano a microbiome effect?			
Cyano	0.1	1	0.8
Not Cyano	0.3	1	0.6
Within cyano a fungus effect?			
Cyano	3.1	1	0.08
Not Cyano	0.2	1	0.7

Table SI4: Fecundity analysis, significant four-way interaction (fungus x cyanobacterium x microbiome x genotype) split up per fixed factor. Per fixed factor all interactions were further investigated.

Factor	F	Df	Df res	p-value
Lab microbiome				
Genotype	22.52	2	292.26	<0.0001
Fungus	2.51	1	292.01	0.11
Cyano	42.45	1	292.02	<0.0001
Genotype x Fungus	3.13	2	292.05	0.04
Genotype x Cyano	3.90	2	292.01	0.02
Fungus x Cyano	1.15	1	292.01	0.28
Genotype x Fungus x Cyano	4.62	2	292.03	0.01
Natural microbiome				
Genotype	14.43	2	295.11	<0.0001
Fungus	13.77	1	295.02	0.0002
Cyano	126.36	1	295.02	<0.0001
Genotype x Fungus	1.05	2	295.01	0.35
Genotype x Cyano	9.28	2	295.04	0.0001
Fungus x Cyano	0.75	1	295.04	0.38
Genotype x Fungus x Cyano	0.80	2	295.03	0.45
Fungus present				
Genotype	27.29	2	290.37	<0.0001
Microbiome	0.87	1	289.25	0.35
Cyano	105.63	1	289.13	<0.0001
Genotype x Microbiome	7.31	2	289.55	0.0007
Genotype x Cyano	12.32	2	289.37	<0.0001
Microbiome x Cyano	0.36	1	289.07	0.54
Genotype x Microbiome x Cyano	1.93	2	289.35	0.15
Fungus absent				
Genotype	8.78	2	298.31	0.0001
Microbiome	3.71	1	298.02	0.05
Cyano	43.53	1	298.07	<0.0001
Genotype x Microbiome	0.03	2	298.03	0.97
Genotype x Cyano	2.05	2	298.05	0.13
Microbiome x Cyano	1.16	1	298.07	0.28
Genotype x Microbiome x Cyano	2.88	2	298.02	0.06
Cyanobacterium present				
Genotype	17.74	2	291.84	<0.0001
Microbiome	11.75	1	291.07	0.0006

Fungus	4.84	1	291.07	0.02
Genotype x Microbiome	4.93	2	291.31	0.007
Genotype x Fungus	0.51	2	291.42	0.60
Microbiome x Fungus	2.00	1	291.01	0.15
Genotype x Microbiome x Fungus	0.13	2	291.31	0.87
Cyanobacterium absent				
Genotype	22.67	2	296.51	<0.0001
Microbiome	0.33	1	296.01	0.56
Fungus	5.85	1	296.04	0.01
Genotype x Microbiome	0.64	2	296.03	0.52
Genotype x Fungus	1.63	2	296.01	0.19
Microbiome x Fungus	0.03	1	296.15	0.85
Genotype x Microbiome x Fungus	5.01	2	296.04	0.007
KNO				
Microbiome	6.70	1	215.07	0.01
Fungus	9.68	1	215.05	0.002
Cyano	77.62	1	215.04	<0.0001
Microbiome x Fungus	1.24	1	215.15	0.26
Microbiome x Cyano	2.56	1	215.03	0.11
Fungus x Cyano	3.33	1	215.09	0.07
Microbiome x Fungus x Cyano	4.51	1	215.05	0.03
OM2				
Microbiome	2.56	1	206.02	0.11
Fungus	1.22	1	06.01	0.26
Cyano	69.46	1	206.04	<0.0001
Microbiome x Fungus	0.18	1	206.21	0.66
Microbiome x Cyano	0.00	1	206.19	0.97
Fungus x Cyano	0.33	1	206.10	0.56
Microbiome x Fungus x Cyano	0.13	1	206.01	0.71
T8				
Microbiome	0.44	1	164.33	0.50
Fungus	1.25	1	164.16	0.26
Cyano	5.71	1	164.67	0.01
Microbiome x Fungus	5.67	1	164.31	0.01
Microbiome x Cyano	0.14	1	164.09	0.70
Fungus x Cyano	0.55	1	165.41	0.45
Microbiome x Fungus x Cyano	3.91	1	164.64	0.05

Table SI5: Post-hoc body size. Difference between different stressor treatments

Contrast	Estimate	SE	Df	t-ratio	p-value
Control – Fungus	0.10	0.02	204	4.21	0.0002
Control – Cyano	0.22	0.02	204	8.94	<0.0001
Control – Combi	0.27	0.02	204	10.91	<0.0001
Fungus – Cyano	0.11	0.02	204	4.64	<0.0001
Fungus – Combi	0.16	0.02	204	6.62	<0.0001
Cyano – Combi	0.05	0.02	204	2.03	0.18

Table S16: Results of the Pearson Correlation tests between and within life history traits and ASV richness of the gut microbial community. Significant results ($p < 0.05$) are indicated with *. Highly significant results ($p < 0.001$) are indicated with ***.

	DF	cor	t	p	Adjusted p
Survival & ASV richness	40	-0.01893206	-0.11976	0.9053	0.905300
Fecundity & ASV richness	40	-0.02058545	-0.13022	0.897	0.905300
Body Size & ASV richness	40	0.05825961	0.36909	0.714	0.905300
Survival & Fecundity	70	0.3216004	2.8417	0.005875*	0.017625*
Survival & Body Size	70	0.1668733	1.416	0.1612	0.332400
Fecundity & Body Size	70	0.3343081	2.9678	0.004103*	0.017625*

Table S17: Overview orders in the gut microbial samples of the recipients and donors. Mean and standard deviation (STDV) are given for the relative abundance per order.

	Recipients											
	C		F		M		MF		L		N	
	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV
Betaproteobacteriales	55,86%	21,82%	37,09%	26,51%	40,22%	26,43%	61,64%	29,86%	54,80%	26,25%	41,35%	26,20%
Pseudomonadales	20,22%	23,54%	29,88%	26,56%	25,80%	28,21%	12,25%	11,80%	11,76%	13,50%	34,24%	27,51%
Bacteroidales	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,04%	0,98%	3,24%	4,55%	12,88%	0,49%	2,29%	1,83%	8,15%
Verrucomicrobiales	3,06%	2,60%	6,99%	5,13%	7,50%	12,38%	6,49%	5,30%	6,44%	9,09%	5,12%	4,83%
Flavobacteriales	3,20%	5,31%	1,07%	1,73%	0,87%	1,53%	2,89%	4,89%	1,97%	4,19%	2,07%	3,51%
Planctomycetales	0,26%	0,50%	2,18%	2,73%	0,45%	1,05%	0,81%	1,62%	0,39%	1,81%	1,41%	1,53%
Actinomycetales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,64%	1,80%	0,00%	0,00%	0,25%	1,14%
Rhizobiales	7,22%	9,44%	6,19%	10,05%	0,84%	0,75%	1,54%	1,75%	4,54%	7,79%	3,87%	7,49%
Micrococcales	1,27%	1,30%	3,29%	5,08%	3,97%	4,90%	1,67%	2,15%	3,90%	4,76%	1,03%	0,98%
Cytophagales	1,22%	2,03%	2,15%	3,54%	1,51%	1,88%	0,82%	1,39%	1,24%	2,01%	1,66%	2,65%
Lactobacillales	1,72%	4,29%	5,41%	13,28%	3,65%	6,45%	2,21%	3,40%	4,69%	9,84%	1,56%	3,67%
Legionellales	0,84%	2,73%	0,36%	0,67%	0,01%	0,03%	0,32%	0,76%	0,04%	0,09%	0,82%	2,24%
Bacillales	0,43%	1,03%	0,38%	0,87%	0,95%	2,14%	1,06%	1,59%	0,90%	1,84%	0,42%	0,83%
Chitinophagales	0,43%	0,94%	0,96%	1,90%	0,62%	0,99%	0,36%	0,47%	0,52%	1,39%	0,67%	0,91%
Caulobacterales	0,11%	0,13%	0,04%	0,07%	0,81%	2,45%	0,15%	0,32%	0,45%	1,73%	0,10%	0,22%
Acetobacterales	0,11%	0,23%	0,11%	0,14%	0,01%	0,03%	0,10%	0,24%	0,03%	0,10%	0,14%	0,22%
Rhodobacterales	0,20%	0,23%	0,36%	0,55%	0,51%	0,90%	0,72%	1,74%	0,45%	1,10%	0,39%	0,67%
Pirellulales	0,19%	0,31%	1,82%	2,14%	0,70%	1,46%	0,09%	0,21%	0,14%	0,63%	1,31%	1,78%
#N/B	1,73%	3,13%	0,48%	0,36%	0,78%	1,16%	0,11%	0,19%	1,32%	2,47%	0,39%	0,75%
Frankiales	0,11%	0,17%	0,24%	0,23%	1,21%	2,58%	0,31%	0,74%	0,28%	0,56%	0,67%	1,94%
Sphingomonadales	0,03%	0,03%	0,13%	0,15%	0,06%	0,12%	0,03%	0,05%	0,04%	0,09%	0,08%	0,12%
Sphingobacteriales	0,16%	0,26%	0,14%	0,22%	0,25%	0,40%	0,01%	0,02%	0,11%	0,28%	0,20%	0,27%
Corynebacteriales	0,16%	0,49%	0,17%	0,23%	0,18%	0,31%	0,26%	0,58%	0,20%	0,41%	0,17%	0,41%
Reyranellales	0,02%	0,05%	0,02%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%	0,04%	0,02%	0,02%
Propionibacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
PeM15	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
Diplorickettsiales	0,26%	0,56%	0,11%	0,32%	1,04%	2,96%	0,81%	1,51%	1,02%	2,22%	0,00%	0,01%

Micropepsales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
SBR1031	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Tepidisphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Caedibacterales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Azospirillales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Candidatus_Falkowbacteria	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
CHAB-XI-27	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Coxiellales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Salinisphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%

Recipients																
	CXL		FXL		MXL		MFXL		CXN		FXN		MXN		MFXN	
	Mean	STDV														
Betaproteobacteriales	64,48%	19,21%	41,52%	25,22%	48,75%	30,01%	61,75%	32,30%	45,81%	21,78%	34,14%	29,28%	25,30%	7,74%	61,53%	32,21%
Pseudomonadales	12,92%	17,50%	14,56%	14,84%	7,68%	6,66%	14,04%	17,18%	28,73%	28,31%	40,09%	28,72%	57,52%	21,35%	10,46%	4,63%
Bacteroidales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1,54%	4,06%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,05%	0,00%	0,00%	9,11%	18,22%
Verrucomicrobiales	2,57%	2,79%	4,50%	3,58%	10,74%	14,82%	7,64%	5,02%	3,63%	2,48%	8,65%	5,60%	1,83%	2,12%	5,33%	6,07%
Flavobacteriales	3,86%	6,95%	0,62%	0,90%	1,14%	1,88%	1,50%	2,41%	2,42%	2,88%	1,37%	2,15%	0,40%	0,46%	4,28%	6,70%
Planctomycetales	0,01%	0,02%	2,12%	4,24%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,55%	0,64%	2,23%	1,64%	1,25%	1,52%	1,62%	2,10%
Actinomycetales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1,27%	2,54%
Rhizobiales	6,09%	6,21%	11,17%	15,43%	0,72%	0,35%	1,89%	1,46%	8,53%	12,80%	2,87%	2,48%	1,05%	1,23%	1,19%	2,17%
Micrococcales	1,77%	1,58%	6,42%	7,38%	5,54%	5,58%	2,24%	2,80%	0,68%	0,54%	1,21%	0,91%	1,21%	1,34%	1,10%	1,46%
Cytophagales	1,09%	1,24%	2,11%	4,02%	1,23%	1,77%	0,63%	1,08%	1,37%	2,83%	2,17%	3,59%	2,01%	2,22%	1,00%	1,80%
Lactobacillales	0,93%	1,32%	11,11%	21,11%	5,33%	7,71%	3,72%	4,42%	2,64%	6,35%	1,61%	2,55%	0,72%	1,21%	0,70%	1,19%
Legionellales	0,03%	0,08%	0,09%	0,18%	0,00%	0,00%	0,06%	0,11%	1,78%	3,99%	0,53%	0,83%	0,03%	0,04%	0,59%	1,06%
Bacillales	0,13%	0,20%	0,79%	1,38%	1,26%	2,70%	1,71%	2,14%	0,77%	1,49%	0,11%	0,13%	0,39%	0,16%	0,40%	0,44%
Chitinophagales	0,04%	0,11%	1,58%	3,10%	0,44%	0,89%	0,44%	0,54%	0,89%	1,29%	0,55%	0,47%	0,93%	1,20%	0,28%	0,47%
Caulobacterales	0,14%	0,16%	0,02%	0,04%	1,23%	3,07%	0,06%	0,11%	0,08%	0,10%	0,05%	0,08%	0,08%	0,17%	0,24%	0,46%
Acetobacterales	0,00%	0,01%	0,16%	0,20%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,23%	0,30%	0,08%	0,09%	0,04%	0,04%	0,21%	0,32%
Rhodobacterales	0,16%	0,25%	0,43%	0,85%	0,30%	0,41%	1,25%	2,50%	0,26%	0,21%	0,32%	0,33%	0,89%	1,45%	0,18%	0,26%
Pirellulales	0,01%	0,01%	0,74%	1,47%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,41%	0,35%	2,55%	2,31%	1,93%	2,00%	0,18%	0,29%

Acidithiobacillales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Entothionellales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
MSBL9	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Spirochaetales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Subgroup_7	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
ADurb.Bin180	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Bacteroidetes_VC2.1_Bac22	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Desulfovibrionales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Methylospirales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Micropepsales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
SBR1031	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Tepidisphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Caedibacterales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Azospirillales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Candidatus_Falkowbacteria	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
CHAB-XI-27	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Coxiellales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Salinisphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%

	Donor				Sample type				Donor + recipient	
	L		N		Donor		Recipient			
	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV	Mean	STDV
Betaproteobacteriales	23,66%	19,31%	42,52%	24,78%	33,09%	22,39%	48,40%	26,78%	46,48%	26,55%
Pseudomonadales	4,21%	2,41%	1,37%	1,63%	2,79%	2,41%	22,46%	23,94%	20,00%	23,32%
Bacteroidales	0,00%	0,00%	0,25%	0,13%	0,12%	0,16%	1,13%	5,82%	1,00%	5,45%
Verrucomicrobiales	0,49%	0,39%	4,36%	6,56%	2,43%	4,67%	5,81%	7,32%	5,39%	7,09%
Flavobacteriales	1,68%	2,50%	10,48%	6,81%	6,08%	6,66%	2,02%	3,84%	2,53%	4,40%
Planctomycetales	0,19%	0,33%	0,03%	0,05%	0,11%	0,23%	0,87%	1,74%	0,78%	1,64%
Actinomycetales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,12%	0,78%	0,11%	0,73%
Rhizobiales	0,20%	0,12%	0,47%	0,53%	0,33%	0,37%	4,22%	7,56%	3,73%	7,18%
Micrococcales	40,12%	37,86%	2,62%	0,91%	21,37%	31,55%	2,53%	3,76%	4,89%	12,57%
Cytophagales	7,14%	11,31%	1,64%	1,31%	4,39%	7,81%	1,44%	2,32%	1,81%	3,48%

Lactobacillales	0,15%	0,23%	0,62%	1,06%	0,38%	0,73%	3,20%	7,64%	2,85%	7,20%
Legionellales	0,16%	0,20%	0,00%	0,00%	0,08%	0,16%	0,41%	1,58%	0,37%	1,48%
Bacillales	0,07%	0,06%	0,01%	0,02%	0,04%	0,05%	0,67%	1,45%	0,59%	1,38%
Chitinophagales	15,64%	26,48%	7,41%	5,37%	11,53%	17,68%	0,59%	1,18%	1,96%	6,91%
Caulobacterales	0,74%	0,45%	0,44%	0,54%	0,59%	0,47%	0,28%	1,26%	0,32%	1,19%
Acetobacterales	0,03%	0,05%	0,24%	0,27%	0,13%	0,21%	0,08%	0,18%	0,09%	0,18%
Rhodobacterales	0,57%	0,60%	3,02%	1,45%	1,79%	1,67%	0,42%	0,91%	0,59%	1,11%
Pirellulales	0,07%	0,13%	0,17%	0,26%	0,12%	0,19%	0,69%	1,42%	0,62%	1,34%
#N/B	0,54%	0,84%	0,58%	0,60%	0,56%	0,65%	0,88%	1,90%	0,84%	1,79%
Frankiales	0,04%	0,07%	5,97%	1,72%	3,01%	3,43%	0,47%	1,39%	0,78%	1,91%
Sphingomonadales	0,16%	0,08%	3,65%	4,47%	1,91%	3,42%	0,06%	0,10%	0,29%	1,28%
Sphingobacterales	0,01%	0,01%	7,74%	7,24%	3,88%	6,24%	0,15%	0,27%	0,62%	2,40%
Corynebacterales	0,01%	0,02%	0,17%	0,14%	0,09%	0,12%	0,19%	0,41%	0,17%	0,38%
Reyranellales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,03%	0,01%	0,03%
Propionibacterales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,01%
PeM15	0,00%	0,00%	0,17%	0,27%	0,08%	0,20%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,07%
Diplorickettsiales	0,00%	0,00%	0,15%	0,23%	0,07%	0,17%	0,53%	1,67%	0,48%	1,57%
Coriobacterales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Pasteurellales	0,01%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,02%	0,05%	0,15%	0,05%	0,14%
Enterobacterales	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,04%	0,01%	0,04%
Aeromonadales	0,49%	0,73%	0,05%	0,07%	0,27%	0,52%	0,05%	0,26%	0,08%	0,31%
Fimbriimonadales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,03%	0,01%	0,03%
Elsterales	0,05%	0,09%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,06%	0,01%	0,03%	0,01%	0,04%
Selenomonadales	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%	0,01%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,01%
Saccharimonadales	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,01%
Armatimonadales	0,00%	0,00%	0,20%	0,34%	0,10%	0,24%	0,00%	0,01%	0,02%	0,09%
Xanthomonadales	0,00%	0,01%	0,48%	0,52%	0,24%	0,42%	1,35%	8,52%	1,21%	7,96%
Oligoflexales	0,00%	0,00%	0,09%	0,09%	0,04%	0,07%	0,01%	0,03%	0,01%	0,04%
Subgroup_2	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Alteromonadales	1,34%	1,94%	0,01%	0,02%	0,68%	1,43%	0,03%	0,18%	0,11%	0,54%
Gemmatales	0,00%	0,00%	0,08%	0,12%	0,04%	0,09%	0,00%	0,02%	0,01%	0,04%
Paracaedibacterales	1,17%	1,86%	0,02%	0,02%	0,60%	1,33%	0,00%	0,02%	0,08%	0,48%
Babeliales	0,13%	0,23%	0,02%	0,01%	0,08%	0,16%	0,00%	0,02%	0,01%	0,06%

Chthoniobacterales	0,17%	0,30%	0,76%	1,29%	0,47%	0,90%	0,33%	1,92%	0,35%	1,82%
Myxococcales	0,09%	0,10%	0,03%	0,02%	0,06%	0,08%	0,01%	0,03%	0,01%	0,04%
Fusobacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,01%	0,01%	0,02%	0,41%	2,53%	0,36%	2,37%
Deinococcales	0,00%	#####	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,11%	0,02%	0,10%
Cellvibrionales	0,00%	0,00%	0,11%	0,05%	0,05%	0,07%	0,02%	0,15%	0,03%	0,14%
Oceanospirillales	0,00%	0,00%	0,14%	0,16%	0,07%	0,13%	0,01%	0,06%	0,02%	0,07%
Rickettsiales	0,17%	0,29%	0,04%	0,05%	0,10%	0,20%	0,00%	0,02%	0,02%	0,07%
Gammaproteobacteria_Incertae_Sedis	0,00%	0,00%	0,05%	0,05%	0,03%	0,04%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,02%
Bdellovibrionales	0,20%	0,17%	0,07%	0,06%	0,13%	0,14%	0,01%	0,02%	0,02%	0,06%
Cardiobacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Rhodothermales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,09%	0,01%	0,09%
Micavibrionales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Rhodospirillales	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Isosphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,67%	1,12%	0,34%	0,80%	0,00%	0,00%	0,04%	0,28%
OPB56	0,02%	0,04%	0,64%	1,10%	0,33%	0,77%	0,00%	0,00%	0,04%	0,28%
Microtrichales	0,00%	0,00%	0,36%	0,60%	0,18%	0,42%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,15%
Methylococcales	0,00%	0,00%	0,36%	0,44%	0,18%	0,34%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,13%
Campylobacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,32%	0,25%	0,16%	0,24%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,09%
Clostridiales	0,00%	0,00%	0,29%	0,32%	0,15%	0,26%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,10%
Steroidobacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,13%	0,16%	0,06%	0,12%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,05%
Phycisphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,12%	0,20%	0,06%	0,14%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,05%
Desulfuromonadales	0,00%	0,00%	0,08%	0,10%	0,04%	0,08%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,03%
211ds20	0,00%	0,00%	0,08%	0,14%	0,04%	0,10%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,04%
Opitutales	0,00%	0,00%	0,06%	0,10%	0,03%	0,07%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%
Pedosphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,05%	0,04%	0,02%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
Balneolales	0,00%	0,00%	0,04%	0,07%	0,02%	0,05%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%
Run-SP154	0,00%	0,00%	0,04%	0,06%	0,02%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%
Desulfobacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,03%	0,02%	0,03%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
Ignavibacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,03%	0,02%	0,03%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
Syntrophobacteriales	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,03%	0,02%	0,03%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
Anaerolineales	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,03%	0,02%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
Omnitrophales	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,03%	0,01%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
Gemmatimonadales	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,04%	0,01%	0,03%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%

Pla1_lineage	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Unknown_Order	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Caldilineales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Cloacimonadales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
JG36-TzT-191	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Leptospirales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Methylacidiphilales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Synergistales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Acidithiobacillales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Entothionellales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
MSBL9	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Spirochaetales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Subgroup_7	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
ADurb.Bin180	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Bacteroidetes_VC2.1_Bac22	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Desulfovibrionales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Methylomirabilales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Micropepsales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
SBR1031	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Tepidisphaerales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Caedibacterales	0,01%	0,01%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Azospirillales	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Candidatus_Falkowbacteria	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
CHAB-XI-27	0,14%	0,12%	0,00%	0,00%	0,07%	0,11%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,04%
Coxiellales	0,06%	0,10%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	0,07%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%
Salinisphaerales	0,03%	0,06%	0,00%	0,00%	0,02%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%

Table S18: Results of post-hoc analyses on donor and donor + recipient ASV richness and beta diversity for the significant results of the statistical analysis. Raw and adjusted (adjusted for multiple comparisons through the control of the false discovery rate (FDR)) p-values are given for the post hoc analyses on beta diversity. Significant results (p<0.05) are indicated with *. Highly significant results (p<0.001) are indicated with ***.

			df	ASV richness		Beta diversity		
				p-value	z-value	p-value	Adjusted p-value	R ²
Donor + Recipient								
	Sample Type	Donor vs Recipient	1	<0.001***	9.788	0.001***	0.0040*	0.08099
	Microbial inoculum	Lab vs Natural	1	<0.001***	-7.849	0.002*	0.0040*	0.06912
Sample Type x Microbial inoculum	Within Donor	Lab vs Natural	1	<0.001***	-6.395	0.1	0.1000	0.34698
	Within Recipient	Lab vs Natural	1	<0.001***	-4.701	0.003*	0.0045*	0.08844
	Within Lab	Donor vs Recipient	1	0.0009*	3.778	0.022*	0.0264*	0.10831
	Within Natural	Donor vs Recipient	1	<0.001***	-8.686	0.002*	0.0040*	0.1609
			Recipient Lab vs Donor Natural	1	<0.001***	-15.640		
		Recipient Natural vs Donor Lab	1	0.6432	1.174			
Donor								
	Microbial inoculum	Lab vs Natural	1	<0.001***	-6.395			

Table S19: Overview significantly different OTUs after edgeR analysis ($p < 0.001$ for all variables except for the three-way interaction in the recipients ($p < 0.05$)).

OTU	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	logFC	logCPM	p-value	FDR
Donors + Recipients (Sample type)									
OTU_204_Roseococcus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseococcus	-6.01898	9.776461	0.0000000000604	0.0000000116
OTU_211_Hyphomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Hyphomonadaceae	Hyphomonas	-5.91395	9.702272	0.0000000000178	0.000000017
OTU_45_NS11-12_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	NS11-12_marine_group		9.252665	12.98736	0.0000000000327	0.0000000209
OTU_87_OPB56	Bacteroidetes	Ignavibacteria	OPB56			7.837424	11.64374	0.0000000000723	0.0000000272
OTU_80_Herbaspirillum_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Herbaspirillum	7.93879	11.73758	0.0000000000857	0.0000000272
OTU_93_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		7.755421	11.56838	0.0000000000857	0.0000000272
OTU_91_Sporichthyaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae		7.772565	11.58419	0.0000000000993	0.0000000272
OTU_81_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	7.890144	11.69261	0.0000000000142	0.0000000324
OTU_98_Polaromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polaromonas	7.644557	11.4669	0.0000000000152	0.0000000324
OTU_143_hgcl_clade_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	hgcl_clade	6.649171	10.59202	0.0000000000366	0.0000000673
OTU_83_Candidatus_Aquirestis_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae	Candidatus_Aquirestis	7.885969	11.68866	0.0000000000386	0.0000000673
OTU_68_Saprospiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae		8.383124	12.15587	0.0000000000583	0.0000000932
OTU_132_Sporichthyaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae		6.752146	10.679	0.0000000000754	0.000000111
OTU_136_Sediminibacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Sediminibacterium	6.699917	10.63481	0.0000000000811	0.000000111
OTU_144_Candidatus_Planktophila_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	Candidatus_Planktophila	6.567318	10.52374	0.000000000012	0.000000153
OTU_106_Rhizorhapis_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Rhizorhapis	7.403723	11.24882	0.000000000013	0.000000156
OTU_130_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	6.790402	10.71145	0.0000000000144	0.000000163
OTU_115_Candidatus_Aquirestis_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae	Candidatus_Aquirestis	7.052307	10.9377	0.0000000000186	0.000000198
OTU_35_Limnobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Limnobacter	9.875782	13.60576	0.0000000000307	0.000000031
OTU_129_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	6.786519	10.70842	0.0000000000353	0.0000000338
OTU_362_Niabella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Niabella	-4.41912	8.837691	0.0000000000552	0.0000000504
OTU_135_Sandarakinorhabdus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sandarakinorhabdus	6.701615	10.64128	0.0000000000587	0.0000000512
OTU_128_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiae		6.796746	10.71718	0.0000000000675	0.0000000563

OTU_181_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	5.876942	9.975422	0.00000000901	0.000000719
OTU_126_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	6.81845	10.73512	0.0000000105	0.000000805
OTU_151_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		6.427228	10.40849	0.0000000012	0.000000854
OTU_145_Dinghuibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Dinghuibacter	6.55025	10.50981	0.0000000012	0.000000854
OTU_182_Candidatus_Planktophila_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	Candidatus_Planktophila	5.871873	9.97433	0.0000000136	0.000000915
OTU_208_Methylotenera_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Methylophilaceae	Methylotenera	5.507454	9.706152	0.0000000014	0.000000915
OTU_168_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	6.120762	10.1629	0.00000000143	0.000000915
OTU_172_Sphingorhabdus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingorhabdus	6.064536	10.11875	0.00000000184	0.000000114
OTU_162_Isosphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Isosphaerales	Isosphaeraceae		6.213563	10.2363	0.00000000269	0.000000161
OTU_180_GKS98_freshwater_group_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	GKS98_freshwater_group	5.893441	9.987683	0.00000000293	0.00000017
OTU_166_Dinghuibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Dinghuibacter	6.148122	10.18458	0.00000000473	0.000000266
OTU_218_Arenimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Arenimonas	5.444683	9.662504	0.00000000582	0.000000319
OTU_175_NS9_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	NS9_marine_group		6.006117	10.07406	0.00000000662	0.000000353
OTU_178_Methylotenera_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Methylophilaceae	Methylotenera	5.949256	10.0305	0.00000000761	0.000000394
OTU_216_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		5.472694	9.681655	0.000000008	0.000000404
OTU_184_env.OPS_17	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	env.OPS_17		5.861341	9.963935	0.00000000941	0.000000463
OTU_188_Trichococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Carnobacteriaceae	Trichococcus	5.80739	9.923118	0.0000000108	0.000000516
OTU_196_Pedobacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Pedobacter	5.727172	9.863734	0.0000000131	0.00000061
OTU_217_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	5.451399	9.667204	0.0000000134	0.00000061
OTU_243_NS11-12_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	NS11-12_marine_group		5.128865	9.450746	0.0000000205	0.000000901
OTU_242_Limnohabitans_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Limnohabitans	5.137304	9.456233	0.0000000207	0.000000901
OTU_209_Candidatus_Limnoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Candidatus_Limnoluna	5.514119	9.710241	0.0000000229	0.000000954
OTU_210_Limnobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Limnobacter	5.503463	9.702688	0.0000000233	0.000000954
OTU_239_Caulobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Caulobacter	5.147777	9.463103	0.0000000234	0.000000954
OTU_249_hgcl_clade_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	hgcl_clade	5.039401	9.393572	0.0000000268	0.00000107
OTU_219_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	5.424239	9.648416	0.000000028	0.00000108

OTU_222_NS11-12_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	NS11-12_marine_group		5.419321	9.645021	0.000000283	0.00000108
OTU_225_Chitinophagaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae		5.402527	9.632864	0.000000296	0.0000011
OTU_244_Rheinheimera_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Alteromonadales	Alteromonadaceae	Rheinheimera	5.104276	9.440193	0.000000297	0.0000011
OTU_200_Candidatus_Limnoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Candidatus_Limnoluna	5.597979	9.801559	0.000000357	0.00000127
OTU_253_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	5.024953	9.384187	0.000000361	0.00000127
OTU_231_Rhodoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Rhodoluna	5.320912	9.577325	0.000000363	0.00000127
OTU_262_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		4.909512	9.312864	0.000000392	0.00000134
OTU_255_GKS98_freshwater_group_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	GKS98_freshwater_group	5.004762	9.37155	0.000000463	0.00000156
OTU_269_Piscinibacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Piscinibacter	4.834137	9.267522	0.000000521	0.00000172
OTU_288_Sediminibacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Sediminibacterium	4.608926	9.137007	0.000000102	0.00000331
OTU_258_Candidatus_Planktophila_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	Candidatus_Planktophila	4.945445	9.335237	0.000000104	0.00000333
OTU_261_Sediminibacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Sediminibacterium	4.926234	9.322538	0.000000109	0.00000344
OTU_263_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.903804	9.309725	0.000000117	0.00000362
OTU_265_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	4.872662	9.28994	0.000000127	0.00000387
OTU_279_Terrimicrobium_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Terrimicrobiaceae	Terrimicrobium	4.688041	9.182118	0.000000134	0.00000401
OTU_267_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	4.846343	9.27499	0.000000139	0.00000409
OTU_272_LD29_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Chthoniobacteraceae	LD29	4.797911	9.246139	0.000000157	0.00000457
OTU_276_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.746264	9.215211	0.000000186	0.00000533
OTU_306_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.44776	9.048803	0.000000192	0.0000054
OTU_326_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.280836	8.962802	0.000000227	0.00000631
OTU_338_Polaromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polaromonas	4.179426	8.912364	0.000000262	0.00000706
OTU_343_Novosphingobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Novosphingobium	4.160764	8.903381	0.000000264	0.00000706
OTU_335_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.193455	8.919075	0.000000265	0.00000706
OTU_304_Cryomorpaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Cryomorpaceae		4.457838	9.05469	0.000000278	0.00000731
OTU_297_Armatimonas_sp.	Armatimonadetes	Armatimonadia	Armatimonadales	Armatimonadaceae	Armatimonas	4.532438	9.095011	0.000000313	0.0000081
OTU_336_Polymorphobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Polymorphobacter	4.179058	8.912505	0.000000332	0.00000849

OTU_361_Candidatus_Methylopusillus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Methylophilaceae	Candidatus_Methylopusillus	4.011642	8.833331	0.00000355	0.00000889
OTU_392_alpha_cluster_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	alpha_cluster	3.780584	8.7325	0.00000357	0.00000889
OTU_64_Rhodospirillum_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodospirillum	8.420851	12.28866	0.00000369	0.00000908
OTU_342_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.164385	8.904951	0.00000379	0.00000913
OTU_307_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiae	Prostheco bacter	4.433486	9.041755	0.00000381	0.00000913
OTU_321_Paracaedibacteraceae	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Paracaedibacterales	Paracaedibacteraceae		4.342142	8.993275	0.00000454	0.0000107
OTU_318_Sphingorhabdus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingorhabdus	4.347742	8.996422	0.00000457	0.0000107
OTU_364_Sediminibacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Sediminibacterium	3.973372	8.815902	0.00000481	0.0000111
OTU_324_CL500-29_marine_group_sp.	Actinobacteria	Acidimicrobia	Microtrichales	Ilumatobacteraceae	CL500-29_marine_group	4.29002	8.967538	0.00000517	0.0000118
OTU_368_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	3.918404	8.791733	0.00000576	0.000013
OTU_371_hgcl_clade_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	hgcl_clade	3.904265	8.785522	0.00000622	0.0000139
OTU_333_Rubrivivax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rubrivivax	4.206861	8.926147	0.00000635	0.0000139
OTU_75_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	7.904336	11.80083	0.00000636	0.0000139
OTU_339_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.17221	8.909252	0.00000666	0.0000144
OTU_344_Ferruginibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Ferruginibacter	4.148638	8.897878	0.00000689	0.0000147
OTU_348_Rhodoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Rhodoluna	4.126975	8.887081	0.00000717	0.000015
OTU_372_Methylobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Methylococcales	Methylomonaceae	Methylobacter	3.889635	8.77915	0.00000727	0.000015
OTU_391_Sediminibacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Sediminibacterium	3.780784	8.732596	0.00000728	0.000015
OTU_397_env.OPS_17	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	env.OPS_17		3.765147	8.726095	0.00000749	0.0000153
OTU_353_Rhodospirillum_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodospirillum	4.05029	8.851458	0.00000885	0.0000179
OTU_355_NS11-12_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	NS11-12_marine_group		4.043916	8.848507	0.00000897	0.0000179
OTU_5_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	12.25893	16.72923	0.00000108	0.0000213
OTU_4_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		10.46973	17.97255	0.00000113	0.0000221
OTU_365_Dinghuibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Dinghuibacter	3.937888	8.800441	0.00000121	0.0000234
OTU_378_Saprospiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae		3.875425	8.772316	0.00000142	0.0000273
OTU_424_Rickettsiella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Diplorickettsiales	Diplorickettsiaceae	Rickettsiella	3.588586	8.662052	0.00000148	0.0000282

OTU_381_Gammaproteobacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria				3.830872	8.753873	0.00000164	0.0000307
OTU_382_Lautropia_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Lautropia	3.830871	8.753873	0.00000166	0.0000307
OTU_616_Rubritepida_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Rubritepida	-2.81584	8.31728	0.00000167	0.0000307
OTU_383_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	3.825542	8.751172	0.00000168	0.0000307
OTU_385_CL500-3_sp.	Planctomycetes	Phycisphaerae	Phycisphaerales	Phycisphaeraeaceae	CL500-3	3.800943	8.741197	0.00000176	0.0000318
OTU_393_SM2D12	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rickettsiales	SM2D12		3.792217	8.7369	0.00000177	0.0000318
OTU_396_SM2D12	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rickettsiales	SM2D12		3.784502	8.733672	0.00000179	0.0000318
OTU_389_Candidatus_Aquiluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Candidatus_Aquiluna	3.785743	8.734816	0.00000181	0.0000318
OTU_427_Candidatus_Planktoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Candidatus_Planktoluna	3.590155	8.656122	0.00000183	0.000032
OTU_404_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	3.739161	8.715503	0.00000195	0.0000336
OTU_449_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	3.43559	8.598318	0.00000212	0.0000362
OTU_410_env.OPS_17	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	env.OPS_17		3.707243	8.702482	0.00000216	0.0000366
OTU_46_Simplicispira_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Simplicispira	9.082594	12.97402	0.00000225	0.0000378
OTU_416_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		3.665945	8.685561	0.00000246	0.000041
OTU_248_Pseudarcicella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Pseudarcicella	4.878687	9.399812	0.00000253	0.0000417
OTU_464_Dechloromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	3.346471	8.566744	0.00000257	0.0000421
OTU_451_Ferruginibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Ferruginibacter	3.403907	8.58704	0.00000293	0.0000475
OTU_425_Pedobacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Pedobacter	3.607639	8.66257	0.000003	0.0000484
OTU_469_Sphingorhabdus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingorhabdus	3.308022	8.553431	0.00000305	0.0000487
OTU_476_Pajaroellobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Myxococcales	Polyangiaceae	Pajaroellobacter	3.280946	8.54413	0.0000034	0.0000536
OTU_434_211ds20	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	211ds20			3.563409	8.645548	0.00000341	0.0000536
OTU_484_Methylotenera_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Methylophilaceae	Methylotenera	3.228159	8.526796	0.00000401	0.0000624
OTU_442_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	3.499116	8.621373	0.0000042	0.000065
OTU_486_Prolixibacteraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Prolixibacteraceae		3.203911	8.518912	0.00000428	0.0000657
OTU_446_Arcobacter_sp.	Epsilonbacteraeota	Campylobacteria	Campylobacterales	Arcobacteraceae	Arcobacter	3.47066	8.610887	0.00000459	0.0000697
OTU_445_Sphingorhabdus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingorhabdus	3.471094	8.611369	0.00000462	0.0000697
OTU_198_Sphingorhabdus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingorhabdus	5.455864	9.841437	0.0000049	0.0000734

OTU_448_Pedobacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Pedobacter	3.441631	8.600324	0.0000051	0.0000758
OTU_169_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	5.845708	10.15589	0.0000537	0.0000792
OTU_461_Roseococcus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseococcus	3.362587	8.572528	0.00000619	0.0000905
OTU_491_Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae				3.166512	8.506944	0.00000647	0.000094
OTU_148_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	6.238131	10.44592	0.00000671	0.0000962
OTU_508_Arcobacter_sp.	Epsilonbacteraeota	Campylobacteriaria	Campylobacterales	Arcobacteraceae	Arcobacter	3.07613	8.478575	0.00000673	0.0000962
OTU_515_Pseudarcicella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Pseudarcicella	3.063411	8.474702	0.00000681	0.0000967
OTU_475_Paracaedibacteraceae	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Paracaedibacterales	Paracaedibacteraceae		3.280376	8.543952	0.00000847	0.000119
OTU_113_Methyloversatilis_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Methyloversatilis	6.804746	11.01497	0.00000863	0.000121
OTU_477_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	3.274762	8.542232	0.00000887	0.000123
OTU_478_Dinghuibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Dinghuibacter	3.256319	8.536285	0.00000902	0.000124
OTU_480_FukuN18_freshwater_group_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Terrimicrobiaceae	FukuN18_freshwater_group	3.24525	8.53261	0.0000093	0.000127
OTU_481_alphal_cluster_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	alphal_cluster	3.245249	8.53261	0.00000933	0.000127
OTU_525_CHAB-XI-27	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	CHAB-XI-27			3.003593	8.456733	0.0000097	0.000131
OTU_485_Saprosiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprosiraceae		3.21152	8.521528	0.0000105	0.000141
OTU_529_Thiobacillus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Hydrogenophilaceae	Thiobacillus	2.96814	8.446485	0.0000106	0.000141
OTU_677_Deinococcus-Thermus	Deinococcus-Thermus	Deinococci	Deinococcales	Deinococcaceae	Deinococcus	-2.49967	8.255473	0.0000115	0.000151
OTU_490_Rudanella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Rudanella	3.173902	8.509152	0.0000119	0.000157
OTU_535_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	2.939184	8.438171	0.0000125	0.000164
OTU_250_Bdellovibrio_sp.	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Bdellovibrionales	Bdellovibrionaceae	Bdellovibrio	4.719588	9.398095	0.0000134	0.000174
OTU_92_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	7.335279	11.5775	0.0000141	0.000181
OTU_494_Rhizobiales_Incertae_Sedis	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiales_Incertae_Sedis		3.129608	8.495334	0.0000142	0.000181
OTU_495_Methylomonaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Methylococcales	Methylomonaceae		3.129608	8.495334	0.0000143	0.000181
OTU_496_Arcobacter_sp.	Epsilonbacteraeota	Campylobacteriaria	Campylobacterales	Arcobacteraceae	Arcobacter	3.13686	8.497436	0.0000146	0.000184
OTU_502_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	3.093028	8.48396	0.0000163	0.000204
OTU_503_Methylocystis_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	Methylocystis	3.093028	8.48396	0.0000164	0.000204
OTU_506_AKYH767	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	AKYH767		3.080626	8.480148	0.0000171	0.000211

OTU_507_Crenothrix_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Methylococcales	Methylomonaceae	Crenothrix	3.080625	8.480148	0.0000172	0.000211
OTU_548_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		2.85625	8.414923	0.0000175	0.000213
OTU_509_Cytophagales	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales			3.06812	8.476327	0.0000176	0.000214
OTU_510_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	3.07527	8.478351	0.000018	0.000216
OTU_511_hgcl_clade_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	hgcl_clade	3.07527	8.478351	0.000018	0.000216
OTU_185_Rhodoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Rhodoluna	5.475454	9.968007	0.0000181	0.000216
OTU_518_Candidatus_Aquirestis_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprosiraceae	Candidatus_Aquirestis	3.025299	8.463252	0.0000202	0.000239
OTU_642_Qipengyuania_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Qipengyuania	-2.49965	8.286674	0.000021	0.000247
OTU_520_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiae	Prostheco bacter	3.003892	8.457065	0.0000223	0.000258
OTU_194_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	5.38232	9.873201	0.0000224	0.000258
OTU_521_Pseudohongiella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Oceanospirillales	Pseudohongiellaceae	Pseudohongiella	3.003891	8.457065	0.0000224	0.000258
OTU_97_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Runella	7.292266	11.51301	0.0000228	0.000262
OTU_526_Chitinophagaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae		2.977379	8.449288	0.0000245	0.000279
OTU_534_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	2.957315	8.443349	0.0000253	0.000287
OTU_375_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacteriales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	3.667293	8.776739	0.0000254	0.000287
OTU_528_LD29_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Chthoniobacteraceae	LD29	2.963937	8.445384	0.0000258	0.000289
OTU_533_Gemmataceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Gemmatales	Gemmataceae		2.950369	8.441468	0.000027	0.000301
OTU_556_PeM15	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	PeM15			2.778188	8.393958	0.0000288	0.000319
OTU_537_hgcl_clade_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	hgcl_clade	2.922844	8.433606	0.0000301	0.000331
OTU_540_env.OPS_17	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	env.OPS_17		2.908881	8.429659	0.0000318	0.000348
OTU_541_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	2.894781	8.4257	0.0000336	0.000365
OTU_542_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		2.894781	8.4257	0.0000337	0.000365
OTU_57_Candidatus_Limnoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Candidatus_Limnoluna	7.703966	12.64816	0.0000365	0.000393
OTU_578_Steroidobacteraceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae		2.667999	8.365685	0.0000369	0.000396
OTU_531_Ralstonia_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Ralstonia	-2.75429	8.445385	0.0000379	0.000404
OTU_123_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	6.459625	10.76111	0.0000387	0.00041
OTU_547_Microtrichales	Actinobacteria	Acidimicrobia	Microtrichales			2.851638	8.41376	0.0000399	0.00042

OTU_551_Massilia_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Massilia	2.815038	8.403741	0.0000446	0.000467
OTU_584_Lentimicrobiaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Lentimicrobiaceae		2.633466	8.357159	0.0000451	0.00047
OTU_552_Dinghuibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Dinghuibacter	2.807162	8.401719	0.000048	0.000497
OTU_576_Cereibacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Cereibacter	2.688195	8.370765	0.0000491	0.000506
OTU_592_Sphingomonadaceae	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae		2.585033	8.345482	0.0000539	0.000552
OTU_212_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		4.921403	9.686927	0.0000541	0.000552
OTU_322_Methyloversatilis_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Methyloversatilis	3.938705	8.985243	0.000058	0.000588
OTU_561_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	2.745648	8.385507	0.0000615	0.00062
OTU_562_Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae				2.745647	8.385507	0.0000617	0.00062
OTU_599_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	2.549317	8.337048	0.0000632	0.000631
OTU_159_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	5.727641	10.27469	0.0000649	0.000645
OTU_564_Chthoniobacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Chthoniobacteraceae	Chthoniobacter	2.72985	8.381425	0.0000658	0.00065
OTU_571_Chryseoglobus_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Chryseoglobus	2.705339	8.375105	0.0000681	0.000669
OTU_567_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	2.713878	8.377332	0.0000701	0.000686
OTU_577_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	2.687813	8.370685	0.0000724	0.000705
OTU_79_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	7.062333	11.74846	0.0000752	0.000728
OTU_579_Candidatus_Planktoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Candidatus_Planktoluna	2.671257	8.366538	0.0000771	0.000743
OTU_587_Ferruginibacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Ferruginibacter	2.614533	8.352588	0.0000778	0.000746
OTU_573_Opitutaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Opitutaes	Opitutaceae		2.6814	8.36911	0.0000787	0.000747
OTU_574_CL500-29_marine_group_sp.	Actinobacteria	Acidimicrobiia	Microtrichales	Ilumatobacteraceae	CL500-29_marine_group	2.681399	8.36911	0.0000788	0.000747
OTU_575_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Prostheco bacter	2.681398	8.36911	0.0000791	0.000747
OTU_43_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	8.19418	13.11802	0.0000828	0.000778
OTU_582_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	2.638694	8.358483	0.0000882	0.000825
OTU_102_Rhodoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Rhodoluna	6.626089	11.36369	0.0000893	0.000831
OTU_583_Saprospiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae		2.631261	8.356688	0.0000962	0.000891
OTU_621_Candidatus_Planktophila_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	Candidatus_Planktophila	2.413933	8.306444	0.000102	0.000936
OTU_298_Acinetobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter	4.025287	9.102349	0.000102	0.000937

OTU_620_NS11-12_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	NS11-12_marine_group		2.416245	8.30699	0.000107	0.000978
OTU_593_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	2.585498	8.345625	0.000108	0.000982
OTU_2_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	8.431113	18.89526	0.000109	0.000982
OTU_591_Terrimicrobium_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Terrimicrobiaceae	Terrimicrobium	2.59684	8.348346	0.000111	0.000995
Donor (Microbial inocula)									
OTU_5_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	-1.331.916	1.916.936	0.468	0.000897801
Recipients (Microbial inocula)									
OTU_23_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-9.01446	14.27256	2.42E-22	4.65E-19
OTU_21_Diplorickettsiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Diplorickettsiales	Diplorickettsiaceae		-9.16824	14.42508	3.37E-21	3.23E-18
OTU_96_Acidovorax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Acidovorax	-6.18931	11.52108	8.06E-20	0.0000000000000000395
OTU_36_FukuN18_freshwater_group_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Terrimicrobiaceae	FukuN18_freshwater_group	-8.2105	13.47783	9.59E-20	0.0000000000000000395
OTU_31_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		8.497236	13.84194	1.03E-19	0.0000000000000000395
OTU_110_Candidatus_Aquiluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Candidatus_Aquiluna	-5.84278	11.19708	1.32E-19	0.0000000000000000402
OTU_38_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		7.496007	13.40543	1.47E-19	0.0000000000000000402
OTU_11_Betaproteobacteriales	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	T34		10.01971	15.3536	5.42E-19	0.000000000000000013
OTU_60_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	6.895876	12.44664	7.4E-19	0.0000000000000000158
OTU_94_Zoogloea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Zoogloea	-6.15161	11.48559	1.48E-18	0.0000000000000000284
OTU_76_Shinella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Shinella	-6.48881	11.80482	2.12E-18	0.0000000000000000369
OTU_12_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	8.041766	15.18068	4.29E-18	0.0000000000000000685
OTU_62_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	6.859713	12.41162	6.18E-18	0.0000000000000000911
OTU_41_Stenotrophomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Stenotrophomonas	-8.02008	13.29045	0.0000000000000000175	0.00000000000000239
OTU_70_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	-6.83545	12.13671	0.0000000000000000345	0.00000000000000441
OTU_49_GKS98_freshwater_group_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	GKS98_freshwater_group	6.963709	12.7796	0.0000000000000000487	0.00000000000000584
OTU_16_Prevotella_7_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Prevotellaceae	Prevotella_7	9.105734	14.62101	0.0000000000000000945	0.00000000000000107
OTU_59_Pseudoxanthomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Pseudoxanthomonas	-7.22347	12.5118	0.0000000000000000178	0.00000000000000189
OTU_101_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	5.981233	11.40187	0.000000000000000021	0.00000000000000212
OTU_61_Rhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Rhodobacter	6.475733	11.87012	0.0000000000000000554	0.00000000000000531

OTU_74_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	5.760004	11.84427	0.00000000000000078	0.00000000000000712
OTU_54_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	7.36481	12.72907	0.000000000000000147	0.00000000000000128
OTU_72_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	6.694433	12.07967	0.000000000000000177	0.00000000000000147
OTU_73_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	-6.61734	12.05903	0.00000000000000024	0.00000000000000191
OTU_82_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-6.41072	11.73055	0.000000000000000259	0.00000000000000199
OTU_50_hgcl_clade_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	hgcl_clade	6.701323	12.94352	0.000000000000000348	0.00000000000000256
OTU_114_Diplorickettsiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Diplorickettsiales	Diplorickettsiaceae		-5.65119	11.02028	0.000000000000000845	0.0000000000000006
OTU_107_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	-5.90705	11.25678	0.000000000000000163	0.00000000000000112
OTU_137_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaeae	Prostheco bacter	-5.22769	10.63659	0.000000000000000169	0.00000000000000112
OTU_84_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		6.277847	11.68172	0.000000000000000249	0.00000000000000159
OTU_26_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	-6.6056	14.002	0.000000000000000261	0.00000000000000161
OTU_103_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	5.921363	11.34579	0.000000000000000304	0.00000000000000182
OTU_77_Actinomyces_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinomycetales	Actinomycetaceae	Actinomyces	6.431433	11.82783	0.000000000000000361	0.00000000000000021
OTU_156_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-4.88886	10.33807	0.000000000000000506	0.00000000000000285
OTU_86_Deefgea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Chitinibacteraceae	Deefgea	6.271405	11.67561	0.000000000000000598	0.00000000000000327
OTU_150_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	4.897957	10.41555	0.000000000000000701	0.00000000000000373
OTU_104_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	-5.57355	11.30169	0.000000000000000787	0.00000000000000394
OTU_146_Staphylococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Staphylococcus	-5.07493	10.50098	0.00000000000000008	0.00000000000000394
OTU_138_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Runella	-5.06595	10.49306	0.000000000000000802	0.00000000000000394
OTU_157_Chitinophagales	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales			-4.83438	10.29088	0.000000000000000122	0.00000000000000583
OTU_163_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	4.679046	10.22545	0.000000000000000138	0.00000000000000648
OTU_100_Enhydrobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Enhydrobacter	5.997493	11.41712	0.000000000000000146	0.00000000000000666
OTU_131_Stenotrophomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Stenotrophomonas	-5.3165	10.71616	0.000000000000000176	0.00000000000000784
OTU_155_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	4.821912	10.34908	0.000000000000000195	0.00000000000000851
OTU_105_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaeae	Prostheco bacter	5.559521	11.26843	0.000000000000000208	0.00000000000000885
OTU_119_Deefgea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Chitinibacteraceae	Deefgea	5.395283	10.86014	0.000000000000000219	0.00000000000000905

OTU_153_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		4.846883	10.37086	0.00000000000222	0.00000000000905
OTU_147_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaeae	Pseudomonas	-5.03752	10.46802	0.000000000000289	0.00000000000115
OTU_48_Limnohabitans_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Limnohabitans	5.367078	10.83451	0.000000000000733	0.00000000000285
OTU_183_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	-4.42605	9.945339	0.000000000000744	0.00000000000285
OTU_127_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	5.058359	10.55714	0.000000000000773	0.0000000000029
OTU_141_Pedobacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Pedobacter	-4.45506	10.32474	0.000000000000862	0.00000000000318
OTU_133_SH-PL14_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae	SH-PL14	5.183222	10.6686	0.000000000000934	0.00000000000338
OTU_158_Fusobacterium_sp.	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	Fusobacterium	-4.82243	10.28056	0.000000000000154	0.00000000000547
OTU_124_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	5.297228	10.77124	0.000000000000179	0.00000000000624
OTU_149_Roseococcus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacterales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseococcus	4.845645	10.36978	0.000000000000191	0.00000000000652
OTU_40_Sediminibacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Sediminibacterium	6.065336	13.2863	0.000000000000198	0.00000000000666
OTU_53_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		5.926896	12.81756	0.000000000000245	0.00000000000809
OTU_109_Betaproteobacteriales	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales			5.209226	11.23557	0.00000000000031	0.0000000000101
OTU_191_Neisseria_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Neisseriaceae	Neisseria	-4.32804	9.864754	0.000000000000389	0.0000000000124
OTU_173_Alkanindiges_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Alkanindiges	-4.60873	10.09807	0.00000000000042	0.0000000000132
OTU_97_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Runella	-4.23697	9.790754	0.000000000000532	0.0000000000165
OTU_189_Ampullimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Ampullimonas	-4.19228	9.754766	0.000000000000709	0.0000000000214
OTU_179_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-4.49792	10.00505	0.000000000000714	0.0000000000214
OTU_152_Lactobacillus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Lactobacillaceae	Lactobacillus	4.890771	10.40925	0.000000000000884	0.0000000000258
OTU_161_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		4.690127	10.23498	0.000000000000889	0.0000000000258
OTU_112_SH-PL14_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae	SH-PL14	4.834959	11.13162	0.00000000000105	0.0000000000301
OTU_193_Bacillus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae	Bacillus	-4.30724	9.847772	0.00000000000116	0.0000000000327
OTU_186_Fusobacterium_sp.	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	Fusobacterium	-4.3815	9.90859	0.00000000000128	0.0000000000355
OTU_190_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	4.266555	9.878502	0.0000000000015	0.000000000041
OTU_192_Methyloversatilis_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Methyloversatilis	-4.31294	9.852424	0.00000000000177	0.0000000000478
OTU_199_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	4.153005	9.785899	0.00000000000244	0.0000000000651

OTU_206_Polymorphobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Polymorphobacter	4.007771	9.669476	0.000000000032	0.00000000084
OTU_202_Massilia_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Massilia	-4.17359	9.739781	0.0000000000357	0.000000000926
OTU_203_Diplorickettsiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Diplorickettsiales	Diplorickettsiaceae		-4.16099	9.729704	0.0000000000381	0.000000000973
OTU_56_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		-5.33514	12.41634	0.0000000000488	0.00000000123
OTU_201_NS11-12_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	NS11-12_marine_group		4.097902	9.741454	0.000000000066	0.00000000164
OTU_197_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	4.192506	9.81796	0.0000000000907	0.00000000223
OTU_230_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.831327	9.531269	0.000000000102	0.00000000248
OTU_229_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.833827	9.533202	0.000000000113	0.0000000027
OTU_241_Sphingomonadaceae	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae		3.655917	9.397628	0.000000000152	0.0000000036
OTU_195_Prevotella_7_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Prevotellaceae	Prevotella_7	4.208009	9.830588	0.000000000167	0.00000000391
OTU_233_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	-3.83867	9.478085	0.00000000021	0.00000000485
OTU_232_Chitinophagaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae		-3.73484	9.399748	0.00000000022	0.00000000501
OTU_236_Porphyrromonas_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	Porphyromonas	-3.80937	9.455843	0.000000000247	0.00000000556
OTU_235_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	3.675565	9.412404	0.000000000329	0.00000000733
OTU_221_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		3.918716	9.599262	0.000000000369	0.00000000814
OTU_256_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Runella	-3.57629	9.282858	0.000000000416	0.00000000906
OTU_245_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		3.609977	9.363277	0.00000000042	0.00000000906
OTU_214_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	3.969626	9.639289	0.000000000511	0.0000000109
OTU_246_Stenotrophomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Stenotrophomonas	-3.66817	9.350181	0.000000000535	0.0000000113
OTU_223_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		3.904514	9.58815	0.000000000699	0.0000000146
OTU_251_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	-3.61683	9.312418	0.000000000716	0.0000000148
OTU_252_Stenotrophomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Stenotrophomonas	-3.61375	9.310165	0.000000000726	0.0000000148
OTU_227_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		3.875683	9.565666	0.0000000008	0.0000000162
OTU_257_Roseococcus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacterales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseococcus	3.330806	9.160665	0.000000000954	0.000000019
OTU_228_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		3.838815	9.537059	0.000000000961	0.000000019
OTU_259_Gemmobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Gemmobacter	3.45294	9.247981	0.000000000971	0.000000019

OTU_247_Galbitalea_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Galbitalea	3.559507	9.325859	0.00000000112	0.0000000218
OTU_237_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacterales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	3.697697	9.429107	0.00000000195	0.0000000373
OTU_238_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	3.68113	9.416598	0.00000000211	0.0000000401
OTU_268_Bosea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	Bosea	3.369234	9.18791	0.00000000218	0.000000041
OTU_58_Ideonella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Ideonella	-4.5294	11.59001	0.00000000347	0.0000000646
OTU_29_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	-5.25031	13.92377	0.00000000353	0.000000065
OTU_64_Rhodoferax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	3.261921	9.112359	0.00000000372	0.000000068
OTU_125_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	-3.99389	10.75642	0.00000000422	0.0000000764
OTU_280_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacterales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	-3.29047	9.080995	0.00000000477	0.0000000842
OTU_281_Sphingobacteriaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae		-3.29047	9.080995	0.00000000478	0.0000000842
OTU_260_Planctomycetales	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales			3.436583	9.236165	0.00000000479	0.0000000842
OTU_264_Moraxellaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae		-3.23114	9.217056	0.00000000518	0.0000000894
OTU_167_env.OPS_17	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	env.OPS_17		3.685183	9.863219	0.00000000518	0.0000000894
OTU_287_Phreatobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiales_Incertae_Sedis	Phreatobacter	3.158002	9.040805	0.00000000592	0.000000101
OTU_293_Phreatobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiales_Incertae_Sedis	Phreatobacter	3.113421	9.010605	0.00000000779	0.000000131
OTU_291_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-3.20716	9.024411	0.00000000782	0.000000131
OTU_305_Gemella_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Family_XI	Gemella	-3.08357	8.942434	0.00000000916	0.000000153
OTU_308_Rothia_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Rothia	-3.06115	8.927817	0.00000000957	0.000000158
OTU_294_Xanthobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Xanthobacteraceae	Xanthobacter	-3.16573	8.996666	0.000000001	0.000000163
OTU_282_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacterales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	-2.81541	8.772872	0.0000000101	0.000000163
OTU_296_Methylobacterium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	Methylobacterium	-3.16152	8.993862	0.0000000102	0.000000165
OTU_270_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		3.358855	9.18053	0.0000000112	0.000000179
OTU_123_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	3.334342	9.163163	0.0000000128	0.000000203
OTU_292_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae		3.117531	9.013377	0.0000000134	0.00000021
OTU_302_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacterales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	-3.10126	8.954022	0.0000000148	0.000000231
OTU_274_Fluviicola_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Crocinitomicaceae	Fluviicola	3.305808	9.143055	0.0000000149	0.000000231
OTU_207_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.430947	9.641082	0.0000000163	0.00000025

OTU_284_Devosia_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Devosiaceae	Devosia	3.173878	9.051632	0.000000189	0.000000288
OTU_278_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	3.254475	9.107178	0.000000197	0.000000297
OTU_301_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	3.037361	8.959781	0.0000000221	0.000000331
OTU_299_WPS-2	WPS-2					3.075892	8.985417	0.0000000285	0.000000423
OTU_311_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.9753	8.918975	0.0000000291	0.000000429
OTU_285_NS9_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	NS9_marine_group		3.169925	9.048933	0.0000000312	0.000000456
OTU_159_Rhodoferrax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferrax	3.161987	9.04352	0.0000000325	0.000000472
OTU_85_Aeromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Aeromonadales	Aeromonadaceae	Aeromonas	-4.17418	11.49999	0.0000000362	0.000000521
OTU_300_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	-2.8314	8.782653	0.0000000421	0.000000602
OTU_325_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	-2.92873	8.843106	0.000000043	0.000000611
OTU_164_Acinetobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter	-3.64603	10.21946	0.000000045	0.000000634
OTU_327_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		-2.91379	8.833727	0.0000000472	0.000000661
OTU_310_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	2.979822	8.921928	0.0000000493	0.000000684
OTU_328_Silanimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Silanimonas	-2.8987	8.824288	0.000000052	0.000000717
OTU_312_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae		2.970763	8.916015	0.0000000583	0.000000798
OTU_66_Microbacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Microbacterium	-4.12517	12.31073	0.0000000716	0.000000973
OTU_117_Stenotrophomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Stenotrophomonas	-3.86245	10.92928	0.000000074	0.000000998
OTU_226_Galbitalea_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Galbitalea	3.305808	9.567553	0.0000000792	0.00000106
OTU_14_Shinella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Shinella	-5.09462	14.83142	0.0000000832	0.00000111
OTU_309_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	2.979822	8.921928	0.000000089	0.00000118
OTU_377_Sphingobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingobium	-2.55158	8.617594	0.00000011	0.00000144
OTU_9_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Prostheco bacter	-4.89942	15.56026	0.000000112	0.00000146
OTU_347_Cellvibrio_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Cellvibrionales	Cellvibrionaceae	Cellvibrio	-2.74402	8.729704	0.000000137	0.00000178
OTU_351_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Prostheco bacter	-2.58339	8.635696	0.000000144	0.00000185
OTU_165_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		3.540058	10.11752	0.000000153	0.00000195
OTU_212_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		2.533594	8.646449	0.000000155	0.00000196
OTU_334_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	2.781684	8.795592	0.000000157	0.00000198

OTU_313_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	2.797141	8.805221	0.000000159	0.00000199
OTU_314_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacterales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	2.696324	8.743125	0.000000169	0.0000021
OTU_323_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.862274	8.846218	0.000000175	0.00000216
OTU_380_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae		-2.52561	8.602947	0.000000196	0.0000024
OTU_359_Reyranella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Reyranellales	Reyranellaceae	Reyranella	-2.67483	8.688677	0.000000213	0.0000026
OTU_345_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	2.728928	8.763024	0.000000225	0.00000273
OTU_215_Tabrizicola_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Tabrizicola	2.718142	8.756422	0.000000254	0.00000306
OTU_331_Roseimaritima_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Roseimaritima	2.797141	8.805221	0.000000255	0.00000306
OTU_332_Rhodobacteraceae	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae		2.792007	8.802019	0.000000262	0.00000311
OTU_340_Pasteurellaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae		-2.69616	8.772872	0.000000263	0.00000311
OTU_367_Kocuria_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Kocuria	-2.60215	8.646449	0.000000344	0.000004
OTU_341_Cyclobacteriaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae		2.744958	8.772872	0.000000344	0.000004
OTU_88_Acinetobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter	-3.71464	11.46903	0.000000344	0.000004
OTU_369_Frigoribacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Frigoribacterium	-2.58967	8.639289	0.000000371	0.00000428
OTU_113_Methyloversatilis_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Methyloversatilis	-2.83431	9.23379	0.000000377	0.00000433
OTU_39_Gemmobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Gemmobacter	-4.04811	13.17883	0.000000381	0.00000435
OTU_289_Babeliales	Dependentiae	Babeliae	Babeliales			-2.40261	8.535132	0.000000461	0.00000523
OTU_398_Reyranella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Reyranellales	Reyranellaceae	Reyranella	2.384664	8.561885	0.000000549	0.00000619
OTU_273_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	2.657329	8.719556	0.00000057	0.00000639
OTU_354_Prevotella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Prevotellaceae	Prevotella	2.645992	8.712751	0.00000061	0.00000679
OTU_330_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	2.634565	8.705914	0.000000652	0.00000723
OTU_194_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacterales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	-2.36649	8.515714	0.000000669	0.00000737
OTU_356_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		2.617252	8.695597	0.000000722	0.00000788
OTU_357_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.617252	8.695597	0.000000723	0.00000788
OTU_390_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Prostheco bacter	-2.47901	8.576952	0.00000075	0.00000812
OTU_394_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		-2.47223	8.5732	0.000000783	0.00000844
OTU_366_Dechloromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	2.539733	8.650015	0.000000841	0.00000901

OTU_388_Actinobacillus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Actinobacillus	-2.45857	8.565666	0.00000858	0.00000913
OTU_400_Corynebacterium_1_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	Corynebacterium_1	-2.4517	8.561885	0.00000896	0.00000949
OTU_409_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomyces	Planctomyces	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.343145	8.538984	0.00000975	0.0000103
OTU_405_Truepera_sp.	Deinococcus-Thermus	Deinococci	Deinococcales	Trueperaceae	Truepera	-2.43086	8.55048	0.00000102	0.0000107
OTU_316_Sphingomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingomonas	-2.24915	8.642873	0.00000103	0.0000107
OTU_373_Brevifollis_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Brevifollis	2.4962	8.624862	0.00000107	0.0000111
OTU_408_Zoogloea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Zoogloea	-2.4168	8.542826	0.00000112	0.0000116
OTU_148_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacteriales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	2.451313	8.599262	0.00000118	0.0000121
OTU_370_Duganella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Duganella	2.515018	8.635696	0.00000133	0.0000136
OTU_414_Saprosiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprosiraceae		-2.38827	8.527396	0.00000134	0.0000136
OTU_374_Enterobacteriaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae		2.4962	8.624862	0.00000149	0.000015
OTU_266_Solitalea_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Solitalea	2.438227	8.591864	0.00000153	0.0000154
OTU_376_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		2.489873	8.621233	0.00000154	0.0000154
OTU_417_Gemmobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacteriales	Rhodobacteraceae	Gemmobacter	-2.35916	8.511799	0.00000159	0.0000158
OTU_384_Phreatobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiales_Incertae_Sedis	Phreatobacter	2.425022	8.584427	0.00000163	0.0000161
OTU_350_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	2.447112	8.739781	0.00000163	0.0000161
OTU_254_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	2.477134	8.613946	0.00000166	0.0000162
OTU_379_Gammaproteobacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria				2.470722	8.610289	0.00000172	0.0000167
OTU_406_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	2.364054	8.55048	0.00000202	0.0000196
OTU_169_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	2.293145	8.511799	0.00000214	0.0000206
OTU_349_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	2.195425	8.459913	0.00000214	0.0000206
OTU_429_Bergeyella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Weeksellaceae	Bergeyella	-2.29912	8.48009	0.00000225	0.0000215
OTU_386_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	2.418373	8.580694	0.00000235	0.0000222
OTU_387_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	2.418373	8.580694	0.00000236	0.0000222
OTU_346_Rothia_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Rothia	-2.46013	8.763024	0.00000247	0.0000232
OTU_320_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	-2.28371	8.472053	0.00000249	0.0000232

OTU_412_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	2.329035	8.531269	0.0000025	0.0000232
OTU_271_Saprospiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae		2.300395	8.515714	0.00000296	0.0000275
OTU_407_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae		2.364054	8.55048	0.00000326	0.00003
OTU_437_Hymenobacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Hymenobacteraceae	Hymenobacter	-2.22844	8.443565	0.00000341	0.0000313
OTU_452_Corynebacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	Corynebacterium	-2.14562	8.401865	0.00000347	0.0000317
OTU_444_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-2.21225	8.435321	0.00000373	0.0000339
OTU_122_Granulicatella_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Carnobacteriaceae	Granulicatella	-3.2395	10.78021	0.00000381	0.0000345
OTU_413_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	2.329035	8.531269	0.00000401	0.0000361
OTU_438_FukuN57_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	FukuN57	2.163976	8.443565	0.00000431	0.0000386
OTU_32_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.015648	13.50024	0.00000493	0.0000439
OTU_435_Rhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Rhodobacter	2.203182	8.463971	0.00000504	0.0000447
OTU_454_Staphylococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Staphylococcus	-2.14562	8.401865	0.00000563	0.0000498
OTU_420_Haliscomenobacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae	Haliscomenobacter	2.263776	8.496032	0.0000057	0.0000501
OTU_421_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		2.263776	8.496032	0.00000574	0.0000502
OTU_422_Rathayibacter_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Rathayibacter	2.25634	8.492063	0.00000593	0.0000516
OTU_462_Saprospiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae		2.039528	8.380555	0.00000616	0.0000533
OTU_423_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	2.248865	8.488083	0.00000618	0.0000533
OTU_436_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	2.171903	8.447669	0.00000633	0.0000544
OTU_439_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae		2.163976	8.443565	0.00000641	0.0000547
OTU_426_Gemmobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Gemmobacter	2.241351	8.484092	0.00000642	0.0000547
OTU_430_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	2.203182	8.463971	0.00000676	0.0000571
OTU_443_Armatimonadales	Armatimonadales	Armatimonada	Armatimonadales			2.14799	8.435321	0.00000676	0.0000571
OTU_463_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-2.10236	8.380555	0.0000073	0.0000614
OTU_352_Shinella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Shinella	2.300739	8.719556	0.00000907	0.0000759
OTU_118_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	-3.00924	10.88608	0.00000953	0.0000794
OTU_441_Rhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Rhodobacter	2.156005	8.439448	0.0000102	0.0000849
OTU_474_Kocuria_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Kocuria	-2.03032	8.345789	0.0000113	0.0000928

OTU_315_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	2.250762	8.886083	0.0000113	0.0000928
OTU_303_Rheinheimera_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Alteromonadales	Alteromonadaceae	Rheinheimera	-1.9642	8.314667	0.0000115	0.0000938
OTU_286_Methylobacterium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	Methylobacterium	2.379934	8.927817	0.0000121	0.000099
OTU_466_NS11-12_marine_group	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	NS11-12_marine_group		2.022094	8.371942	0.0000141	0.000115
OTU_432_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	2.058296	8.435321	0.0000142	0.000115
OTU_450_Haemophilus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Haemophilus	2.098942	8.410302	0.0000142	0.000115
OTU_468_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		1.968489	8.345789	0.0000144	0.000116
OTU_415_Acidovorax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Acidovorax	2.004446	8.363277	0.0000152	0.000122
OTU_453_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	2.082215	8.401865	0.0000154	0.000123
OTU_455_Candidatus_Paracaedibacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Paracaedibacterales	Paracaedibacteraceae	Candidatus_Paracaedibacter	2.082215	8.401865	0.0000156	0.000124
OTU_487_Bdellovibrio_sp.	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Bdellovibrionales	Bdellovibrionaceae	Bdellovibrio	-1.97383	8.319154	0.0000162	0.000128
OTU_471_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	1.977563	8.350181	0.000018	0.000141
OTU_472_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	1.977563	8.350181	0.0000191	0.00015
OTU_465_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	2.030837	8.376255	0.0000206	0.00016
OTU_419_Caulobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Caulobacter	-1.9349	8.30112	0.0000208	0.000161
OTU_401_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	2.022094	8.371942	0.0000216	0.000166
OTU_277_Mycobacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Mycobacteriaceae	Mycobacterium	1.977563	8.350181	0.0000216	0.000166
OTU_498_0319-6G20	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Oligoflexales	0319-6G20		-1.905	8.287445	0.0000246	0.000189
OTU_35_Limnobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Limnobacter	-1.83272	8.255024	0.0000257	0.000196
OTU_473_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	1.977563	8.350181	0.0000285	0.000217
OTU_479_Chitinophagales	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales			1.959358	8.341384	0.0000307	0.000232
OTU_512_Staphylococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Staphylococcus	-1.86415	8.269008	0.0000319	0.000241
OTU_513_Achromobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Achromobacter	-1.86415	8.269008	0.0000321	0.000241
OTU_102_Rhodoluna_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Rhodoluna	2.751212	10.41555	0.0000329	0.000247
OTU_492_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	1.874469	8.30112	0.0000334	0.000249
OTU_459_Rickettsiales	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rickettsiales	AB1		-1.85375	8.264362	0.0000341	0.000252
OTU_440_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae		-1.85612	8.439448	0.0000341	0.000252

OTU_103_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	6.99120688154199	11.3457893793716	1.82378060868894E-14	3.4961874268567E-11
OTU_73_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	7.48646245895293	12.0590291841766	2.54050932814221E-13	2.43507819102431E-10
OTU_161_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		5.74278825679379	10.2349779732467	4.92679098989873E-12	3.14821944254529E-09
OTU_158_Fusobacterium_sp.	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	Fusobacterium	5.79670767785809	10.2805590075556	1.62488365542418E-11	7.78725491862038E-09
OTU_140_MWH-Ta3_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	MWH-Ta3	5.94733612132693	10.4720531520178	4.76102128708094E-11	1.53854490575875E-08
OTU_72_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	6.44617197890117	12.0796727610771	4.81547701332943E-11	1.53854490575875E-08
OTU_240_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	OTU_240_Microbacteriaceae	4.67961808382394	9.39974836276559	7.62285123829614E-11	2.08757226054481E-08
OTU_36_FukuN18_freshwater_group_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Terrimicrobiaceae	FukuN18_freshwater_group	- 8.69409363078018	13.4778344971428	9.04773603815923E-11	2.1680637481439E-08
OTU_221_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		4.94993158376515	9.59926217206087	1.30320482694839E-10	2.77582628140007E-08
OTU_70_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	7.48959876199529	12.1367139569318	1.64815398066932E-10	3.15951118094309E-08
OTU_193_Bacillus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae	Bacillus	5.24270710697915	9.84777216113617	3.26412168167929E-10	5.5734874268128E-08
OTU_223_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	OTU_223_Verrucomicrobiaceae	4.9352132070193	9.58815021694065	3.48888101834917E-10	5.5734874268128E-08
OTU_54_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	- 6.9067400267184	12.7290722008988	4.04743764707587E-10	5.96841382264957E-08
OTU_238_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	4.70297616618518	9.41659754745781	8.73040523446356E-10	1.19544191674762E-07
OTU_47_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	7.32633538443365	12.9954398855033	1.17617665303723E-09	1.46699128048482E-07
OTU_260_Planctomycetales	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales		OTU_260_Planctomycetales	4.44694812848967	9.23616488819711	1.22440586790595E-09	1.46699128048482E-07
OTU_114_Diplorickettsiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Diplorickettsiales	Diplorickettsiaceae	OTU_114_Diplorickettsiaceae	- 6.42107781073522	11.0202831016843	1.38788609832809E-09	1.56504567676174E-07
OTU_292_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	OTU_292_Microbacteriaceae	4.10948074347444	9.01337693703203	1.57109687088784E-09	1.67321816749555E-07
OTU_214_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	- 4.92283213947754	9.63928906593245	1.72837289286366E-09	1.74383728190508E-07
OTU_119_Deefgea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Chitinibacteraceae	Deefgea	5.93724151293344	10.8601426124127	2.12293603271049E-09	0.0000002034834187353
OTU_270_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		4.36512161199068	9.18053018922429	3.51854120400471E-09	3.21192547051287E-07
OTU_299_WPS-2	WPS-2					4.06510369490482	8.98541685569114	4.69525233591684E-09	4.09127214906936E-07
OTU_58_Ideonella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Ideonella	- 6.57845423081531	11.5900081631612	5.9247276852008E-09	4.93813172718692E-07
OTU_280_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	4.21479527349689	9.08099451567337	6.70733049078161E-09	5.35748022951181E-07

OTU_33_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	- 8.20951353 683997	13.6713416 482312	7.20705895313 035E-09	5.52637280526 036E-07
OTU_31_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		7.15572398 758747	13.8419367 950537	1.49124922784 855E-08	1.09950952684 064E-06
OTU_174_Haemophilus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Haemophilus	5.03161197 657528	10.0809945 156734	1.64597315799 676E-08	0.00000116864 09421777
OTU_284_Devosia_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Devosiaceae	Devosia	- 4.09164760 137342	9.05163245 604203	1.93234159176 841E-08	1.28894070388 984E-06
OTU_123_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	- 4.26099211 150268	9.16316305 72542	1.97711183591 795E-08	1.28894070388 984E-06
OTU_309_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	3.96238570 820022	8.92192802 970576	2.01712160233 151E-08	1.28894070388 984E-06
OTU_278_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	- 4.17683494 642498	9.10717844 747703	2.74437598835 972E-08	1.69708669989 857E-06
OTU_310_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacterales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	- 3.88535743 405888	8.92192802 970576	3.65790915353 298E-08	2.19131620228 835E-06
OTU_291_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	- 4.04924351 901985	9.02441098 730701	4.54833631843 066E-08	2.64216991588 836E-06
OTU_331_Roseimaritima_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Roseimaritima	3.76567340 704268	8.80522099 80089	4.99724436578 52E-08	2.81756395565 007E-06
OTU_294_Xanthobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Xanthobacteraceae	Xanthobacter	- 4.00555524 383317	8.99666599 68241	5.41745188949 077E-08	2.96721579204 394E-06
OTU_341_Cyclobacteriaceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	OTU_341_Cyclobacteriaceae	3.70911760 921309	8.77287222 031104	6.45227609373 867E-08	3.43583701991 584E-06
OTU_212_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	OTU_212_Verrucomicrobiaceae	3.38014270 883266	8.64644885 750532	7.26153184002 02E-08	3.76225852359 965E-06
OTU_241_Sphingomonadaceae	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	OTU_241_Sphingomonadaceae	4.38691911 885293	9.39762831 089122	8.70019954985 19E-08	4.38902172028 055E-06
OTU_61_Rhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Rhodobacter	5.55338459 865205	11.8701160 82354	8.94849189193 409E-08	4.39852793765 068E-06
OTU_226_Galbitalea_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Galbitalea	3.98515088 534247	9.56755331 233354	9.59095740647 193E-08	4.59646633705 167E-06
OTU_354_Prevotella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Prevotellaceae	Prevotella	3.60137025 724277	8.71275122 787347	1.05519950998 654E-07	4.93370112352 242E-06
OTU_356_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	OTU_356_Verrucomicrobiaceae	3.56995486 154146	8.69559650 68344	1.22193214916 768E-07	5.46457067275 254E-06
OTU_357_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.56995486 154146	8.69559650 68344	1.22575137677 809E-07	5.46457067275 254E-06
OTU_373_Brevifollis_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae	Brevifollis	3.43697004 45288	8.62486199 529717	1.34964026220 14E-07	0.00000588013 72332729
OTU_325_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	- 3.75422768 278728	8.84310575 801376	1.52235612588 139E-07	6.48523709625 472E-06
OTU_67_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	6.27021133 765252	12.1752800 890934	1.64434750531 35E-07	0.00000685263 94949695
OTU_287_Phreatobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiales_Incertae_Sedis	Phreatobacter	3.47916968 157595	9.04080542 555768	1.84949117395 229E-07	7.54356293716 286E-06

OTU_85_Aeromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Aeromonadales	Aeromonadaceae	Aeromonas	5.04633892063245	11.4999900285209	1.90769955055489E-07	0.0000076188750800286
OTU_105_Prostheco bacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaeae	Prostheco bacter	5.91644542098941	11.2684281669704	2.63109313692041E-07	0.0000102934807009723
OTU_312_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	OTU_312_Microbacteriaceae	3.7931410628379	8.91601533683586	2.97046427816383E-07	0.0000113887600424801
OTU_23_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-7.99951289688257	14.2725554310631	3.16909434442607E-07	0.0000119120663887545
OTU_386_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	3.35086697928526	8.5806944120216	3.44893462061083E-07	0.000012510689560708
OTU_387_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	3.35086697928526	8.5806944120216	3.45887609137988E-07	0.000012510689560708
OTU_388_Actinobacillus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Actinobacillus	3.32098484866815	8.56566620278927	3.98580554868385E-07	0.0000141496096978277
OTU_330_Pseudorhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Pseudorhodobacter	-3.51345955251905	8.70591379781992	4.19898115486341E-07	0.0000146353579524966
OTU_435_Rhodobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Rhodobacter	3.11002690855417	8.46397080571992	4.29724269585378E-07	0.000014710382585628
OTU_104_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	6.00014732652971	11.3016873157166	4.52054186763918E-07	0.0000152032960706391
OTU_359_Reyranella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Reyranellales	Reyranellaceae	Reyranella	-3.48192397908594	8.68867709289461	4.80894511844834E-07	0.0000158943927449405
OTU_413_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	3.25139731937186	8.53126919500876	5.54870894716706E-07	0.000018028601782575
OTU_29_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	6.0199081053993	13.9237707877043	5.94859932654842E-07	0.0000190057748483222
OTU_125_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	4.75621497285051	10.7564216995304	6.62680613205582E-07	0.0000208255530412312
OTU_420_Haliscomenobacter_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae	Haliscomenobacter	3.1782824182439	8.49603201495222	7.30809771090746E-07	0.0000224796893835208
OTU_421_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae	OTU_421_Rubinisphaeraceae	3.1782824182439	8.49603201495222	7.38769134669697E-07	0.0000224796893835208
OTU_468_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaeae	OTU_468_Verrucomicrobiaceae	2.84195996771054	8.3457893793716	8.07675074853155E-07	0.0000241923924764609
OTU_429_Bergeyella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Weeksellaceae	Bergeyella	3.14455828128389	8.4800904710832	8.25807546808536E-07	0.0000243549702651071
OTU_254_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	-3.34138840889318	8.61394621781799	8.86413983478412E-07	0.0000257462970655775
OTU_266_Solitalea_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Solitalea	3.29047066336576	8.59186371973971	9.30569521333546E-07	0.0000266253995880061
OTU_65_Rothia_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Rothia	5.79126931103324	12.3236277294475	1.16937017309461E-06	0.0000329659209091524
OTU_215_Tabrizicola_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Tabrizicola	3.48492159339135	8.75642169953045	1.20875580291687E-06	0.0000335823894810382
OTU_471_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.85244281158614	8.35018114848876	1.25340315874209E-06	0.0000338502524358902
OTU_394_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	OTU_394_Burkholderiaceae	-3.26192078552309	8.57319987547468	1.25371305318112E-06	0.0000338502524358902

OTU_350_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	3.17637641539423	8.73978143384262	1.34922822979936E-06	0.0000359232016184078
OTU_66_Microbacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Microbacterium	4.89237921124521	12.310728912351	1.41839933643248E-06	0.0000372475551772747
OTU_138_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Runella	-4.78233089837513	10.4930563623864	1.54414143218716E-06	0.0000400016098040917
OTU_408_Zoogloea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Zoogloea	-3.2012466124649	8.54282622643116	1.63719235654767E-06	0.0000414349192818418
OTU_95_Betaproteobacteriales	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	OTU_95_Betaproteobacteriales		5.20350152439597	11.563776621588	1.64269893866457E-06	0.0000414349192818418
OTU_311_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.55719462321363	8.91897471231641	1.79703525516687E-06	0.0000447391764175959
OTU_401_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	2.90374404029165	8.37194166722757	2.17373308777834E-06	0.0000534236708880908
OTU_207_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.44391861926597	9.6410823477555	2.21392260982911E-06	0.0000537226537093975
OTU_423_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	-3.08851016981967	8.48808326183673	2.47490982582316E-06	0.0000593050267012875
OTU_426_Gemmobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Gemmobacter	-3.08011017496326	8.48409240164069	2.54366394599756E-06	0.0000602000467219422
OTU_320_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	-3.05461269172569	8.47205315201778	2.81155380154046E-06	0.0000657286419213788
OTU_482_Rubinisphaeraceae	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae	OTU_482_Rubinisphaeraceae	2.81004651806387	8.33253328266934	3.25099167159005E-06	0.0000750861570414231
OTU_483_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	2.81004651806387	8.33253328266934	3.29107780501368E-06	0.0000751070970501336
OTU_286_Methylobacterium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Beijerinckiaceae	Methylobacterium	-3.2648885315753	8.92781658906821	3.55791708230489E-06	0.0000802414946679821
OTU_487_Bdellovibrio_sp.	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Bdellovibrionales	Bdellovibrionaceae	Bdellovibrio	2.77741111988461	8.31915425286814	3.86771903974595E-06	0.0000862141558045697
OTU_462_Saprospiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae	OTU_462_Saprospiraceae	-2.77128566735008	8.38055479753228	4.00215612920855E-06	0.0000881854402263539
OTU_450_Haemophilus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Haemophilus	-2.91989326080616	8.41030214092633	4.65720484904647E-06	0.000101452973813887
OTU_398_Reyranella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Reyranellales	Reyranellaceae	Reyranella	2.7129393201655	8.56188456224684	4.87919901821525E-06	0.000104437317892529
OTU_453_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	-2.90094132927733	8.40186530377769	0.000004903160464438	0.000104437317892529
OTU_183_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	4.43653464538836	9.94533941631581	5.12629493335896E-06	0.000107990191068672
OTU_498_0319-6G20	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Oligoflexales	0319-6G20	OTU_498_0319-6G20	2.69826206483572	8.2874453931408	0.0000054679567534902	0.000113935577135225
OTU_358_Solitalea_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Solitalea	2.68659207165109	8.28285812364515	5.74059254311942E-06	0.000118330278550107

OTU_402_Micrococcus_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Micrococcus	2.99172561002108	8.55809298308447	6.20561222640055E-06	0.000126554879127765
OTU_492_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	- 2.66296501272243	8.30112033003788	6.56854276335834E-06	0.000132546278709031
OTU_142_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	OTU_142_Microbacteriaceae	4.42604545014275	10.6057048400477	6.80601651304036E-06	0.000135907642244775
OTU_514_Acinetobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter	2.6510047780811	8.26900814488412	6.96886658560492E-06	0.00013772492004747
OTU_489_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	- 2.68528955939388	8.31016546964088	7.12319317046438E-06	0.000139338380691635
OTU_467_Roseateles_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Roseateles	2.62678267641578	8.2597004026579	7.71967394399355E-06	0.00014948095909733
OTU_473_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	- 2.78168351445541	8.35018114848876	8.06726250714329E-06	0.000154649422261937
OTU_479_Chitinophagales	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales		OTU_479_Chitinophagales	- 2.76081233612057	8.3413842002516	8.51326930126926E-06	0.000161583537133992
OTU_522_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.58966950339868	8.24562521744617	9.24252658409413E-06	0.000173705131977534
OTU_504_Veillonella_sp.	Firmicutes	Negativicutes	Selenomonadales	Veillonellaceae	Veillonella	2.57708320729157	8.24090280720377	9.63482631052783E-06	0.000179320019779436
OTU_229_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.18114952713819	9.53320180754276	0.0000102731970473835	0.000189362680190714
OTU_122_Granulicatella_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Carnobacteriaceae	Granulicatella	4.51289736019815	10.7802141956522	0.0000104361320663129	0.000190533954010685
OTU_553_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	OTU_553_Burkholderiaceae	2.40260804973733	8.17806193363354	0.0000120073097854383	0.000217151064704578
OTU_345_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	- 3.27669884089436	8.7630244343547	0.0000122392680133988	0.000219277353099865
OTU_527_SH-PL14_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales	Rubinisphaeraceae	SH-PL14	- 2.49620035217344	8.23616488819711	0.00001355987953142	0.000240687861682705
OTU_89_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	OTU_89_Burkholderiaceae	- 4.52201233717453	11.6716706675889	0.0000139477956211472	0.000245302056933388
OTU_154_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	4.34298971041519	10.3611024348661	0.0000147738960363554	0.000256976283255586
OTU_555_Galbitalea_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Galbitalea	2.38827058971606	8.17311271766181	0.0000148796908927334	0.000256976283255586
OTU_277_Mycobacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Mycobacteriaceae	Mycobacterium	- 2.7072739092294	8.35018114848876	0.0000159484565621008	0.000272974921692385
OTU_546_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.45857414756249	8.19769074038247	0.0000175910410147378	0.000298425005533207
OTU_76_Shinella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Shinella	4.91911843695685	11.8048210825411	0.0000185178354121993	0.000311392021799877
OTU_516_Roseococcus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseococcus	- 2.57004308088542	8.26436178002776	0.0000194910104260617	0.000324906669450089

OTU_205_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	- 3.71678771 222858	9.67998089 39248	0.00001994065 77959018	0.00032953656 0299516
OTU_517_Leucobacter_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Leucobacter	- 2.54584637 045477	8.25502391 544842	0.00002164181 84169867	0.00035459287 0986013
OTU_96_Acidovorax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Acidovorax	- 4.70336670 864129	11.5210802 857148	0.00002317783 17274445	0.00037654155 4419585
OTU_26_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	- 5.40251976 61528	14.0019962 10785	0.00002435774 21049977	0.00038992557 1156246
OTU_519_Planctomycetales	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales		OTU_519_Planctomycetales	2.35226752 40032	8.24562521 744617	0.00002440848 6457355	0.00038992557 1156246
OTU_557_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	2.37378921 301133	8.16814646 476845	0.00002714869 81924941	0.00043011615 2355464
OTU_565_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	2.32945194 526917	8.15314430 142921	0.00003376946 42909675	0.00052850374 7173199
OTU_539_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	- 2.44478484 267289	8.21705606 52494	0.00003391025 60784056	0.00052850374 7173199
OTU_319_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	- 2.43163946 661597	8.21223904 895163	0.00003571236 79962257	0.00055210168 910294
OTU_572_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	2.29911821 197928	8.14305548 380563	0.00003963325 97424426	0.00060781567 14101
OTU_52_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	4.75011094 769546	12.8362734 163853	0.00004362913 89984582	0.00066378618 6190829
OTU_472_Pseudomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas	2.57708320 729157	8.35018114 848876	0.00004730000 4193736	0.00071396935 4640882
OTU_452_Corynebacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	Corynebacterium	2.63894456 121729	8.40186530 377769	0.00004846015 84006303	0.00072119078 386634
OTU_69_Saprosiraceae	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Chitinophagales	Saprosiraceae	OTU_69_Saprosiraceae	4.37244921 884796	12.1684573 569237	0.00004886860 72028848	0.00072119078 386634
OTU_256_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Runella	3.31341659 503184	9.28285812 364515	0.00004890704 3246022	0.00072119078 386634
OTU_20_Luteolibacter_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Rubritaleaceae	Luteolibacter	4.67067077 447992	14.5038756 212583	0.00005116214 09472252	0.00074619247 1350869
OTU_559_Devosiaceae	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Devosiaceae	OTU_559_Devosiaceae	2.17848137 272912	8.15816237 619583	0.00005175705 95133981	0.00074619247 1350869
OTU_230_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	3.40265798 14581	9.53126919 500876	0.00005177026 53571547	0.00074619247 1350869
OTU_190_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	3.35086697 928526	9.87850165 177463	0.00005319291 28379285	0.00076097622 3211261
OTU_11_Betaproteobacteriales	Proteobacteria	Gamma proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	T34		5.20898953 223475	15.3536029 399531	0.00005427749 54122805	0.00077074043 4854383
OTU_585_Microbacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Microbacterium	2.23646760 654817	8.12266369 497445	0.00005600771 44983398	0.00078946168 156851
OTU_194_Brevundimonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacteriales	Caulobacteraceae	Brevundimonas	- 2.76081233 612057	8.51571438 081392	0.00006048318 19606573	0.00084632306 4369197
OTU_380_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	OTU_380_Microbacteriaceae	2.77741111 988462	8.60294721 886873	0.00006276815 23536815	0.00086947548 3926062

OTU_366_Dechloromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	- 2.67884077 172375	8.65001547 252551	0.00006339304 41293053	0.00086947548 3926062
OTU_78_Corynebacterium_1_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	Corynebacterium_1	4.19457696 174723	11.7883283 623785	0.00006352645 80612287	0.00086947548 3926062
OTU_149_Roseococcus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseococcus	- 3.79789086 092373	10.3697803 259381	0.00006395203 08991	0.00086947548 3926062
Recipients (Stressor treatments x Microbial inocula)									
OTU_73_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	8.83042717 603799	12.0590291 841766	1.90163928570 552E-12	3.64544251069 748E-09
OTU_158_Fusobacterium_sp.	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	Fusobacterium	6.87036471 95834	10.2805590 075556	1.16027177793 997E-10	1.11212049915 547E-07
OTU_70_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	8.57280547 507686	12.1367139 569318	4.07543111165 276E-10	2.60420048034 611E-07
OTU_193_Bacillus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae	Bacillus	6.30985526 258679	9.84777216 113618	1.65053349640 291E-09	7.91018178151 095E-07
OTU_36_FukuN18_freshwater_group_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Terrimicrobiaceae	FukuN18_freshwater_group	- 9.34946553 990565	13.4778344 971428	5.69713347573 227E-09	2.18428097459 575E-06
OTU_280_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacteriales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	5.26052755 022322	9.08099451 567337	1.18539919087 932E-08	3.74015478369 162E-06
OTU_116_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	7.35950555 270384	10.9300186 170321	1.36573205455 615E-08	3.74015478369 162E-06
OTU_114_Diplorickettsiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Diplorickettsiales	Diplorickettsiaceae	OTU_114_Diplorickettsiaceae	- 7.41263518 299956	11.0202831 016843	3.30631722368 019E-08	7.92276264724 366E-06
OTU_240_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	OTU_240_Microbacteriaceae	5.47031993 478003	9.39974836 276559	6.87283100521 973E-08	0.00001463913 0041118
OTU_111_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	7.45395648 857115	11.1493692 577378	2.74965511598 602E-07	0.00004584347 10656114
OTU_388_Actinobacillus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Actinobacillus	4.32992088 564089	8.56566620 278927	2.76301510000 368E-07	0.00004584347 10656114
OTU_291_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	- 5.00500068 105837	9.02441098 730701	2.99643850066 199E-07	0.00004584347 10656114
OTU_33_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	- 9.20176090 450501	13.6713416 482312	3.10884258660 901E-07	0.00004584347 10656114
OTU_294_Xanthobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Xanthobacteraceae	Xanthobacter	- 4.95993039 997391	8.99666599 68241	3.38161339071 426E-07	0.00004630394 90714232
OTU_429_Bergeyella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Weeksellaceae	Bergeyella	4.14295795 384204	8.48009047 108319	4.44039530168 804E-07	0.00005674825 19555731
OTU_58_Ideonella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Ideonella	- 7.50181261 772776	11.5900081 631612	5.79474994203 867E-07	0.00006942834 77430508
OTU_23_Polynucleobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Polynucleobacter	- 8.99669142 442387	14.2725554 310631	6.47913338191 917E-07	0.00007306175 7018465
OTU_325_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	- 4.69975451 506913	8.84310575 801376	6.93482915014 925E-07	0.00007385593 04490896

OTU_487_Bdellovibrio_sp.	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Bdellovibrionales	Bdellovibrionaceae	Bdellovibrio	3.74893823583228	8.31915425286814	1.32826523426629E-06	0.000134014971267815
OTU_359_Reyranella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Reyranellales	Reyranellaceae	Reyranella	-4.41587215075766	8.68867709289461	1.54820385930399E-06	0.000146991505735689
OTU_104_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	7.07562770481337	11.3016873157166	1.61023558708892E-06	0.000146991505735689
OTU_498_0319-6G20	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Oligoflexales	0319-6G20	OTU_498_0319-6G20	3.66296501272243	8.2874453931408	1.71297438187375E-06	0.000149262358638726
OTU_85_Aeromonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Aeromonadales	Aeromonadaceae	Aeromonas	6.33011943011301	11.4999900285209	1.89046071067453E-06	0.000157565790537525
OTU_394_Burkholderiaceae	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	OTU_394_Burkholderiaceae	-4.18469171215122	8.57319987547468	3.04415534323468E-06	0.00024315190804087
OTU_408_Zoogloea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Rhodocyclaceae	Zoogloea	-4.12060589342501	8.54282622643116	3.67831126175383E-06	0.000282052907551284
OTU_320_Hydrogenophaga_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Burkholderiaceae	Hydrogenophaga	-3.96507166669705	8.47205315201778	5.04153416763587E-06	0.000365600696424392
OTU_183_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	5.48828648130948	9.94533941631581	5.31152135404717E-06	0.000365600696424392
OTU_138_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Spirosomaceae	Runella	-5.75587666575442	10.4930563623864	5.34002060505111E-06	0.000365600696424392
OTU_47_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	8.14522456081399	12.9954398855033	0.0000056067827330034	0.000370627672385087
OTU_557_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	3.30580842952408	8.16814646476846	6.51121437669923E-06	0.000416066598671081
OTU_565_Aurantimicrobium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Aurantimicrobium	3.25633975325978	8.15314430142921	7.82300967819114E-06	0.000483764824293304
OTU_585_Microbacterium_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Microbacterium	3.15200309344505	8.12266369497445	0.0000122022690772159	0.00072827748874302
OTU_140_MWH-Ta3_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	MWH-Ta3	5.39231742277876	10.4720531520178	0.0000125368581786748	0.00072827748874302
OTU_160_Rothia_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Rothia	5.59825932333461	10.2409028072038	0.0000145023715145043	0.000817677829214846
Recipients (Stressor treatments x Microbial inocula x Genotype)									
OTU_294_Xanthobacter_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales		Xanthobacteraceae	-6.513.654	8.996.666	2.58	0.004953957
OTU_359_Reyranella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Reyranellales		Reyranellaceae	-5.955.058	8.688.677	6.83	0.006543253
OTU_408_Zoogloea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales		Rhodocyclaceae	-5.649.190	8.542.826	11.8	0.007526680
OTU_96_Acidovorax_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales		Burkholderiaceae	-9.023.498	11.521.080	30.3	0.014522936
OTU_138_Runella_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales		Spirosomaceae	-7.322.930	10.493.056	1,28E+02	0.049033917
Recipients within lab microbiome inoculum (Stressor treatments)									
OTU_73_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	8.83042718	12.8135303	0.0000000097475	0.000018686
OTU_116_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	7.35950555	11.3982632	0.000000073613	0.000070558

OTU_33_Flavobacterium_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Flavobacterium	-9.2017609	13.3444687	0.00000013603	0.000075062
OTU_158_Fusobacterium_sp.	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	Fusobacterium	6.87036472	10.9431871	0.00000015662	0.000075062
OTU_240_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae		5.47031993	9.72331025	0.0000003896	0.00014937
OTU_70_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	8.57280548	12.8945379	0.00000047934	0.00015315
OTU_47_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	8.14522456	12.3577524	0.00000093946	0.00023781
OTU_193_Bacillus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae	Bacillus	6.30985526	10.4620342	0.00000099242	0.00023781
OTU_140_MWH-Ta3_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	MWH-Ta3	5.39231742	9.66037899	0.0000022924	0.00048828
OTU_111_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	7.45395649	11.5857334	0.0000028245	0.00052568
OTU_280_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacterales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	5.26052755	9.5555828	0.0000030164	0.00052568
OTU_36_FukuN18_freshwater_group_sp.	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Chthoniobacterales	Terrimicrobiaceae	FukuN18_freshwater_group	-9.34946554	14.2567824	0.0000037186	0.00059405
Recipients within natural microbiome inoculum (Stressor treatments)									
OTU_103_Pirellula_sp.	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Pirellulales	Pirellulaceae	Pirellula	7.90339838	12.4833509	0.000000029775	0.0000057079
OTU_161_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		6.64759167	11.3032362	0.0000001308	0.00012537
OTU_226_Galbitalea_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Galbitalea	5.75851112	10.5183887	0.00000064021	0.00035656
OTU_221_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		5.84533516	10.5923893	0.00000074399	0.00035656
OTU_292_Microbacteriaceae	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae		4.98714117	9.89380478	0.0000011756	0.00045071
OTU_214_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	-5.89885328	10.6383256	0.0000016921	0.00052019
OTU_223_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		5.83038805	10.5796031	0.0000018995	0.00052019
OTU_260_Planctomycetales	Planctomycetes	Planctomycetacia	Planctomycetales			5.33301727	10.1659919	0.0000022696	0.00052802
OTU_72_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	6.68519089	13.2403132	0.0000026241	0.00052802
OTU_238_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	5.59420939	10.380215	0.0000028658	0.00052802
OTU_299_WPS-2	WPS-2					4.94150051	9.85895538	0.0000034838	0.00052802
OTU_140_MWH-Ta3_sp.	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteriia	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	MWH-Ta3	6.30783327	11.091391	0.0000035368	0.00052802
OTU_284_Devosia_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Devosiaceae	Devosia	-5.0487055	9.94122156	0.0000035807	0.00052802
OTU_310_Roseomonas_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Acetobacterales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas	-4.83569955	9.7791881	0.0000043811	0.00056801
OTU_54_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	-7.26044573	13.9021732	0.0000044572	0.00056801
OTU_111_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	-5.31523344	10.1516651	0.0000047408	0.00056801

OTU_270_DEV007	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	DEV007		5.24933296	10.0988777	0.0000053179	0.00059339
OTU_123_Algoriphagus_sp.	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Cytophagales	Cyclobacteriaceae	Algoriphagus	-5.22286942	10.0778161	0.0000055718	0.00059339
OTU_278_Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium_sp.	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Rhizobiaceae	Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium	-5.1363899	10.0095468	0.0000065668	0.00066255
OTU_212_Verrucomicrobiaceae	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae	Verrucomicrobiales	Verrucomicrobiaceae		4.23095443	9.42140308	0.0000072734	0.00069715
OTU_116_Streptococcus_sp.	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus	-4.87992355	9.81235496	0.000010982	0.00098379
OTU_174_Haemophilus_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Haemophilus	5.24933296	10.1371947	0.00001129	0.00098379
OTU_309_Legionella_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Legionellales	Legionellaceae	Legionella	4.83569955	9.7791881	0.000012008	0.00099261
OTU_119_Deefgea_sp.	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Betaproteobacteriales	Chitinibacteraceae	Deefgea	6.549225	11.9741612	0.000012427	0.00099261

Table SI10: Overview primers LSU and SSU region for the characterization of the fungal infection.

Region	Primer Name	Forward/reverse	Sequence
LSU	LR0R	Forward	GTACCCGCTGAACTTAAGC
	LR5	Reverse	TCCTGAGGGAAACTTCG
SSU	NS1	Forward	GTAGTCATATGCTTGTCTC
	NS4	Reverse	CTTCCGTCAATTCCTTAAG
ITS 1 and 2	ITS1F	Forward	CTTGGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA
	ITS4	Reverse	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC
ITS 2	ITS86F	Forward	GTGAATCATCGAATCTTTGAA
	ITS4	Reverse	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC

Table SI11: Summary of the sequencing results of characterization of the infection. Sample represents the sample name. Sample details shows Daphnia with visible infection, and Daphnia with no visible infection. Sequence fragment shows if the small subunit or the large subunit of the ribosome is sequenced. Forward and reverse show if the sequence is the forward or reverse sequence. Received sequence shows a part of the received sequence. Length shows the length of the received sequence. nValue is 50% of the sequences length, which we used as expectation value in the FungiDB blast. FungiDB shows the best match of the sequence in the FungiDB blasting. Score is the nucleotide match between query and alignment sequences and E-value is the random background noise.

Sample	Sample details	Sequence fragment	Forward	Reverse	Received sequence	Length	Expectation Value	FungiDB	Score	E value
S4 SSU NS4	Visible infection	Short Subunit		X	TTCCCCGGAACCAAAGACTTTGGTTTCCCGGAAGCTGCCCGTCGAG TCATTGGAGTAACTCCGACGGATTGCTGGTTGGCATCGTTATGGT TAGAACTAGGGCGGTATCTGATCGCCTTCAACCTCTAACTTTCGTT CTTGATCAAGGAAAACATTCTTGGCAAATGCCTTCGCTGTTGTTTCGT CTTGCGGCGGTCCAAGAATTCACCTCTGTCGCCGCGAGTACGAATG CCCCCGTCGCTCTATTGACCATTACCTCGGGTCCAAAAGAAAAG ACCAGAAAATCGGACCGAGGTCCTATCCATCATTCCATGCTGCG ATATTCAGGCGTTGGGATACACCTGCTTTGAGCACTCTAATTTGTT AAAGTAAACGTTGCCGGCCGCCGAGACACCCGGTGAAGGGCACC CCGAACGATTGACTGGGTGGAGCGAACCCGCTCAACTGAACGCGA GCGATCACCCCCCTCGACGGAGCGAACCCCGAAGAGGAAGAA AACGAAACGCCACGCGAACCGATACAACGCGACCCACCGGCCACC ACTCCGGCGATGTTGTCCGACCGTGAAGAGAGTCGGGCTTTGACAC CCGGGCTCCAGAGCGTGAAACGCAACACCTTGATTAGAGCGG CGCCGCCCGCCGAAGACAGACATCCGACTACGAGCTTTTTAACCG CAACAACTTAATATACGCTATTGGAGCTGGAGTTACCGCGGCTGC TGGCACAGACTTGCCCTCAATGGTTCCTCGTTAAAGGATTTAAA GTGTAATCAATCAATCACGGGGCCTCGGAAGAGTCCCGTATCGTT ATTTTTCGTAACCTCCCCGTGCCGGGAGTGGGTAATTTGCGCGC CTGCTGCCTTCTTGATGTGGTAGCCGTTTCTCAGGCTCCCTCTCC GGAATCGAACCCCGATTCCCCGTTACCCGTAGCAACCATGGTAGGC GCGTAACTACCATCGACAGTTGATAAGGCAGACATTTGAAAGATA CGTCGCCGGCTCGAAGGCATGCGATCGGCGTGAAGTTATCCAGAG TCACAAAATTGGGTACGGGTGCGCGACGGTTGCCCGCTCGCCC GACTGGTTTTGATCTAATAAAAGC	1127	563	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	500	1E-138
S4 SSU NS1	Visible infection	Short Subunit	X		GCCGCTAGACGGCGAAACCGCAATGGCTCAATAAATCAGTTATG GTTCCTTAGATCCACTCCATCCTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTA GAGCTAATACATGACTCGAGCCTCGACTGCGCCCGCTTCGCGGTG GGTGCAAGAGAGGTGCTTTTATTAGATCAAACCAAGTCGGGGCGA GCGGCGGGCAACCGTCGCGCGACCCGTACCAATTTTGGTACTCTG GATAAATTCACGCCGATCGCATGGCCTTCGAGCCGGCGACGTATCT TTCAAATGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGGTTACGCGCTAC CATGGTTGCTACGGGTAACGGGGAATCGGGGTTGATTCCGGAGA GGGAGCTGAGAAACGGCTACCACATCAAGGAAGGCAGCAGGC GCGCAAATTACCACTCCCGCACGGGGAGGTAGTGACGAAAAAT AACGATACGGGACTCTCCGAGGCCCGTGATTGGAATGAGTACAC TTTAAATCCTTTAACGAGGAACCATTTGGAGGGCAAGTCTGGTGCCA GCAGCCGCGGTAACCTCAGCTCCAATAGCGTATATTAAGTTGTTG CGGTTAAAAGCTCGTAGTCGGATGTCTGCTTCGGCCGGGCGGC	1064	531	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	544	1E-151

					<p>GCCGCTCTGAATCAAGGGTGTTCGCTTTCACGCTCTGGGAGCCCGG GTGTCAAAGCCCGACTCTTTCACGGTCGGACAACATCGCCGGAGT GGTGGCCGGTGGGTGCGGTTGTATCGGTTGCGGTGGCGTTTCGTTT TCTTCTCTTCGGGGTTCGCTCCGTCGAGGGGGGGGGGTGATCGCT CGCGTTACAGTTGACGCGGTTGCTCCACCCAGTCAATCGTTCGGGG TGCCCTTACCAGGGTGTCTCGGGCGGCCGGCAACGTTTACTTTGAA CAAATTAGAGTGCTCAAAGCAGGTGTATCCCAACGCCTGAATATCG CAGCATGGAATGATGGAATAGGACCTCGGTCCGATTTTGCTGGTCT TTTCTTTGGACCCGAGGTAATGGTCAATAAGAGACGGACGGGGG CATTCGTA CTGC</p>					
S5 SSU NS4	Visible infection	Short Subunit		X	<p>TTCCCCGGAACCAAAGACTTTGGTTTCCGGGAAGCTGCCCGTCGAG TCATTGGAGTA ACTCCGACGGATTGCTGGTTGGCATCGTTTATGGT TAGAACTAGGGCGGTATCTGATCGCTTCAACCTCTAACTTTCGTT CTTGATCAAGGAAAACATTCTGGCAAATGCCTTCGCTGTTGTTCTGT CTTGCGGGCGTCCAAGAATTCACCTCTGTGCGCCGAGTACGAATG CCCCCGTCCGTCTATTGACCATTACCTCGGGTCCAAAAGAAAAG ACCAGCAAAATCGGACCGAGGTCTATTCCATCATTCCATGCTGCG ATATTCAGGCGTTGGGATACACCTGCTTGGAGCACTCTAATTTGTTT AAAGTAAACGTTGCCGGCCGCCGAGACACCCGGTGAAGGGCACC CCGAACGATTGACTGGGTGGAGCGAACCCGCTCAACTGAACGCGA GCGATCACCCCCCTCGACGGAGCGAACCCGAAGAGGAAGAA AACGAAACGCCACGCGAACCGATACAACGCGACCCACCGGCCACC ACTCCGGCGATGTTGTCCGACCGTGAAGAGAGTCCGGCTTTGACAC CCGGGCTCCAGAGCGTGAAACGCAACACCCTTGATTAGAGCGG CGCCGCCCGCCGAAGACAGACATCCGACTACGAGCTTTTTAACCG CAACAACCTTAATATACGCTATTGGAGCTGGAGTTACCGCGGCTGC TGGCACCAGACTTGCCCTCAATGGTTCCTCGTTAAAGGATTTAAA GTGTACTATTCCAATCACGGGGCCTCGGAAGAGTCCCGTATCGTT ATTTTTCGTCACTACCTCCCCGTGCCGGGAGTGGGTAATTTGCGCGC CTGCTGCCTTCTTTGGATGTGGTAGCCGTTTCTCAGGCTCCCTCTCC GGAATCGAACCCCGATTCCCGTTACCCGTAGCAACCATGGTAGGC GCGTAACTACCATCGACAGTTGATAAGGCAGACATTTGAAAGATA CGTCGCCGGCTCGAAGGCCATGCGATCGGCGTGAAGTTATCCAGA GTCACAAATTGGGTACGGGTGCGCGACGGTTGCC</p>	1093	546	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	508	8E-141
S5 SSU NS1	Visible infection	Short Subunit	X		<p>GCCGCTAGACGGCGAAACCGCAATGGCTCAATAAATCAGTTATG GTTCTTAGATCCACTCCATCCTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTA GAGCTAATACATGCACTCGAGCCTCGACTGCGCCCGTTCGCGGTG GGTGCAGAAGAGGTGCTTTTATTAGATCAAACAGTCCGGGGCGA GCGGCGGGCAACCGTCGCGCGACCCGTACCAATTTTGGTACTCTG GATAACTTCACGCGATCGCATGGCCTTCGAGCCGGCGACGTATCT TTCAAATGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGGTTACGCGCTAC CATGGTTGTACGGGTAACGGGGAATCGGGGTTGATTCCGGAGA GGGAGCCTGAGAAACGGCTACCACATCAAGGAAGGCAGCAGGC GCGCAAATACCCTCCCGCACGGGGAGGTAGTGACGAAAAAT AACGATACGGGACTTTCCGAGGCCCGGTTGATTGGAATGAGTACAC TTTTAAATCCTTTAACGAGGAACCATTTGGAGGGCAAGTCTGGTGCCA GCAGCCGCGGTA ACTCCAGCTCCAATAGCGTATATTAAGTTGTTG CGGTTAAAAGCTCGTAGTCGGATGTCTGTCTTCGCGCCGGGCGGC GCCGCTCTGAATCAAGGGTGTTCGCTTTCACGCTCTGGGAGCCCGG</p>	1088	544	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	544	1E-151

					GTGTCAAAGCCGACTCTTTCACGGTCGGACAACATCGCCGGAGT GGTGGCCGGTGGGTCGCGTTGTATCGGTTGCGGTGGCGTTTCGTTT TCTTCTTTCGGGGTTCGCTCGTTCGAGGGGGGGGGTATCGCTC GCGTTCAGTTGACGCGGTTTCGCTCCACCCAGTCAATCGTTCGGGGT GCCCTTACCCGGGTGTCTCGGGCGGCCGGCAACGTTTACTTTGAAC AAATTAGAGTGCTCAAAGCAGGTGTATCCCAACGCTGAATATCGC AGCATGGAATGATGGAATAGGACCTCGGTCGATTTTGTGGTCTT TTCTTTTGACCCGAGGTAATGGTCAATAGAAACGGACGGGGGCA TTCGTAAGTTCGCGGACAGAGGTGAAATCTTGGACC					
S4 LSU LR5	Visible infection	Long Subunit		X	TAGTCTTTCGCCCTATACCCAACCTCCGACGATCGATTTGCACGTCA GAATCGTTCGCGACCTCCACAGGGTTTCCCCTGGCTTCGCTCTGG CCAGGCATAGGTACCATCTTTCGGGTCCCAACGTGTACGCTTTG GTTCTGTCGGCCGACTCGGCACACCGTTTGACCGGGGCCTCGCGAG CATTTCGACGCCAGGGGTTGCGCCGCTCTGTTTCGAGACGGGATC ACCCCTCGCGGATGCACCCTCATCGGGGCGGCTTCACTTTCATTGCG CCTCGCGAGTTTCGTAATAGACTCGACGACTCGCGCACATGTTAGA CTCCTTGGTCCGTGTTTCAAGACGGGTTCGGGTGGGACCCGACTTCT ACTCTCCGCTCTGGGCTCCGCGGTTTCTACAACGTGATGCCAAGC CCTGAAGTCCAGATCGAAGCCTTAGCGAGATACACGTAGACAAT CCGGGAGGAGACAGGTACGACCGGGCAGTACTGTTGAGTGACGC CGCGCTCGTCGAGGGCACACGAGGTAACCCAAAACCTCGCTAACGA ACGCCCGTATAACAGACACCCAGTTCGGTTCGCGGAGTCTACTAGG CCCCCACTTGGCGACCTTGGCGGGCTAATGCGGTCTTCGCAAC GAACAGAGCCGCAATCAAGTCGGTCTTTCGACGAGAGGGCA TGCAACCAAGTGCCGGGAGCGGGGGCTGTTTCGACCTTCGAGGGC CCACCCGTTAACCCCTGAACGGTTTCACGCACTTGAACCTCTCT CTTCAAAGTCTTTTCAACTTCCCTCGCGGACTTGTTCGCTATCGG TCTCGTGGCGATATTTAGCCTTAGAAGGAGTTTACCTCCCGCTTAGG GCTGCACGCTCAAGCAACCCGACTTTCGGGAAGGGATCCGATGCA CGGTCTCGGCTCGTCTAAGCTACGGGCTGACACCCTCTGTGGGTT GCTCGCCCGTTCATGGAGACTTGGACGATATATACCGGACAGGCG CGCAGATCTCCGAAACACCACTTCCCTCGGCACCCGCTCAACCG GGCGGAGGTTTCGGTGTGGGCTCATCCCTGTTTCGCTCGCCGCTAC TAAGGGAATCCTTGTAGTTTCTTTTC	1133	566	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	262	5E-67
S4 LSU LROR	Visible infection	Long Subunit	X		AACAGGATCCCTTAGTAGCGGCGAGCGAACAGGGATGAGCCAG CACCGAACCTCGCGCCCGGTTGAGCGGGTCCGAGGAATGTGGTG TTCGGGAGGATCGTGCAGCCTGTCCGGTATATATCGTCCAAGTCT CCATGAACGGGGCGAGCAACCCACAGAGGGTGCAGGCCCGTAGC TTAGACGAGCCGAGACCGTGCATCGGATCCCTTCCCAAGAGTCGG GTTGCTTAGCGTGACGCCCTAAGCGGGAGGTAACCTCCTTCTAAG GCTAAATATCGCCACGAGACCGATAGCGAACAGTACCGCGAGGG AAAGTTGAAAAGAACTTTGAAGAGAGAGTTCAAGAGTGCGTGAAA CCGTTACGGGGGTTAAACGGGTGGGCCCTCGAAGGTGCAACGAGC CCCCGCTCCGGCACTTGGTTGCATGCCCTGCTGCGAAGAGACC GACTTGATTTGGCGGCTCTGTTGTTGGCGAGGACCGCATTAGCCG CGCAAGGTCCGCAAGTGGGGGGCCTAGTAGGACTCCGCGACCGA CTGGGTGTCTGTTATACGGGGGCTTCTGTTAGCGAGTTTTGGGTTAC CTCGTGTGCCCTCGACGAGCGGGGCTCACTCAACAGTACTGCCCG GTCGTGACCTGTCTCCTCCCGATTGTCTACGTGTATCTCGTAGAG	1109	554	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	244	1E-61

					GCTTCGATCTGGAGCTTCAGGGCTTGGCATCACGTTGTAGAAAACC GCGGAGGCCAGAGCGGAGAGTAGAAGTCGGTCCCACCCGACCC GTCTTGAAACACGGACCAAGGAGTCTAACATGTGCGCGAGTCGTC GAGTCTATTACGAAACTCGCGAGGCGCAATGAAAGTGAAGCGGCC CCGATGAGGGTGCATCCGCGAGGGGTGATCCCGTCTCGAACAGAG CGGGCGCAACCCCTGGGCGTCCGAATGCTCGCGAGGCCCGGTCA AACGGTGTCCGAGTCGCGCGGACGAACCAAGAGCGTACACGTTG GGACCCGAAAGATGGTGACCTATGCCTGGCCAGGACGAAGCCAGG GGAAACCCTGGTGGAGGTCCGACGATTCTGACGTGCAATCGAT CGTCGAGTTGGGTATAGGG					
S5 LSU LR5	Visible infection	Long Subunit		X	ATTAGTCTTTCGCCCTATACCCAACCTCCGACGATCGATTGACGCT CAGAATCGTGCAGACTCCACCAGGGTTTCCCTGGCTTCGTCT GGCCAGGCATAGGTCACCATCTTTCGGGTCCCAACGTGTACGCTCT TGTTTCGTCGGCCGACTCGGCACACCGTTTGACCGGGCCTCGCG AGCATTCCGACGCCAGGGTTGCGCCCGCTCTGTTGAGACGGG ATCACCCCTCGCGGATGCACCCTATCGGGGCCGCTTCACTTTCATT GCGCTCGCGAGTTTCGTAATAGACTCGACGACTCGCGCACATGTT AGACTCCTTGGTCCGTGTTTCAAGACGGGTGGGTGGGACCCGACT TCTACTCTCCGCTCTGGGCTCCGCGTTTTCTACAACGTGATGCCA AGCCCTGAAGCTCCAGATCGAAGCCTTAGCGAGATACACGTAGAC AATCCGGGAGGAGACAGGTACGACCGGGCAGTACTGTTGAGTGA CGCCGCGCTCGTCGAGGGCACACGAGGTAACCCAAAACCTCGTAA CGAACGCCCCGTATAACAGACACCCAGTCGGTTCGCGGAGTCTACT AGGCCCCCACTTGCAGACTTGGCGGGCTAATGCGGTCTCTCGCC AACGAACAGAGCCGCAAATCAAGTCGGTCTTTCGAGCAGAGG GCATGCAACCAAGTGCCGGGAGCGGGGCTCGTTCGACCTTCGAG GGCCACCCGTTTAAACCCCTGAACGTTTTACGCACTCTTGAATC TCTCTCAAAGTTCTTTCAACTTTCCTCGCGGACTTGTTCGCTAT CGGTCTCGTGGCGATATTTAGCCTTAGAAGGAGTTTACCTCCGCTT AGGGCTGCACGCTCAAGCAACCCGACTCTTGGGAAGGGATCCGAT GCACGGTCTCGGCTCGTCTAAGCTACGGGCTGACACCCCTGTGG GTTGCTCGCCCCGTTTATGGAGACTTGGACGATATATACCGGACAG GCGGCACGATCCTCCGAACACCACATTCCTCGGACCCGCTCAC CGGGCGAGGTTCCGTTGCTGGGCTCATCCCTGTTGCTCGCGCTA CTAAGGGAATCCTTGTAGTT	1126	563	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	251	1E-63
S5 LSU LROR	Visible infection	Long Subunit	X		TAACAGGATTCCTTAGTAGCGGCGAGCGAACAGGGATGAGCCCA GCACCGAACCTCGCGCCGTTGAGCGGGTGCCGAGGAATGTGGT GTTCCGGGAGGATCGTGCAGCCTGTCCGGTATATATCGTCAAAGTC TCCATGAACGGGGCGAGCAACCCACAGAGGGTGTGAGGCCGTAG CTTAGACGAGCCGAGACCGTGCATCGGATCCCTCCCAAGAGTCGG GTTGCTTGAAGCTGCAGCCCTAAGCGGGAGGTAACCTCCTTCTAAG GCTAAATATCGCCACGAGACCGATAGCGAACAAGTACCGCGAGGG AAAGTTGAAAAGAACTTTGAAGAGAGAGTTCAAGAGTGCGTGAAA CCGTTGAGGGGTTAAACGGGTGGGCCCTCGAAGGTCGAACGAGC CCCCGCTCCCGCACTTGGTTGCATGCCCTGCTGCGAAGAGACC GACTTGATTTGGCGGCTCTGTTGTTGGCGAGGACCGCATTAGCCG CGCAAGGTCGCAAGTGGGGGCTAGTAGGACTCCGCGACCGA CTGGGTGTCTGTTATACGGGGCTTCTTAGCGAGTTTTGGGTTAC CTCGTGTGCCCTCGACGAGCGGGCTCACTCAACAGTACTGCCCG	1134	567	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	244	1E-61

					<p>GTCGTGACCTGTCTCTCCCGATTGTCTACGTGTATCTCGCTAGAG GCTTCGATCTGGAGCTTCAGGGCTTGGCATCACGTTGTAGAAAACC GCGGAGGCCAGAGCGGAGAGTAGAAGTCGGGTCCACCCGACCC GTCTTGAACACGGACCAAGGAGTCTAACATGTGCGCGAGTCGTC GAGTCTATTACGAAACTCGCGAGGGCGAATGAAAGTGAAGCGGCC CCGATGAGGGTGCATCCGCGAGGGGTGATCCCGTCTCGAACAGAG CGGGCGCAACCCCTGGGCGTCCGAATGCTCGCGAGGCCCGGTCA AACGGTGTGCCGAGTCGGCCGGACGAACCAAGAGCGTACACGTTG GGACCCGAAAGATGGTGACCTATGCCTGGCCAGGACGAAGCCAGG GGAAACCCTGGTGGAGTCCGCGAGGATTCTGACGTGCAATCGAT CGTCGGAATTGGGTATAGGGGCGAAAGACAATCGAACCTCTAGT</p>					
G4 SSU NS4	No visible infection	Short Subunit		X	<p>TTCCCCGGAACCAAGACTTTGGTTTCCCGGAAGCTGCCCGTCGAG TCATTGGAGTAACTCCGACGGATTGCTGGTTGGCATCGTTTATGGT TAGAACTAGGGCGGTATCTGATGCCTTCGAACCTCTAACTTTCGTT CTTGATCAAGGAAAACATTCTTGGCAAATGCCTTCGCTGTTGTTCTG CTTGCGGGCGTCCAAGATTTACCTCTGTCGCCGAGTACGAATG CCCCGTCCGTCTCTATTGACCATTACCTCGGGTCCAAAAGAAAAG ACCAGCAAAATCGGACCGAGGTCTATTCCATCATTCCATGCTGCG ATATTCAGGCGTTGGGATACACCTGCTTTGAGCACTCTAATTTGTT AAAGTAAACGTTGCCGGCCCGGAGACACCCGGTGAAGGGCACC CCGAACGATTGACTGGGTGGAGCGAACCGGTCAACTGAACGCGA GCGATCACCCCCCTCGACGGAGCGAACCCGAAGAGGAAGAAA ACGAAACGCCACGCAACCGATACAACGCGACCCACCGGCCACCA CTCCGGCGATGTTGTCCGACCGTGAAGAGAGTCGGGCTTTGACACC CGGGCTCCCAGAGCGTGAACGCAACACCCTTGATTCAGAGCGGC GCCGCCGGCCGAAGACAGACATCCGACTACGAGCTTTTTAACCGC AACAACTTAATATACGCTATTGGAGCTGGAGTTACCGCGGCTGCT GGCACCAGACTTGCCCTCCAATGGTTCCTCGTTAAAGGATTTAAAG TGTAATCAATCAATCACGGGGCTCGGAAGAGTCCCGTATCGTTA TTTTTCGCTACTACCTCCCCGTGCCGGGAGTGGGTAATTTGCGCGCC TGCTGCCTTCTTGGATGTGGTAGCCGTTTCTCAGGCTCCCTCTCCG GAATCGAACCCGATTCCCCGTTACCCGTAGCAACCATGGTAGGCG CGTAACCTACCATCGACAGTTGATAAGGCAGACATTTGAAAGATAC GTCGCCGGCTCGAAGGCCATGCGATCGGCGTGAAGTTATCCAGAG TCACCAAATTGGTACGGTTCGCGGACGTTGCCCGCGCTCGCCCC ACTGGTTTGTATCTAATAAAG</p>	1123	561	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	511	7E-142
G4 SSU NS1	No visible infection	Short Subunit	X		<p>GCCGCTAGACGGCGAAACCGCAATGGCTCAATAAATCAGTTATG GTTCTTAGATCCACTCCATCCTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTA GAGCTAATACATGCACTCGAGCCTCGACTGCGCCCGCTTCGCGGTG GGTGCAAGAGAGGTGCTTTTATTAGATCAAACAGTCGGGGCGA GCGGCGGGCAACCGTCGCGCGACCCGTACCAATTTTGGTACTCTG GATAACTTCACGCCGATCGCATGGCCTTCGAGCCGGCGACGTATCT TTCAAATGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGGTTACGCGCTAC CATGGTTGCTACGGGTAACGGGGAATCGGGTTCGATTCCGGAGA GGGAGCCTGAGAAACGGTACCACATCCAAGGAAGGCAGCAGGC GCGCAAATTACCACTCCCGGCACGGGGAGGTAGTGACGAAAAAT AACGATACGGGACTCTCCGAGGCCCGTATTGGAATGAGTACAC TTTAAATCCTTAAACGAGGAACCATTGGAGGGCAAGTCTGGTGCCA GCAGCCGGGTAACCTCAGCTCCAATAGCGTATATTAAGTTGTTG</p>	1160	580	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	544	1E-151

					CGGTAAAAAGCTCGTAGTCGGATGTCTGTCTTCGGCCGGGCGGC GCCGCTCTGAATCAAGGGTGTTCGCTTTCACGCTCTGGGAGCCCGG GTGTCAAAGCCCGACTCTTTCACGCTCGGACAACATCGCCGGAGT GGTGGCCGGTGGGTTCGCGTTGTATCGGTTTCGCGTGGCGTTTCGTTT TCTTCTCTTCGGGGTTCGCTCCGTCGAGGGGGGGGTGATCGCTCG CGTTCAGTTGACGCGGTTTCGCTCCACCCAGTCAATCGTTCGGGGTG CCCTTACC GG GTGTCTCGGGCGGCCGCAACGTTTACTTTGAACA AATTAGAGTGCTCAAAGCAGGTGTATCCCAACGCCTGAATATCGCA GCATGGAATGATGGAATAGGACCTCGGTCCGATTTTGCTGGTCTTT TCTTTTGGACCCGAGGTAATGGTCAATAGAGACGGACGGGGGCAT TCGTACTGCGGCGACAGAGGTGAAATTCTTGGACCGCGCAAGACG AACAAACAGCGAAGGCATTTGCCAAGAATGTTTTCTTGATCAGAAC GAAAGTAGAGGTTTCGAA					
G5 SSU NS4	No visible infection	Short Subunit		X	TTCCCCGGAACCAAAGACTTTGGTTTCCCGGAAGCTGCCCGTCGAG TCATTGGAGTAACTCCGACGGATTGCTGGTTGGCATCGTTTATGGT TAGAACTAGGGCGGTATCTGATCGCCTTCGAACCTCTAACTTTCGTT CTTGATCAAGGAAAACATTCTTGGCAAATGCCTTCGCTGTTGTTCGT CTTGCGGGCGGTCCAAGAATTTACCTCTGTGCGCCGAGTACGAATG CCCCGTCGCTCTATTGACCATTACCTCGGGTCCAAAAGAAAAG ACCAGCAAAATCGGACCGAGGTCCTATTCCATCATTCCATGCTGCG ATATTCAGGCGTTGGGATACACCTGCTTTGAGCACTTAATTTGTTT AAAGTAAACGTTGCCGGCCGCCGAGACACCCGGTGAAGGGCACC CCGAACGATTGACTGGGTGGAGCGAACCGGTCAACTGAACGCGA GCGATCACCCCCCTCGACGGAGCGAACCCGAAGAGGAAGAAA ACGAAACGCCACGCGAACCGATACAACGCGACCCACCGGCCACCA CTCCGGCGATGTTGTCCGACCGTGAAGAGAGTCGGGCTTTGACACC CGGGCTCCCAGAGCGTGAACGCAACACCCTTGATTCAGAGCGGC GCCGCCGGCCGAAGACAGACATCCGACTACGAGCTTTTTAACCGC AACAACTTAATATACGCTATTGGAGCTGGAGTTACCGCGGCTGCT GGCACCAGACTTGCCCTCAATGGTTCCTCGTTAAAGGATTTAAAG TGTA CT CATTCCAATCACGGGGCCTCGGAAGAGTCCCGTATCGTTA TTTTTCGTA CT ACCTCCCCGTGCCGGGAGTGGGTAATTTGCGCGCC TGCTGCCTTCTTGGATGTGGTAGCCGTTTCTCAGGCTCCCTCTCCG GAATCGAACCCCGATTCCCCGTTACCGTAGCAACCATGGTAGGCG CGTAACCTACCATCGACAGTTGATAAGGCAGACATTTGAAAGATAC GTCGCGGGCTCGAAGGCATGCGATCGGCGTGAAGTTATCCAGAGT CACAAA	1063	531	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	500	1E-138
G5 SSU NS1	No visible infection	Short Subunit	X		GCCGCTAGACGGCGAAACCGCAATGGCTCAATAAATCAGTTATG GTTCTTAGATCCACTCCATCCTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTA GAGCTAATACATGCACTCGAGCCTCGACTGCGCCCGCTTCGCGGTG GGTGCAAGAGAGGTGCTTTTATTAGATCAAACCCAGTCGGGGCGA GCGGCGGGCAACCGTCGCGCGACCCGTACCAATTTTGGTGACTCTG GATAACTTACGCCGATCGCATGGCCTTCGAGCCGGCGACGTATCT TTCAAATGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGGTTACGCGCCTAC CATGGTTGCTACGGGTAACGGGGGAATCGGGGTTGATTCCGGAGA GGGAGCTTGAGAAACGGCTACCACATCCAAGGAAGGCAGCAGGC GCGCAAATTACCACTCCCGGCACGGGGAGGTAGTGACGAAAAAT AACGATACGGGACTCTTCCGAGGCCCGTGATTGGAATGAGTACAC TTTAAATCCTTAAACGAGGAACCATTGGAGGGCAAGTCTGGTGCCA	1167	583	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i>	544	1E-151

					GCAGCCGCGGTAAGTCCAGCTCCAATAGCGTATATTAAGTTGTTG CGTTAAAAAGCTCGTAGTCGGATGTCTGTCTTCGGCCGGGCGGC GCCGCTCTGAATCAAGGGTGTTCGCTTTCACGCTCTGGGAGCCCGG GTGTCAAAGCCCGACTCTTTCACGGTCGGACAACATCGCCGGAGT GGTGGCCGGTGGGTCGCGTTGTATCGGTTTCGCGTGGCGTTTCGTTT TCTTCTCTTCGGGGTTCGCTCCGTCGAGGGGGGGGGTGTATCGCTC GCGTTCAGTTGACGCGGTTTCGCTCCACCCAGTCAATCGTTTCGGGGT GCCCTTACCGGGTGTCTCGGGCGGCCGGCAACGTTTACTTTGAAC AAATTAGAGTGCTCAAAGCAGGTGTATCCCAACGCTGAATATCGC AGCATGGAATGATGGAATAGGACCTCGGTCCGATTTTGTGGTCTT TTCTTTGGACCCGAGGTAATGGTCAATAGAGACGGACGGGGGCA TTCGACTGCGGCGACAGAGGTGAAATTCTGGACCGCCGCAAGA CGAACACAGCAAAGGCATTTGCCAAGAATGTTTCTTGATCAAG AACGAAAGTTAGAGGTTGAAAGG					
G4 LSU LR5	No visible infection	Long Subunit	X		TTAAGTCTTTCGCCCCTATACCCAAGTCCGACGATCGATTTGCACGT CAGAATCGCTGCGGACCTCCACCAGGGTTTCCCCTGGCTTCGTCT GGCCAGGCATAGGTCACCATCTTTCGGGTCCCAACGTGTACGCTCT TGTTTCGTCGGCCGACTCGGCACACCGTTTTCGCGGGGCTCGCG AGCATTGCGACGCCAGGGGTTGCGCCGCTCTGTTTCGAGACGGG ATCACCCCTGCGGATGCACCCTCATCGGGCCGCTTCACTTTCATT GCGCTCGCGAGTTTTCGTAATAGACTCGACACTCGCGCACATGTT AGACTCCTTGGTCCGTGTTTCAAGACGGGTGCGGTGGGACCCGACT TCTACTCTCGCTCTGGGCTCCGCGGTTTTCTACAACGTGATGCCA AGCCCTGAAGCTCCAGATCGAAGCCTTAGCGAGATACACGTAGAC AATCCGGGAGGAGACAGGTCACGACCGGGCAGTACTGTTGAGTGA CGCCGCGCTCGTCGAGGGCACACGAGGTAACCCAAAAGTCTGTA CGAACGCCCGTATAACAGACACCCAGTCCGTCGCGGAGTCCCTACT AGGCCCCCACTTTCGCGACCTTGGCGCGGCTAATGCGGTCTCGCC AACGAACAGAGCCGCAAAATCAAGTCCGTCTTTCGACGAGAGG GCATGCAACCAAGTCCCGGGAGCGGGGGCTCGTTTCGACCTTCGAG GGCCACCCGTTTAAACCCCTGAACGGTTTTCACGACTCTTGAATC TCTCTCAAAGTTCTTTCACTTTCCTCGCGTACTTGTTCGCTAT CGGTCTCGTGGCGATATTTAGCCTTAGAAGGAGTTTACCTCCCGCTT AGGGCTGCACGCTCAAGCAACCCGACTCTTGGGAAGGGATCCGAT GCACGGTCTCGGCTCGTCTAAGCTACGGGCTGACACCCTCTGTGG GTTGCTCGCCCCGTTTCATGGAGACTTGGACGATATATACCGGACAG GCGCGCACGATCCTCCGAACACCACATTCTCGCACCCGCTCAA CCGGGCGCGAGGTTTCGGTCTGGGCTCATCCCTGTTTCGCTCGCCG TACTAAGGGAATCCTTGTAGTTTCTTTTC	1135	567	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	262	5E-67
G4 LSU LROR	No visible infection	Long Subunit	X		GGATTCCTTAGTAGCGCGGAGCGAACTGGGATGAGCCAGCACC GAACCTCGCGCCCGTTGAGCGGGTGCCGAGGAATGTGGTGTTCG GGAGGATCGTGCAGCCTGTCCGGTATATATCGTCCAAGTCTCAT GAACGGGGCGAGCAACCCACAGAGGGTGTTCAGGCCGTAGCTTAG ACGAGCCGAGACCGTGCATCGGATCCCTTCCAAGAGTCGGGTTGC TTGAGCGTGCAGCCCTAAGCGGGAGGTAACTCCTTCTAAGGCTAA ATATCGCCACGAGACCGATAGCGAACAAGTACCGCGAGGGAAAGT TGAAAAGAATTTGAAGAGAGAGTTCAAGAGTGCGTGAAACCGTT CAGGGGGTTAAACGGGTGGGCCCTCGAAGGTGCAACGAGCCCCG CTCCCGCACTTGGTTGCATGCCCTGCTGCGAAGAGACCGACTT	1140	570	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	237	2E-59

					GATTTGGCGGCTCTGTTTCGTTGGCGAGGACCGCATTAGCCGCGCCA AGGTCGCAAGTGGGGGGCCTAGTAGGACTCCGCGACCGACTGGG TGTCTGTTATACGGGGCGTTGTTAGCGAGTTTTGGGTTACCTCGT GTGCCCTCGACGAGCGGGCGTCACTCAACAGTACTGCCGGTCTGT GACCTGTCTCCTCCCGGATTGTCTACGTGTATCTCGTAGAGGCTTC GATCTGGAGCTTCAGGGCTTGGCATCACGTTGTAGAAAACCGCGG AGGCCAGAGCGGAGAGTAGAAGTCGGGTCCCACCCGACCCGTCT TGAAACACGGACCAAGGAGTCTAACATGTGCGCGAGTGTGCGAGT CTATTACGAAACTCGCGAGGCGCAATGAAAGTGAAGCGGCCCGGA TGAGGGTGCATCCGCGAGGGGTGATCCCGTCTCGAACAGAGCGGG CGCAACCCTGGGCGTCCGAATGCTCGCGAGGCCCGGTCAAACG GTGTGCCGAGTCGGCCGGACGAACCAAGAGCGTACACGTTGGGAC CCGAAAGATGGTGACCTATGCCTGGCCAGGACGAAGCCAGGGGAA ACCCTGGTGGAGTCCGCGAGGATTCTGACGTGCAAATCGATCGTC GGAGTTGGGTAAGGGGCGAAAGACTAATCGAACCTCTAGTAGCTG GTCCC					
G5 LSU LR5	No visible infection	Long Subunit		X	GTTTCGATTAGTCTTTGCCCCCTATACCCAACCTCCGACGATCGATTTG CACGTCAGAATCGCTGCGGACCTCTACCAGGGTTTTCCCTGGCTTC GTCCTGGCCAGGCATAGGTCACCATCTTTGGGTCCCAACGTGTAC GCTCTTGGTTCGTCCGGCCGACTCGGCACACCGTTTGACCGGGGCC TCGCGAGCATTGCGACGCCAGGGGTTGCGCCCGCTCTGTTGAGA CGGGATCACCCCTCGCGGATGCACCCTCATCGGGGCGCTTCACTT TCATTGCGCTCGCGAGTTTCGTAATAGACTCGACGACTCGCGCAC ATGTTAGACTCCTTGGTCCGTGTTTCAAGACGGGTCGGGTGGGACC CGACTTCTACTCTCCGCTCTGGGCCTCCGCGTTTTTCTACAACGTGA TGCCAAGCCCTGAAGCTCCAGATCGAAGCCTCTAGCGAGATACACG TAGACAATCCGGGAGGAGACAGGTACGACCGGGCAGTACTGTTG AGTGACGCCGCGCTCGTCGAGGGCACACGAGGTAACCCAAAACCTC GCTAACGAACGCCCCGTATAACAGACACCCAGTCGGTCCGCGGAGTC CTACTAGGCCCCCACTTGGCGACCTTGGCGCGGCTAATGCGGTCC TCGCCAACGAACAGAGCCGCAAAATCAAGTCGGTCTCTTCGAGCA GAGGGCATGCAACCAAGTCCCGGGAGCGGGGCTCGTTCGACCTT CGAGGGCCACCCGTTTAAACCCCTGAACGTTTTACGCACTCTTG AACTCTCTCTCAAAGTTCTTTCAACTTTCCCTCGCGGACTTGTTC GCTATCGGTCTCGTGGCGATATTTAGCCTTAGAAGGAGTTTACCTCC CGCTTAGGGCTGCACGCTCAAGCAACCCGACTTTGGGAAGGGAT CCGATGCACGGTCTCGGCTCGTCTAAGCTACGGGCTGACACCCTC TGTGGGTTGCTCGCCCGTTTCATGGAGACTTGGACGATATATACCG GACAGGCGCGCACGATCCTCCCGAACCCACATTCTCGGCACCCG CTCAACCGGGCGCGAGGTTGCGGTGCTGGGCTCATCCTGTTGCTC GCCGCTACTAAGGGAATCCTTGTAGTTTCTTT	1138	569	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	260	2E-66
G5 LSU LROR	No visible infection	Long Subunit	X		TAACAGGATTCCTTAGTAGCGGCGAGCGAACAGGGATGAGCCCA GCACCGAACCTCGCGCCCGTTGAGCGGGTGCCGAGGAATGTGGT GTTCCGGGAGGATCGTGCGCCTGTCCGGTATATATCGTCCAAGTC TCCATGAACGGGGCGAGCAACCCACAGAGGGTGTGAGGCCCGTAG CTTAGACGAGCCGAGACCGTGCATCGGATCCCTTCCAAGAGTCGG GTTGCTTAGAGCTGCAGCCCTAAGCGGGAGGTAACCTCCTTCTAAG GCTAAATATCGCCACGAGACCGATAGCGAACAGTACCGCGAGGG AAAGTTGAAAAGAACTTTGAAGAGAGAGTTCAAGAGTGCGTGAAA	1141	570	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	244	1E-61

				CCGTT CAGGGGTTAAACGGGTGGGCCCTCGAAGGTCGAACGAGC CCCCGCTCCCGGCACTTGTTGCATGCCCTCTGCTGCGAAGAGACC GACTTGATTTGGCGGCTCTGTTTCGTTGGCGAGGACCGCATTAGCCG CGCCAAGGTCCGCAAGTGGGGGGCCTAGTAGGACTCCGCGACCGA CTGGGTGTCTGTTATACGGGGCGTTCGTTAGCGAGTTTTGGGTTAC CTCGTGTGCCCTCGACGAGCGGGCGTCACTCAACAGTACTGCCCC GTCGTGACCTGTCTCCTCCCGATTGTCTACGTGTATCTCGCTAGAG GCTTCGATCTGGAGCTTCAGGGCTTGGCATCACGTTGTAGAAAACC GCGGAGGCCCAAGCGGAGAGTAGAAGTCGGGTCCACCCGACCC GTCTTGAACACGGACCAAGGAGTCTAACATGTGCGCGAGTCGTC GAGTCTATTACGAAACTCGCGAGGCGCAATGAAAGTGAAGCGGCC CCGATGAGGGTGCATCCGCGAGGGGTGATCCCGTCTCGAACAGAG CGGGCGCAACCCTGGGCGTCCGAATGCTCGCGAGGCCCGGTCA AACGGTGTGCCGAGTCGGCCGGACGAACCAAGAGCGTACACGTTG GGACCCGAAAGATGGTGACCTATGCCTGGCCAGGACGAAGCCAGG GGAAACCCTGGTGGAGGTCGCAGCGATTCTGACGTGCAATCGATC GTCGGAGTTGGGATAGGGGCGAAGACTAATCGAACATCTAGTACT GGTCCC				
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Supplementary figures Chapter 4

Figure S11: Microscopic pictures of the stressor treatments; (A) *Aspergillus* infection treatment: hyphae and surrounding spores stained with dapi with 400 x magnification under UV fluorescence (for characterization process, see further) and (B) *Microcystis* treatment: Colony of *Microcystis* surrounded with individual cells with 160 x magnification.

Figure S12: Rarefaction curve of the raw sequencing data. Number of reads are represented on the x-axis, number of ASVs are represented on the y-axis. (A) overview (B) zoomed in on the first 5000 reads.

Figure S13: Unionplots representing the unique and shared ASVs between donor bacterioplankton and recipient *Daphnia* in the (A) laboratory treatment and (B) natural treatment. L=laboratory treatment, N=natural treatment, S=stressor treatment (fungus, cyanobacterium and combination), CTL=control treatment, D=donor bacterioplankton.

Figure S14: Pearson regression between (A) Fecundity and body size, and (B) Survival and Fecundity. Non-adjusted p-values and correlation coefficient (R) are noted per figure.

Figure S15: Pearson regression between (A) Survival, (B) Fecundity, (C) Body size and ASV richness of the gut microbial community of recipient *Daphnia*. Non-adjusted p-values and correlation coefficient (R) are noted per figure.

Figure S16: ggplot representing the ASVs at family level that were significantly different between the stressor x microbiome x genotype interaction. Colors indicate the stressor treatments: Grey= control treatment, Yellow= *Aspergillus* infection, Red= *Microcystis* infection, Orange= Combination treatment with both *Aspergillus* and *Microcystis* infection.

A

B

Figure S17: ggplot representing the ASVs at family level that were significantly different between the different stressor treatments within the (A) lab and (B) natural microbial water treatment. Colors indicate the stressor treatments: Grey= control treatment, Yellow= *Aspergillus* infection, Red= *Microcystis* infection, Orange= Combination treatment with both *Aspergillus* and *Microcystis* infection.

Figure S18: Part (155 to 310 nucleotides) of the multiple sequence alignment pattern of the sample sequences with *Aspergillus aculeatus* ATCC 16872. Sequences of *Daphnia* with a visible and no visible infection, together with the *Aspergillus aculeatus* ATCC 16872 strain are aligned (sample names are shown in the left column). Color represents a specific type of nucleotide that matches with the *Aspergillus aculeatus* strain. Hyphen (-) represents a gap where no match between the nucleotides of the *Aspergillus aculeatus* strain and the aligned sequence of the sample is found. Asterisk on the top represents the nucleotides that are common in all the aligned sequences